

LATTICE EQUABLE QUADRILATERALS III: TANGENTIAL AND EXTANGENTIAL CASES

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Abstract

A lattice equable quadrilateral is a quadrilateral in the plane whose vertices lie on the integer lattice and which is equable in the sense that its area equals its perimeter. This paper treats the tangential and extangential cases. We show that up to Euclidean motions, there are only 6 convex tangential lattice equable quadrilaterals, while the concave ones are arranged in 7 infinite families, each being given by a well known Diophantine equation of order 2 in 3 variables. On the other hand, apart from the kites, up to Euclidean motions there is only one concave extangential lattice equable quadrilateral, while there are infinitely many convex ones.

1. Introduction

A *lattice equable quadrilateral* (LEQ for short) is a quadrilateral whose vertices lie on the integer lattice \mathbb{Z}^2 and which is equable in the sense that its area equals its perimeter. This paper is a continuation of the work [3], which treated lattice equable parallelograms, and [4], which treated lattice equable kites, trapezoids and cyclic quadrilaterals, but this paper can be read independently of the previous two. Here we examine convex and concave LEQs that are either *tangential*, i.e., their sides or extended sides are tangent to an incircle, or *extangential*, i.e., their sides or extended sides are tangent to an excircle.

Before stating our main results, let us make some general remarks about the importance and occurrence of tangential and extangential LEQs, up to Euclidean motions. Remarkably, tangential and extangential LEQs apparently constitute a

large component of the overall set of LEQs. For example, apart from parallelograms and trapezoids, we know of only one convex LEQ that is neither tangential nor extangential. This is the LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (2, 0), (8, 8), (8, 15)$ and side lengths 2, 10, 7, 17. There seem to be significantly more tangential LEQs than extangential LEQs, within a ball of any given radius of sufficient size. The tangential LEQs are mainly concave; indeed, as we show in Corollary 1, there are only 6 convex tangential LEQs. The extangential LEQs are mainly convex; we show in Corollary 3 that there is only one concave non-kite extangential LEQ. Kites which are not parallelograms are both tangential and extangential, and they are the only LEQs with this property.

Consider a tangential LEQ $OABC$ whose sides OA, AB, BC, CO have length a, b, c, d , respectively, which therefore are integers [3, Remark 2]. The key to our results on tangential LEQs is the observation that a certain pair of functions of the side lengths take a very restricted range of possible values. The functions are as follows.

Definition 1. For a tangential LEQ $OABC$, let

$$\sigma = \frac{ad + bc + 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}}{16 + (a - b)^2}, \quad \tau = \frac{ab + cd - 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}}{16 + (a - d)^2},$$

where $\delta = 1$ if B lies within the circumcircle of the triangle OAC , and $\delta = -1$ otherwise.

In fact, as we show in Subsection 2.3, the functions σ and τ can only take the seven possible values 2, 3, 5, 9, $9/8, 5/4, 3/2$, and moreover $\frac{1}{\sigma} + \frac{1}{\tau} = 1$. In particular, in each case at least one of σ, τ is an integer and belongs to $\{2, 3, 5, 9\}$.

For each of the seven possibilities for the pair (σ, τ) , we show that the side lengths satisfy a certain corresponding Diophantine equation, and conversely, solutions to the equation, along with some auxiliary conditions, lead to the existence of a corresponding tangential LEQ. There is a certain redundancy both in the statement of the seven results and their proofs, so we have been at pains to present the results in as compact a form as possible. The statements of the resulting theorem and its converse are rather cumbersome, but considerable saving is attained in the long run. Before stating the results, note that for a tangential LEQ $OABC$ with successive side lengths a, b, c, d , we see in Remark 9 that by making a reflection if necessary, we may assume that a and c are even in the case $\sigma = \tau = 2$. Our classification result for tangential LEQs is then as follows.

Theorem 1. *Suppose that $OABC$ is a tangential LEQ with vertices O, A, B, C in positive cyclic order and successive side lengths a, b, c, d , respectively. Suppose also that if $OABC$ is concave, then its reflex angle is at B . Without loss of generality we also assume that a and c are even in the case $\sigma = \tau = 2$. Then the following conditions hold:*

- (i) $|c - b|\tau < a + c$, (ii) $(a + d)\tau > a + c$, (iii) $(b + c)\tau \neq a + c$.

Moreover, $OABC$ is convex if and only if $(b + c)\tau > a + c$. Furthermore, there are two cases:

- (a) If $\tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$, then $a, \tau b$ have the same parity and setting $u = \frac{\tau b - a}{2}, v = \frac{\tau b + a}{2}$, we have

$$(2\tau)^2 + u^2 = v^2 - \left(v - \frac{\tau - 1}{2}c\right)^2. \tag{1}$$

- (b) If $\sigma \in \{3, 5, 9\}$, then $a, \sigma d$ have the same parity and setting $u = \frac{\sigma d - a}{2}, v = \frac{\sigma d + a}{2}$, we have

$$(2\sigma)^2 + u^2 = v^2 - \left(v - \frac{\sigma - 1}{2}c\right)^2. \tag{2}$$

We now state the converse result.

Theorem 2. Let $x \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$ and suppose we have an integer solution (u, v, c) of the Diophantine equation

$$(2x)^2 + u^2 = v^2 - \left(v - \frac{x - 1}{2}c\right)^2 \tag{3}$$

for which $u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{x}$ and $c > 0$, and further that c is even when $x = 2$ and that c is not divisible by 3 if $x = 3$. Then we have the following.

- (a) Let $t = x, a = v - u, b = (v + u)/t, d = a + c - b$, and suppose the following conditions hold:

- (i) $|c - b|t < a + c$, (ii) $(a + d)t > a + c$, (iii) $(b + c)t \neq a + c$.

Then there is a tangential LEQ $OABC$ with successive side lengths a, b, c, d for which $(\sigma, \tau) = \left(\frac{t}{t-1}, t\right)$.

- (b) Let $s = x, a = v - u, d = (v + u)/s, b = a + c - d$ and suppose that the above conditions (i) – (iii) hold for $t = \frac{s}{s-1}$ and that $b > 0$. Then there is a tangential LEQ $OABC$ with successive side lengths a, b, c, d for which $(\sigma, \tau) = (s, t)$.

Furthermore, in both of the above cases, if $OABC$ is concave, then the reflex angle is at B .

Corollary 1. Up to Euclidean motions, there are only six convex tangential LEQs:

- the 4×4 square,
- the isosceles trapezoid of side lengths 5, 2, 5, 8,

- the right trapezoid of side lengths 5, 3, 4, 6,
- the equable rhombus of side length 5,
- the equable kite of side lengths 3 and 15,
- the LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (40, 9), (36, 12), (35, 12)$, and side lengths 37, 1, 5, 41.

Corollary 2. *The incenter of a tangential LEQ is an integer lattice point in the cases where $\sigma, \tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 5/4, 3/2\}$.*

Examples where $\sigma, \tau \in \{9, 9/8\}$ and the incenter is not an integer lattice point are given in Example 1.

We now turn to our results on extangential LEQs. Consider an extangential LEQ $OABC$ whose sides OA, AB, BC, CO have length a, b, c, d , respectively. We introduce functions analogous to those of Definition 1. More precisely, it is convenient to define functions Σ, T analogous to $8\sigma, 8\tau$, as follows.

Definition 2. For an extangential LEQ $OABC$, let

$$\Sigma = 8 \cdot \frac{ad + bc + 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16 + (a - c)^2},$$

$$T = 8(a + b)^2 \cdot \frac{ab + cd + 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2},$$

where $\delta = 1$ if B lies within the circumcircle of the triangle OAC , and $\delta = -1$ otherwise.

The functions Σ, T are not constrained to take only a finite number of possible values, as was the case with σ, τ . So the study of extangential LEQs is somewhat more complicated than that of tangential LEQs. Our main result is as follows.

Theorem 3. *If a non-kite extangential LEQ $OABC$ has successive side lengths a, b, c, d , then Σ, T are integers and one of the following holds:*

- (a) $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$ or $(18, 50)$,
- (b) $(\Sigma, T) = (5m^2, 5m^2 + 5)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 10n^2 = -1$ and $(5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$.
- (c) $(\Sigma, T) = (m^2, m^2 + 1)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 2n^2 = -1$ and $(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$.

The situation concerning case (a) of the above theorem is very satisfactory. We examine the two possibilities for (Σ, T) in Subsection 3.3, and study the corresponding extangential LEQs up to Euclidean motions. We explicitly classify all

LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$; there is a single infinite family corresponding to solutions of the negative Pell equation $x^2 - 2y^2 = -1$. For $(\Sigma, T) = (18, 50)$, we prove that there is precisely one extangential LEQ; this isolated example has side lengths $(a, b, c, d) = (13, 2, 5, 10)$ and is shown on the right of Figure 10.

We do not give a complete classification for case (b) of the above theorem. However, in Subsection 3.3 we consider $m = 3$, which is the smallest value of m for which $m^2 - 10n^2 = -1$ has a solution. Here $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$, and we give explicit formulas for infinitely many such LEQs. The side lengths of the first three members of this family are given in Table 5. One sees that the lengths grow very rapidly. The next possible value of m is $m = 117$; see Remark 30. Here $(\Sigma, T) = (5 \cdot 117^2, 5 \cdot 117^2 + 5)$. In Example 5, we exhibit the smallest possible extangential LEQ with this (Σ, T) pair; it has perimeter $\cong 3 \cdot 10^{27}$.

We do not know if there are any LEQs satisfying condition (c) of the above theorem.

Open Problem. Does there exist an integer solution (m, n) of the negative Pell equation $m^2 - 2n^2 = -1$, for which the Diophantine equation $(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$ has an integer solution for (Y, Z) .

Even if there were such a solution, it would still be necessary to prove that there are lattice vertices that realize the corresponding side lengths. We show at the very end of the paper that if there is an extangential LEQ corresponding to case (c) of Theorem 3, then its perimeter is at least 10^{718} .

As a consequence of our study, we have the following.

Corollary 3. *Up to Euclidean motions, there is only one concave non-kite extangential LEQ; it is the LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (12, 5), (10, 5), (6, 8)$ and side lengths $(13, 2, 5, 10)$.*

Theorem 3 is proved by reducing it to the following number theoretic result.

Theorem 4. *Let $y, z, k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k > 16$ and $k > yz$. Suppose that the numbers*

$$\Sigma := \frac{8(z^2 + k)}{k - 16}, \quad \Sigma' := \frac{y^2 \Sigma}{k} \quad \text{and} \quad x := \sqrt{\frac{k(\Sigma + \Sigma')}{8}}$$

are all integers. Then either

- (a) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (9, 9), (12, 24), (16, 16), (24, 12), (10, 40), (40, 10)$ or $(18, 32)$,
- (b) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (5m^2, 5)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 10n^2 = -1$ and $(5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$,
- (c) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (m^2, 1)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 2n^2 = -1$ and $(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$.

The proof of this theorem is established by writing the ratio $\frac{\Sigma'}{\Sigma}$ as $\frac{u}{v}$, with $\gcd(u, v) = 1$, and considering the 6 cases according to whether the pair (u, v) is respectively (odd,even), (odd,odd), or (even,odd), and whether the 2-adic order of the even number (respectively $v, u + v$ or u) is even or odd. Each of the six cases is conducted by a series of contradiction arguments.

The paper is organized in two Sections. Section 2 covers tangential LEQs. Subsection 2.1 develops some general results true for all tangential quadrilaterals. Subsection 2.2 gives explicit examples: we present calculations of the incenters of LEQs that are kites, and we give an infinite nested family of non-dart concave tangential LEQs. Subsection 2.3 gives a series of lemmas on tangential LEQs leading to the definition of the key functions σ and τ , and their properties. In Subsection 2.4 we give the proof of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1. Subsection 2.5 is the most substantial part of Section 2. Here we prove Theorem 2 and Corollary 2. The final subsection of Section 2, Subsection 2.6, gives more examples. In particular, we show that there are infinitely many LEQs for each of the seven possible choices of (σ, τ) .

Section 3 treats extangential LEQs. Subsections 3.1 and 3.2 follow the general plan adopted in Subsections 2.1 and 2.3 of Section 2; Subsection 3.1 presents some general results for all extangential quadrilaterals, and Subsection 3.2 gives a series of lemmas leading to the definition of the functions Σ and T , and their properties. Subsection 3.3 treats extangential LEQs in the cases where $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18), (18, 50)$ and $(45, 50)$. Subsection 3.4 shows how Theorem 3 can be deduced from Theorem 4. Subsection 3.5 is the longest subsection in the paper; here we prove Theorem 4. This subsection also contains the proof of Corollary 3, see Remark 32. Finally, in Subsection 3.6 we discuss the Open Problem presented above.

We will use the following notation. In this paper, a quadrilateral $OABC$ is defined by four vertices O, A, B, C , no three of which are colinear, such that the line segments OA, AB, BC, CO have no interior points of intersection; that is, our quadrilaterals have no self-intersections. We always write the vertices O, A, B, C in positive (counterclockwise) cyclic order, and if O, A, B, C is concave, then the labelling is chosen so that the reflex angle is at B . We use the notation $K(OABC)$ for area and $P(OABC)$ for perimeter. Throughout this paper, for ease of expression, we often simply write K for $K(OABC)$, and P for $P(OABC)$, and we abbreviate the triangle areas $K(COA), K(OAB), K(ABC), K(BCO)$ as K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C , respectively. We denote the lengths of the sides OA, AB, BC, CO by the letters a, b, c, d , respectively. The lengths of the diagonals OB, AC are denoted p, q , respectively; see Figure 1. We use vector notation, such as \overrightarrow{AB} . But we use the same symbol, A say, for the vertex A and its position vector \overrightarrow{OA} . Finally, by *Euclidean motions*, we mean both the orientation preserving and orientation reversing kinds; that is, we consider the group generated by translations, rotations and reflections. In this paper, we employ the term *positive* in the strict sense. So $\mathbb{N} = \{n \in \mathbb{Z} \mid n > 0\}$.

We used Mathematica and Maple for many of the calculations and algebraic

manipulations in this paper. The factorizations of large numbers conducted at the end of the paper were performed using Dario Alpern’s integer factorization calculator [5]. We remark that Alpern has a very nice continued fraction calculator, and a quadratic Diophantine equation solver that we also found useful [6].

Figure 1: Illustration of some of the notation used.

2. Tangential Quadrilaterals

2.1. Basic Notions for Tangential LEQs

It is well known and easy to see that a triangle is equable if and only if its incircle has radius 2. A quadrilateral that has an incircle is said to be *tangential*, or *circumscribable* [29, 18, 23, 26]. Obviously, a tangential quadrilateral is equable if and only if its incircle has radius 2. Pitot’s theorem says that a quadrilateral with successive side lengths a, b, c, d is tangential if and only if the following equation holds:

$$a + c = b + d \tag{4}$$

(see [36], [10, p. 62–64] and [25]). While Pitot’s Theorem is usually stated only for convex quadrilaterals, it also holds in the concave case. Indeed, consider a concave quadrilateral $OABC$ with reflex angle at B . Let A' denote the point of intersection of the side OA and the extension of side BC . Similarly, let C' denote the point of intersection of the side OC and the extension of side AB . Let a, b, c, d denote the lengths of OA, AB, BC, CO , respectively, and similarly, let a', b', c', d' denote the lengths of $OA', A'B, BC', C'O$. Then it is easy to see that Equation (4) holds if and only if $a' + c' = b' + d'$; see [10, Problem 2.62]. That is, $OABC$ is tangential if and only if $OA'BC'$ is tangential.

Figure 2 gives an example of a concave tangential LEQ. Note that, as this example shows, for a concave tangential LEQ $OABC$, while the associated convex tangential quadrilateral $OA'BC'$ is equable, it may fail to have integer sides or have its vertices on lattice points.

Figure 2: A concave tangential LEQ with side lengths 16,5,2,13.

For the rest of this subsection, $OABC$ denotes a tangential (convex or concave) quadrilateral, with vertices in counterclockwise cyclic order, and a, b, c, d denote the lengths of the sides OA, AB, BC, CO , respectively.

Proposition 1. *If $OABC$ is tangential, then $OABC$ is a kite if and only if one of the diagonals divides $OABC$ into two triangles of equal area.*

Proof. Obviously, if $OABC$ is a kite, then its axis of symmetry diagonals divides $OABC$ into two triangles of equal area. Conversely, as the triangle OAB has side lengths a, b, p , Heron’s formula [33, Chap. 6.7] for the area gives

$$K_A = \sqrt{s(s-a)(s-b)(s-p)},$$

where $s = \frac{a+b+p}{2}$ is the semi-perimeter. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} 16K_A^2 &= (a+b+p)(a+b-p)(a-b+p)(-a+b+p) \\ &= -(a^2-b^2)^2 + 2(a^2+b^2)p^2 - p^4. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, from triangle OBC , we have $16K_C^2 = -(c^2-d^2)^2 + 2(c^2+d^2)p^2 - p^4$. Hence, subtracting,

$$2(a^2-d^2+b^2-c^2)p^2 = 16(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a^2-b^2)^2 - (c^2-d^2)^2. \tag{5}$$

Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} a^2-d^2+b^2-c^2 &= (a-d)(a+d) + (b-c)(b+c) \\ &= (a-d)(a+d+b+c) = 2(a+c)(a-d), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (a^2-b^2)^2 - (c^2-d^2)^2 &= (a-b)^2(a+b)^2 - (d-c)^2(c+d)^2 \\ &= (a-b)^2(a+b+c+d)(a+b-c-d) = 4(a-d)(a+c)(a-b)^2. \end{aligned}$$

So Equation (5) gives

$$(a + c)(a - d)p^2 = 4(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a - d)(a + c)(a - b)^2. \tag{6}$$

Now, assume that $K_A = K_C$. Then Equation (6) gives $(a - d)p^2 = (a - d)(a - b)^2$. Notice that $p = \pm(a - b)$ is impossible, as otherwise the triangle OAB would be degenerate. Hence, $a = d$. Moreover, as $K_A = K_C$, the points A, C are equidistant from the line through O, B . So the triangles OAB and OBC are congruent, and hence $OABC$ is a kite. Clearly, by considering triangles OAC and BCA , the same argument would hold if $K_O = K_B$. \square

It is well known that the incenter I of a convex tangential quadrilateral lies on the *Newton line* \mathcal{N}_C , which is the line passing through the midpoints of the two diagonals; see [8, Chap. 7.5], [9, Chap. 2.7] and [13]. This is also true for concave tangential quadrilaterals, because the midpoints of the three diagonals of a complete quadrilateral are collinear (see [39] for 23 proofs of this fact). Let M_A, M_O denote the midpoint of the diagonals AC, OB , respectively; see Figures 3 and 4. Notice that M_A, M_O are distinct, and the Newton line unambiguously defined, if and only if $OABC$ is not a parallelogram.

Figure 3: The Newton line of a convex tangential quadrilateral.

Figure 4: The Newton line of a concave tangential quadrilateral.

Proposition 2. *If $OABC$ is tangential and is not a parallelogram, then $OABC$ is a kite if and only if the Newton line $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{L}}$ contains one of the diagonals.*

Proof. It is obvious that if $OABC$ is a kite, then $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{L}}$ is the axis of symmetry of $OABC$ and hence contains a diagonal. Conversely, suppose $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{L}}$ coincides with one of the diagonals, say OB . As $M_A \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{L}}$, we have $K(OAM_A) = K(COM_A)$ and $K(ABM_A) = K(BCM_A)$, and hence

$$K_A = K(OAM_A) + K(ABM_A) = K(COM_A) + K(BCM_A) = K_C.$$

Thus the diagonal OB divides $OABC$ into two triangles of equal area. Then $OABC$ is a kite by Proposition 1. □

Remark 1. For further equivalent conditions for a tangential quadrilateral to be a kite, see [19].

The radius r of the incircle, called the *inradius*, is given by the following obvious formula:

$$r = \frac{K}{a + c}.$$

We will be mainly interested in the equable case, where $r = 2$, but in this subsection we consider the general case as it provides a useful comparison for results on the exradius of extangential quadrilaterals, which we will consider below in Section 3.

Proposition 3. *If $OABC$ is tangential, we have the following two expressions for the incenter I :*

$$(a) \quad I = \frac{r}{2} \frac{aC + dA}{K_O}, \quad (b) \quad I = A + \frac{r}{2} \frac{a(B - A) - bA}{K_A}.$$

Proof. Suppose A, C have coordinates $(a_1, a_2), (c_1, c_2)$, respectively, let $I = (i_1, i_2)$ be the incenter. Considering the area of triangle AIO , we have $ra = a_1i_2 - a_2i_1$. Similarly, from the area of triangle COI , we have $rc = -c_1i_2 + c_2i_1$. Hence,

$$r \begin{pmatrix} a \\ c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -a_2 & a_1 \\ c_2 & -c_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{and so} \quad \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{r}{a_1c_2 - a_2c_1} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & a_1 \\ c_2 & a_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a \\ c \end{pmatrix}.$$

That is, $I = \frac{r}{2} \frac{aC + dA}{K_O}$, which is expression (a) in the statement of the proposition. Similarly, by considering triangles BIA and OAI we obtain (b). □

Note that the above proposition holds in both convex and concave cases, but in the latter case, with a reflex angle at B for example, the signed area K_B is negative. For more on the incenter of tangential quadrilaterals, see [7].

Proposition 4. *For a tangential equable quadrilateral $OABC$, one has*

$$(K_A - (a + b))(K_O - (a + d)) = bd - ac.$$

Proof. Equating the two expressions for I from the above proposition, with $r = 2$, and taking the vector cross product by C on the right, gives

$$d = K_O + \frac{a(K_C - K_O) - bK_O}{K_A},$$

so $K_O K_A - dK_A + aK_C - (a + b)K_O = 0$. Thus, as $K_C = 2(a + c) - K_A$, we have $K_O K_A - (a + d)K_A - (a + b)K_O + 2a(a + c) = 0$. The required identity is then obtained by factorizing, using the fact that $2a(a + c) = (a + b)(a + d) - (bd - ac)$ since $a + c = b + d$. \square

Since the incentre I lies on Newton line, I is of the form $\lambda M_A + (1 - \lambda)M_O$, for some $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. The following result will use the fact that for a (arbitrary) quadrilateral $OABC$, one has the following elementary vector equation:

$$K_O B = K_C A + K_A C. \tag{7}$$

This equation is proved in [1], as an application of the vector triple product (a generalization to higher dimensions is given in [2]). Alternately, one can simply notice that the vector products $A \times (K_C A + K_A C - K_O B)$ and $B \times (K_C A + K_A C - K_O B)$ are both zero, so Equation (7) follows as A, B are linearly independent in our case.

Proposition 5. *If $OABC$ is tangential but is neither a parallelogram nor a kite, we have the following two expressions for the coordinate λ :*

$$(a) \quad \lambda = \frac{r(a - b)}{2K_O - r(a + c)}, \quad (b) \quad \lambda = 1 - \frac{r(b - c)}{2K_A - r(a + c)}.$$

Furthermore, if $OABC$ is a kite, then the first of the above expressions for λ holds if $OABC$ is not a rhombus and we relabel the vertices if necessary so that OB is the axis of symmetry.

Proof. By definition, $I = \lambda M_A + (1 - \lambda)M_O = \lambda \frac{A+C}{2} + (1 - \lambda) \frac{B}{2}$, so using Equation (7) to eliminate B , we have

$$I = \frac{\lambda K_O + (1 - \lambda)K_C}{2K_O} A + \frac{\lambda K_O + (1 - \lambda)K_A}{2K_O} C.$$

Comparing with Proposition 3(a) gives $rd = \lambda K_O + (1 - \lambda)K_C$ and $ra = \lambda K_O + (1 - \lambda)K_A$, so

$$\lambda(K_O - K_C) = rd - K_C \tag{8}$$

$$\lambda(K_O - K_A) = ra - K_A. \tag{9}$$

Adding Equation (9) to Equation (8) and using $K_A + K_C = r(a + c)$ gives $\lambda(2K_O - r(a + c)) = r(d - c)$. If $OABC$ is not a kite, then by Proposition 1, $K_O \neq K_B$, so

Family	Equation	M	B	$I_{n,i}$	$\lambda_{n,i}$
$K1$	$n^2 - 5i^2 = 4$	$\frac{1}{2}(n + 5i)(2, 1)$	$n(2, 1)$	$\frac{n+i}{2}(2, 1)$	$1/5$
$K2$	$n^2 - 5i^2 = 1$	$(2n + 5i)(2, 1)$	$4n(2, 1)$	$2(n + 2i)(2, 1)$	$4/5$
$K3$	$n^2 - 2i^2 = 1$	$(n + 2i)(2, 2)$	$4n(1, 1)$	$2(n + i)(1, 1)$	$1/2$
$K4$	$2n^2 - i^2 = 1$	$(4n + 3i)(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})$	$12n(1, 1)$	$2(3n + 2i)(1, 1)$	$8/9$

Table 1: The four families of kites.

$2K_O \neq r(a + c)$. If $OABC$ is a kite but not a rhombus, and we relabel the vertices if necessary so that OB is the axis of symmetry, then once again $2K_O \neq r(a + c)$. In either case,

$$\lambda = \frac{r(d - c)}{2K_O - r(a + c)} = \frac{r(a - b)}{2K_O - r(a + c)},$$

as required.

Subtracting Equation (9) from Equation (8) gives $\lambda(K_A - K_C) = r(d - a) + K_A - K_C$. If $OABC$ is not a kite, then once again $2K_O \neq r(a + c)$ by Proposition 1, so

$$\lambda = 1 + \frac{r(d - a)}{K_A - K_C} = 1 - \frac{2(b - c)}{2K_A - r(a + c)}.$$

□

Remark 2. As we mentioned above, it is well known that for a tangential quadrilateral $OABC$, its incenter I lies on the Newton line. It is less commonly mentioned that I lies *between* M_A and M_O ; that is, it lies on the closed line segment between M_A and M_O . This can be proved by an easy geometric argument. We will not require this fact, though for equable tangential quadrilaterals, it follows from the above proposition and Remark 7 below.

2.2. Examples of Tangential LEQs

Of course, the lattice equable kites are tangential. For each of the four families $K1 - K4$ of [4, Theorem 1] we use Propositions 3 and 5 to compute the incenter $I_{n,i}$ and the parameter $\lambda_{n,i}$ for which $I_{n,i} = \lambda_{n,i}M + (1 - \lambda_{n,i})\frac{B}{2}$, where $M = M_A$. We omit the details, which are completely routine. The results are given in Table 1. Notice that in family $K1$, $n + i$ is even. Hence, $I_{n,i}$ is a lattice point for all the families.

We will now exhibit an infinite nested family of non-dart concave tangential LEQs. Let (u_i, v_i) be the i -th solution to the Pell equation $u^2 - 3v^2 = 1$, with initial solution $(u_1, v_1) = (2, 1)$. From the standard theory of Pell equations, one has the recurrences:

$$u_{i+1} = 2u_i + 3v_i, \quad v_{i+1} = u_i + 2v_i. \tag{10}$$

u_i	v_i	A_i	B	A_{i+1}	a_i	b_i	c_i	d_i
2	1	(8,6)	(8,0)	(18,24)	10	6	26	30
7	4	(18,24)	(8,0)	(56,90)	30	26	102	106
26	15	(56,90)	(8,0)	(198,336)	106	102	386	390
97	56	(198,336)	(8,0)	(728,1254)	390	386	1446	1450

Table 2: The first four members of the tangential family.

Let A_i denote the point with coordinates $(x_i, y_i) = (2u_i + 4, 6v_i)$, and let B be the point $(8, 0)$. We will consider the lattice quadrilateral OA_iBA_{i+1} . To verify that OA_iBA_{i+1} has no self-intersection, it suffices to calculate the vector cross products $\overrightarrow{OA_i} \times \overrightarrow{OA_{i+1}}$ and $\overrightarrow{BA_{i+1}} \times \overrightarrow{BA_i}$, using the recurrence relations (10), and see that they are both positive. We leave the details to the reader.

Let the lengths of the segments $OA_i, A_iB, BA_{i+1}, A_{i+1}O$ be denoted a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i , respectively. We have

$$a_i^2 = x_i^2 + y_i^2 = 4u_i^2 + 16u_i + 16 + 36v_i^2 = 16u_i^2 + 16u_i + 4 = (4u_i + 2)^2.$$

So $a_i = 4u_i + 2$ and $d_i = a_{i+1}$. Similarly, the distance b_i is given by

$$b_i^2 = (2u_i - 4)^2 + (6v_i)^2 = 4u_i^2 - 16u_i + 16 + 36v_i^2 = 16u_i^2 - 16u_i + 4 = (4u_i - 2)^2.$$

So $b_i = 4u_i - 2$ and $c_i = b_{i+1}$. Thus OA_iBA_{i+1} is tangential because

$$a_i - b_i + c_i - d_j = (4u_i + 2) - (4u_i - 2) + (4u_{i+1} - 2) - (4u_{i+1} + 2) = 0.$$

The perimeter $P(OA_iBA_{i+1})$ of OA_iBA_{i+1} is $a_i + b_i + c_i + d_j = 8(u_i + u_{i+1})$, while the area $K(OA_iBA_{i+1})$ of OA_iBA_{i+1} is $4(y_{i+1} - y_i) = 24(v_{i+1} - v_i)$. Hence, using the recurrence relations (10),

$$\begin{aligned} K(OA_iBA_{i+1}) - P(OA_iBA_{i+1}) &= 24(v_{i+1} - v_i) - 8(u_i + u_{i+1}) \\ &= 24(u_i + v_i) - 8(3u_i + 3v_i) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

So OA_iBA_{i+1} is a LEQ. The vertices and side lengths of the first four members of this family are given in Table 2. The first two members of the family are shown in Figure 5.

By Proposition 3(b), the incenter I_i of OA_iBA_{i+1} is calculated to be:

$$\begin{aligned} I_i &= A_i + \frac{(4u_i + 2)(B - A_i) - (4u_i - 2)A}{K(A_iBO)} \\ &= (4 + 2u_i + 2v_i, 2u_i + 6v_i) = A_i + (2v_i, 2u_i), \end{aligned}$$

using $u_i^2 = 1 + 3v_i^2$. In particular, the incenters I_i are all lattice points. From

Figure 5: The first two members of the family.

Proposition 5, for $I_i = \lambda_i M_O + (1 - \lambda_i) M_{A_i A_{i+1}}$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_i &= \frac{4}{K(OA_i A_{i+1}) - ((4u_i + 2) + (4u_{i+1} - 2))} \\ &= \frac{4}{6(1 + 2u_i + 2v_i) - ((4u_i + 2) + 4(2u_i + 3v_i - 2))} = \frac{1}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, the family members all have the same value of the parameter λ_i . The Newton line for the first member of the family is shown (dotted) in Figure 6.

2.3. Lemmata for Tangential LEQs

For this subsection, $OABC$ denotes an equable tangential quadrilateral. In particular, it has inradius $r = 2$. Let θ denote the interior angle of $OABC$ at A ; see Figure 1. By the cosine rule, $p^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \theta$. As $|ab \cos \theta| = \sqrt{a^2 b^2 - a^2 b^2 \sin^2 \theta} = \sqrt{a^2 b^2 - 4K_A^2}$, so

$$p^2 = a^2 + b^2 \pm 2\sqrt{a^2 b^2 - (2K_A)^2}, \tag{11}$$

where the sign of the square root depends on whether θ is acute or obtuse. Similarly,

$$q^2 = a^2 + d^2 \pm 2\sqrt{a^2 d^2 - (2K_O)^2}. \tag{12}$$

The distances p, q may fail to be integers (see [4, Theorem 4]), but as O, A, B, C are lattice points, p^2, q^2 are integers. So the following lemma is immediate from Equations (11) and (12), and does not require the equability or tangential hypothesis.

Lemma 1. *The integers $a^2 b^2 - (2K_A)^2$ and $a^2 d^2 - (2K_O)^2$ are squares.*

Figure 6: First member of the family.

Lemma 2. *If $OABC$ is not a kite, one has*

$$p^2 = \frac{8(K_A - K_C)}{a - d} + (a - b)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad q^2 = \frac{8(K_O - K_B)}{a - b} + (a - d)^2.$$

Furthermore, if $OABC$ is a kite with OB as its axis of symmetry, and if $OABC$ is not a rhombus, then the above formula for q^2 still applies and one has the following formula for p^2 :

$$p^2 = \frac{2(a + c)^2(a - b)}{K_O - K_B}.$$

Proof. Arguing exactly as in Proposition 1 we reobtain Equation (6):

$$(a + c)(a - d)p^2 = 4(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a - d)(a + c)(a - b)^2.$$

If $a = d$, then by the tangential hypothesis, $b = c$, so $OABC$ is a kite. Thus, if $OABC$ is not a kite, $a \neq d$ and we have

$$p^2 = 4(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a - b)^2.$$

Then as $K_A^2 - K_C^2 = (K_A + K_C)(K_A - K_C) = 2(a + c)(K_A - K_C)$, from which the required formula for p^2 follows. Similarly, the formula for q^2 is obtained by applying Heron's formula to triangles OAC and BCA .

If $OABC$ is a kite with OB as its axis of symmetry, and is not a rhombus, then $a = d, b = c$ and $a \neq b$, and the argument giving the formula for q^2 remains

valid. For p^2 , we use the standard formula for the area of a kite: $pq = 2K$. So $p^2 = 16(a + c)^2/q^2 = \frac{2(a+c)^2(a-b)}{K_O - K_B}$, as required. \square

Remark 3. If $OABC$ is not a kite, then from the above lemma, using Equation (11),

$$\frac{8(K_A - (a + c))}{a - d} = \frac{p^2 - (a - b)^2}{2} = ab \pm \sqrt{a^2b^2 - (2K_A)^2},$$

which is an integer by Lemma 1. Similarly, $\frac{8(K_O - (a+c))}{a-b}$ is an integer. If $OABC$ is a kite with OB as its axis of symmetry, and if $OABC$ is not a rhombus, then by the same reasoning, $\frac{8(K_O - (a+c))}{a-b}$ is again an integer.

At this point we pause to explain the investigation we are about to perform. The integers $\frac{8(K_A - (a+c))}{a-d}$ and $\frac{8(K_O - (a+c))}{a-b}$, defined above for non-kites, will play a key role in what follows. Using Proposition 5 (or Proposition 4) one could easily directly show that these integers obey an important relation: their product is 8 times their sum (see Lemma 5 below). This enables us to show that these integers are restricted to a small set of possibilities (see Lemma 6 below). However, we will follow a somewhat more circuitous route to this result. We proceed by developing results that will lead to the functions σ, τ of Definition 1, given in the Introduction, which hold for all tangential LEQs (kites as well as non-kites). This enables us to then progress in a more natural manner, without having to appeal to the classification of kites in [3]. Although it involves some unpleasant computations, this pathway forward also has the advantage that it reveals certain important relations that will be useful in what follows.

Lemma 3. *The integer $abcd - 4(a + c)^2$ is a square, and*

$$K_A = (a + c) + (a - d) \frac{ab + cd \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}}{16 + (a - d)^2}$$

$$K_O = (a + c) + (a - b) \frac{ad + bc \mp 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}}{16 + (a - b)^2},$$

where the signs of the square roots in the formulas for K_O and K_A are opposite.

Remark 4. In the statement of the above lemma, the terms

$$ab + cd \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad ad + bc \mp 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}$$

are positive. Indeed, using $d = a - b + c$, by the arithmetic mean–geometric mean inequality, $ab + cd \geq 2\sqrt{abcd} > \sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}$. In particular, $K_A < a + c$ if and only if $a < d$.

Proof of Lemma 3. The formulas for K_A and K_O obviously hold when $OABC$ is a rhombus. So, without loss of generality, we may assume that either $OABC$ is not a kite, or is a kite that is not a rhombus and has axis of symmetry OB . Then from Lemma 2 and Equation (12),

$$\frac{4(K_O - K_B)}{a - b} - ad = \frac{q^2 - a^2 - d^2}{2} = \pm\sqrt{a^2d^2 - (2K_O)^2}$$

so squaring, using $K_O + K_B = 2(a + c)$ and rearranging gives

$$16(K_O - (a + c))^2 - 4ad(a - b)(K_O - (a + c)) = -(a - b)^2K_O^2.$$

Let $s := \frac{K_O - (a + c)}{a - b}$. Thus

$$16s^2 + ((a - b)s + (a + c))^2 = 4ads. \tag{13}$$

Hence, $\alpha s^2 + 2\beta s + \gamma = 0$, where, using $a + c = b + d$,

$$\alpha = 16 + (a - b)^2, \quad \beta = -(ad + cb), \quad \gamma = (a + c)^2.$$

Thus, as $\beta^2 - \alpha\gamma = 4(abcd - 4(a + c)^2)$ (using $a + c = b + d$ again), we have

$$s = \frac{ad + cb \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}}{16 + (a - b)^2},$$

which gives the required formula for K_O . In particular, as s is rational, $abcd - 4(a + c)^2$ is a square, as claimed. The formula for K_A is similarly obtained by equating p^2 from Lemma 2 and Equation (11).

It remains to see that the signs of the square roots in the formulas for K_O and K_A are opposite. Let $R = 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}$. Obviously, we may assume that $R \neq 0$. Let us write

$$K_A = (a + c) + (a - d)\frac{ab + cd + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2}$$

$$K_O = (a + c) + (a - b)\frac{ad + bc + \delta_O R}{16 + (a - b)^2},$$

where δ_A, δ_O are each ± 1 . Using $a + c = b + d$,

$$K_A - (a + b) = (d - a) + (a - d)\frac{ab + cd + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2} = (d - a)\frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2}$$

$$K_O - (a + d) = (b - a) + (a - b)\frac{ad + bc + \delta_O R}{16 + (a - b)^2} = (b - a)\frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_O R}{16 + (a - b)^2}.$$

Notice also that $(d - a)(b - a) = bd - ac$. Hence, by Proposition 4,

$$\frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2} \cdot \frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_O R}{16 + (a - b)^2} = 1. \tag{14}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2} \cdot \frac{16 - (ac + bd) - \delta_A R}{16 + (a - b)^2} \\ &= \frac{(16 - (ac + bd))^2 - R^2}{(16 + (a - d)^2)(16 + (a - b)^2)} = \frac{(16 - (ac + bd))^2 - 4(abcd - 4(a + c)^2)}{(16 + (a - d)^2)(16 + (a - b)^2)}, \end{aligned}$$

and substituting $d = a + c - b$ one finds that this expression reduces to 1. Hence, if $\delta_O = \delta_A$, Equation (14) gives

$$\frac{16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_A R}{16 + (a - d)^2} \cdot \frac{2\delta_A R}{16 + (a - b)^2} = 0,$$

which can only happen if $16 - (ac + bd) + \delta_A R = 0$, as $R \neq 0$. But in that case, one would have $(16 - (ac + bd))^2 = R^2$, which is impossible, since we have already seen that substituting $d = a + c - b$ one has

$$(16 - (ac + bd))^2 - R^2 = (16 + (a - d)^2)(16 + (a - b)^2) > 0.$$

So $\delta_O = -\delta_A$, as claimed. □

A tangential quadrilateral is cyclic if and only if its area is given by $K = \sqrt{abcd}$ [20, Theorem 4]. Hence, the integer $abcd - 4(a + c)^2$ in the above proposition is zero if and only if $OABC$ is cyclic. This motivates the following result.

Lemma 4. *The sign of the square root in the formulas for K_O is positive if and only if B lies within the circumcircle of the triangle OAC ; in particular, the sign for K_O is positive if $OABC$ is concave.*

Proof. In the notation of the above proof, let $x = \delta_O 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}$, so

$$\begin{aligned} K_O &= (a + c) + (a - b) \frac{ad + bc + x}{16 + (a - b)^2} \\ K_A &= (a + c) + (a - d) \frac{ab + cd - x}{16 + (a - d)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

From a standard criterion for a point to be within the circumcircle of a triangle (see [16]), B is inside the circumcircle of the triangle OAC if and only if

$$p^2 K_O < d^2 K_A + a^2 K_C. \tag{15}$$

First suppose that $OABC$ is not a kite. Now, $d^2 K_A + a^2 K_C = K_A(d^2 - a^2) + 2a^2(a + c)$, and by Lemma 2,

$$K_O p^2 = K_O \left(\frac{16(K_A - (a + c))}{a - d} + (a - b)^2 \right).$$

Also, by Proposition 4, $K_O K_A = (a+d)K_A + (a+b)K_O - 2a(a+c)$. So Inequality (15) can be written as $E > 0$ where

$$E = K_A(d^2 - a^2) + 2a^2(a + c) - \left(\frac{16((a + d)K_A + (a + b)K_O - 2a(a + c) - (a + c)K_O)}{a - d} + (a - b)^2 K_O \right).$$

Substituting the formulas for K_O and K_A , one has

$$\begin{aligned} E &= (d^2 - a^2) \left(a + c + \frac{(a - d)(ab + cd - x)}{16 + (a - d)^2} \right) + 2a^2(a + c) \\ &\quad - \frac{16}{a - d} \left((a + d) \left(a + c + \frac{(a - d)(ab + cd - x)}{16 + (a - d)^2} \right) - 2a(a + c) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (b - c) \left(a + c + \frac{(a - b)(bc + ad + x)}{16 + (a - b)^2} \right) \right) \\ &\quad - (a - b)^2 \left(a + c + \frac{(a - b)(bc + ad + x)}{16 + (a - b)^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting $d = a + c - b$ one finds that the above expression reduces (rather miraculously) to $E = (a + c)x$. Hence, as claimed, $x > 0$ if and only if B is inside the circumcircle of the triangle OAC .

Now, consider the case where $OABC$ is a kite with axis of symmetry OB . Then $a = d, b = c, K_A = K_C = a + c$ and Inequality (15) is: $p^2 K_O < 2a^2(a + c)$. By Lemma 2, $p^2 = \frac{2(a+c)^2(a-c)}{K_O - K_B} = \frac{(a+c)^2(a-c)}{K_O - (a+c)}$. So the required condition is $E > 0$, where

$$E = \frac{2a^2(K_O - (a + c))}{(a + c)(a - c)} - K_O = \frac{(a^2 + c^2)K_O - 2a^2(a + c)}{a^2 - c^2}.$$

Substituting for K_O , and using $d = a, b = c$, one finds that the above expression reduces to

$$E = \frac{-16(a + c)^2 + 4a^2c^2 + x(a^2 + c^2)}{(a + c)(16 + (a - c)^2)}.$$

Notice that the denominator of E is positive, and in the numerator, $-16(a + c)^2 + 4a^2c^2 = x^2$, so the numerator is $x(a^2 + c^2 + x)$. Now, $a^2 + c^2 + x > 0$ since $(a^2 + c^2)^2 - x^2 = (a^2 - c^2)^2 + 16(a + c)^2 > 0$. Hence, $x > 0$ if and only if B is inside the circumcircle of the triangle OAC . \square

From this point on, we employ the functions σ, τ given in Definition 1 of the Introduction.

Remark 5. From Definition 1 and Lemmas 3 and 4,

$$K_O = a + c + (a - b)\sigma, \tag{16}$$

$$K_A = a + c + (b - c)\tau. \tag{17}$$

Remark 6. By Lemma 3, Lemma 4, and Proposition 5, if $OABC$ is a tangential LEQ that is not a rhombus, then $\lambda = \frac{1}{\sigma}$.

Remark 7. By Remark 4, σ and τ are both positive.

Remark 8. We saw in the proof of Lemma 3, in Equation (13), that for $a \neq b$, one has, using $a + c = b + d$,

$$16\sigma^2 + ((d - c)\sigma + (a + c))^2 = 4ad\sigma. \tag{18}$$

It is easy to verify directly that this equation also holds when $a = b$. Similarly, the following equation holds in all cases:

$$16\tau^2 + ((b - c)\tau + (a + c))^2 = 4ab\tau. \tag{19}$$

Remark 9. Suppose $\sigma = \tau = 2$. Then Equation (18) gives

$$16 \cdot 2^2 + (2(d - c) + (a + c))^2 = 8ad.$$

In particular, $(2(d - c) + (a + c))^2$ is divisible by 8, and hence, being a square, it is divisible by 16. In particular, $a + c$ is even. Furthermore ad must be even. Hence, by a reflection in the line $y = x$ if necessary, we may assume that a is even. Then as $a + c$ is even, c is also even.

Suppose $\tau = 3$. Then Equation (19) gives

$$16 \cdot 3^2 + (a + 3b - 2c)^2 = 12ab.$$

In particular, $a + 3b - 2c$ is even so a and $3b$ have the same parity, and we can pose $(3b - a)/2 = u$ and $(3b + a)/2 = v$. This gives $36 + (u + a - c)^2 = 3ab$, so $36 + (u + c)^2 = 3ab - a^2 - 2ua + 4uc + 2ac = 6bc$. Hence, $u + c$ is divisible by 3, say $u + c = 3k$, so bc is divisible by 3. But $4 + k^2$ is not divisible by 3, so bc is not divisible by 9. Thus precisely one of the numbers b, c is divisible by 3. Hence, by a reflection in the line $y = x$ if necessary, we may assume that c is not divisible by 3, and that b is divisible by 3. By the same reasoning, for $\sigma = 3$, we may assume that c is not divisible by 3, and that d is divisible by 3.

Lemma 5. For σ, τ as defined in Definition 1, one has $\sigma + \tau = \sigma\tau$.

Proof. As in the proof of Lemma 4, let $x = 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + c)^2}$. Then cross-multiplying, the required identity is $E = 0$, where

$$E = (ad + bc + x)(16 + (a - d)^2) - (ab + cd - x)(16 + (a - b)^2) - (ad + bc + x)(ab + cd - x).$$

Expanding and using $d = a + c - b$, one has

$$E = x^2 + 4(4a^2 + 8ac - a^2bc + ab^2c + 4c^2 - abc^2).$$

Then replacing x^2 by $4(abcd - 4(a + c)^2)$ and using $d = a + c - b$ again gives $E = 0$, as required. □

Remark 10. Observe that 8σ and 8τ are integers. Indeed, if $OABC$ is not a kite, then from Lemma 3,

$$8\sigma = \frac{8(K_O - (a + c))}{a - b}, \quad 8\tau = \frac{8(K_A - (a + c))}{a - d},$$

which are integers by Remark 3. If $OABC$ is a kite but not a rhombus, with for example, axis of symmetry OB so $a = d, b = c$, then σ is still given by the above formula and is an integer by Remark 3, while $8\tau = ac - \delta\sqrt{a^2c^2 - 4(a + c)^2}$, which is an integer by Lemma 3. In fact, if $OABC$ is a kite that is not a rhombus, then by [4, Theorem 1], $OABC$ appears in Table 2, at the beginning of Subsection 2.2. Its λ value is thus either $1/5, 4/5, 1/2$ or $8/9$, and so here (σ, τ) is either $(5, 5/4), (5/4, 5), (2, 2)$ or $(9/8, 9)$, respectively, by Remark 6. If $OABC$ is a rhombus, then by [4, Corollary 1], $OABC$ is either the 4×4 square or the equable rhombus of side length 5. Furthermore, 8σ and 8τ are $a^2 \pm \sqrt{a^4 - 16a^2}$, which are also integers by Lemma 3. For the 4×4 square, this gives $(\sigma, \tau) = (2, 2)$. For the rhombus of side length 5, if one chooses OB to be the longest diagonal, then $(\sigma, \tau) = (\frac{5}{4}, 5)$, while if OB is the shortest diagonal, then $(\sigma, \tau) = (5, \frac{5}{4})$.

Lemma 6. For σ, τ as defined in Definition 1, the only possibilities for the unordered pairs $\{\sigma, \tau\}$ are $\{9, \frac{9}{8}\}, \{5, \frac{5}{4}\}, \{3, \frac{3}{2}\}$ and $\{2, 2\}$.

Proof. By Remarks 7 and 10, $\sigma' = 8\sigma, \tau' = 8\tau$ are positive integers and by Lemma 5, $\sigma'\tau' = 8(\sigma' + \tau')$ which can be written as

$$(\sigma' - 8)(\tau' - 8) = 2^6.$$

The only positive integer solutions of the above equation are then

$$\{\sigma', \tau'\} \in \{\{9, 72\}, \{10, 40\}, \{12, 24\}, \{16, 16\}\},$$

giving the result announced. □

As mentioned in Remark 6, if $OABC$ is a tangential LEQ that is not a rhombus, then $\lambda = \frac{1}{\sigma}$. So Lemma 6 has the following corollary.

Corollary 4. There are only seven possibilities for the barycentric coordinate parameter λ , namely $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{9}, \frac{8}{9}$, corresponding to $\sigma = 2, 3, \frac{3}{2}, 5, \frac{5}{4}, 9, \frac{9}{8}$, respectively.

Remark 11. Consider a reflection in the line $y = x$, followed by a relabelling of the vertices so they are positively oriented; that is, the vertices O, A, B, C are permuted to O, C, B, A , respectively. It is easy to see that under this operation, σ and τ are left unchanged, and the side lengths a, b, c, d are permuted to d, c, b, a , respectively.

Notice that for convex tangential LEQs (where we are not concerned about having the reflex angle at B), under the rotation for which the vertices O, A, B, C are

permuted to A, B, C, O , respectively, σ and τ are interchanged, and the side lengths a, b, c, d are permuted to d, a, b, c , respectively. So, for the study of convex tangential LEQs, up to Euclidean motions, we may assume that $\sigma \leq \tau$; that is, $\tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$.

Notice also for convex tangential LEQs, under the rotation for which the vertices O, A, B, C are permuted to B, C, O, A , respectively, σ and τ are also left unchanged, and the side lengths a, b, c, d are permuted to c, d, a, b , respectively. Note that the two permutations $\sigma_1 : (a, b, c, d) \mapsto (d, c, b, a)$ and $\sigma_2 : (a, b, c, d) \mapsto (c, d, a, b)$ are involutions and their compositions give the Klein group $\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z}$, under which each letter can be moved to any of the four positions. So, for example, without changing σ and τ , we may assume in the convex case that b is the smallest of the side lengths. Note however that when $\sigma = \tau = 2$, this potentially conflicts with the requirement in Theorem 1 (and in the proof of Corollary 1 which uses Theorem 1) that we also require a and c to be even. As we saw in Remark 9, $a + c$ and ad are even when $\sigma = \tau = 2$. So by reflection we may suppose that a, c are even. Then by applying σ_2 if necessary, we may assume that $b \leq d$.

In summary, for convex tangential LEQs we may assume the following:

- (a) $\tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$,
- (b) a, c are even and $b \leq d$ when $\tau = 2$,
- (c) b is the smallest of the side lengths when $\tau \in \{3, 5, 9\}$.

2.4. Proof of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1

Proof of Theorem 1. Lemma 6 gives 7 possibilities for the ordered pair (σ, τ) . Using $\frac{1}{\tau} + \frac{1}{\sigma} = 1$ and $a + c = b + d$, let us restate Equations (17) and (16):

$$K_A = a + c + (b - c)\tau, \tag{20}$$

$$K_O = a + c + (a - b)\frac{\tau}{\tau - 1}. \tag{21}$$

We now consider the area restrictions:

- As $K_A > 0$, Equation (20) gives $a + c + (b - c)\tau > 0$, which gives part of (i).
- As $K_C > 0$ and $K_C = 2(a + c) - K_A$, Equation (20) gives $a + c - (b - c)\tau > 0$, which gives the other part of (i).
- As $K_O > 0$, Equation (21) gives $(a + c)(\tau - 1) + (a - b)\tau > 0$, which gives (ii).
- We also have $K_B \neq 0$ as otherwise ABC would be colinear. Thus $K_O \neq 2(a + c)$ and Equation (21) gives $(a - b)\frac{\tau}{\tau - 1} \neq a + c$, which gives (iii).

Further, $OABC$ is convex if and only if $K_O < 2(a + c)$. As we have just seen, this occurs when $(a - b)\frac{\tau}{\tau - 1} < a + c$; that is, when $(b + c)\tau > a + c$.

Recall that from Remark 8,

$$16\tau^2 + ((b - c)\tau + (a + c))^2 = 4ab\tau, \tag{22}$$

$$16\sigma^2 + ((d - c)\sigma + (a + c))^2 = 4ad\sigma. \tag{23}$$

(a). If $\tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$, then Equation (22) gives $16\tau^2 + (\tau b + a - (\tau - 1)c)^2 = 4\tau ab$. So $\tau b + a - (\tau - 1)c$ is even. If $\tau = 2$, then $a, \tau b$ have the same parity since a is even by assumption. If $\tau \in \{3, 5, 9\}$, then $(\tau - 1)c$ is even, so $a, \tau b$ again have the same parity. Thus $v = \frac{\tau b + a}{2}$ is an integer, and we have $(2\tau)^2 + (v - \frac{\tau - 1}{2}c)^2 = \tau ab$. Then since $\tau ab = v^2 - u^2$, we have Equation (1) as required.

(b). This case is completely analogous to case (a). Let $\sigma \in \{3, 5, 9\}$; then Equation (23) gives $16\sigma^2 + (\sigma d + a - (\sigma - 1)c)^2 = 4\sigma ad$. So $\sigma d + a$ is even and $v = \frac{\sigma d + a}{2}$ is an integer. We have $(2\sigma)^2 + (v - \frac{\sigma - 1}{2}c)^2 = \sigma ad$. Then since $\sigma ad = v^2 - u^2$, we have Equation (2) as required. \square

Proof of Corollary 1. We use the notation of Theorem 1. By Remark 11, we may assume that $\tau \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$, that a, c are even and $b \leq d$ when $\tau = 2$, and that b is the smallest of the side lengths when $\tau \in \{3, 5, 9\}$.

As in the statement of Theorem 1, let $u = \frac{\tau b - a}{2}, v = \frac{\tau b + a}{2}$. Rewriting Condition (i) of Theorem 1, we have

$$(\tau - 1)c < 2v, \tag{24}$$

$$2u < (\tau + 1)c, \tag{25}$$

and the convexity condition is

$$2u > -c(\tau - 1). \tag{26}$$

So by Inequalities (25) and (26), we have $-\frac{\tau - 1}{2}c < u < \frac{\tau + 1}{2}c$. When $\tau = 2$, as $b \leq d$, we have $2b \leq b + d = a + c$, so $u \leq \frac{1}{2}c$. When $\tau \in \{3, 5, 9\}$, as b is the smallest of the side lengths, we have $\tau b \leq (\tau - 1)c + a$, so $u = (\tau b - a)/2 \leq \frac{\tau - 1}{2}c$. Thus, in all cases, we have

$$-\frac{\tau - 1}{2}c < u \leq \frac{\tau - 1}{2}c. \tag{27}$$

Assume $\tau = 2$. By Inequality (27), we have $u^2 \leq \frac{1}{4}c^2$. Thus by Theorem 1, $16 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - \frac{1}{2}c)^2$ gives

$$16 + \frac{1}{4}c^2 \geq 16 + u^2 = vc - \frac{1}{4}c^2,$$

from which it follows that

$$32 \geq c(2v - c). \tag{28}$$

From Inequality (24), we have $2v > c$. So Inequality (28) has only a finite number of solutions. Indeed, one finds readily there are just 20 such pairs c, v with c even

and $2v > c$ for which Inequality (28) holds. For only three of these pairs does the equation $16 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - \frac{1}{2}c)^2$ have an integer solution for u with $u + v$ even; these are $(c, v, u) = (4, 2, 6), (2, 1, 9), (8, 4, 6)$, corresponding to the sides $(a, b, c, d) = (4, 4, 4, 4), (8, 5, 2, 5), (2, 5, 8, 5)$, respectively. The last two cases correspond to the same LEQ, up to Euclidean motion.

Assume $\tau = 3$. By Inequality (27), we have $-c < u \leq c$. So $36 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2$ gives $36 + c^2 \geq 36 + u^2 = 2vc - c^2$, from which it follows that

$$18 \geq c(v - c). \tag{29}$$

By Inequality (24), we have $v > c$, so $c, v - c \in \{1, \dots, 18\}$. One finds there are just 58 pairs c, v with $v > c$ for which Inequality (29) holds. Of these, there is only one where the equation $16 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2$ has an integer solution u for which $v + u \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, and such that for the resulting side lengths (a, b, c, d) , one has $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$; this is the case $(c, v, u) = (4, 7, 2)$, corresponding to the sides $(a, b, c, d) = (5, 3, 4, 6)$.

Assume $\tau = 5$. By Inequality (27), we have $-2c < u \leq 2c$. So $100 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 2c)^2$ gives $100 + 4c^2 \geq 100 + u^2 = 4vc - 4c^2$, from which it follows that

$$25 \geq c(v - 2c). \tag{30}$$

By Inequality (24), we have $v > 2c$, so $c, v - 2c \in \{1, \dots, 25\}$. One finds there are just 86 pairs c, v with $v > 2c$ for which Inequality (30) holds. Of these, one finds there is only one where the equation $100 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 2c)^2$ has an integer solution u for which $(v + u)/5$ is an integer, and such that for the resulting side lengths (a, b, c, d) , one has $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$; this is the case $(c, v, u) = (5, 15, 10)$, corresponding to the sides $(a, b, c, d) = (5, 5, 5, 5)$.

Assume $\tau = 9$. By Inequality (27), we have $-4c < u \leq 4c$. So $324 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 4c)^2$ gives $324 + 16c^2 \geq 324 + u^2 = 8vc - 16c^2$, from which it follows that

$$41 \geq c(v - 4c). \tag{31}$$

By Inequality (24), we have $v > 4c$, so $c, v - 4c \in \{1, \dots, 41\}$. One finds there are 979 pairs c, v with $v > 4c$ for which Inequality (31) holds. Of these, one finds there are only two where the equation $324 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 4c)^2$ has an integer solution u for which $(v + u)/9$ is an integer, and such that for the resulting side lengths (a, b, c, d) , one has $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$; these are the cases $(c, v, u) = (3, 21, 6)$ and $(5, 23, 1)$, corresponding respectively to the sides $(a, b, c, d) = (15, 3, 3, 15)$ and $(37, 1, 5, 41)$.

This completes the proof of the corollary. □

2.5. Proof of Theorem 2

We follow the general strategy used in [42], but in our case we employ a slightly different solution form for the Diophantine equations that appear in the statement

of Theorem 2.

Lemma 7. *Suppose $z^2 + w^2 + u^2 = v^2$ for integers u, v, w, z and that the prime decomposition of $\gcd(u, v, w, z)$ contains no term ρ^k where ρ is congruent to 3 modulo 4 and k is odd. Then there are integers p, q, m, n such that*

$$v - u = p^2 + q^2, \quad v + u = m^2 + n^2, \quad w = pm + qn, \quad z = pn - qm.$$

Numbers u, v, w, z for which $z^2 + w^2 + u^2 = v^2$ are said to form a *Pythagorean quadruple*, and of course their study has a long history; see [35]. The above lemma is essentially equivalent to a classical result which says that if $z^2 + w^2 + u^2 = v^2$ for integers u, v, w, z with $\gcd(u, v, w, z) = 1$, then supposing z, w are even, there are integers p, q, m, n such that

$$v - u = 2(p^2 + q^2), \quad v + u = 2(m^2 + n^2), \quad w = 2(pm + qn), \quad z = 2(pn - qm).$$

This result, sometimes attributed to V. A. Lebesgue, is proved in many places; see [12, pp. 28-37], [15], [31, p.14] and [38]. We require the slightly stronger formulation of Lemma 7, which is readily deduced from the treatment given in [14, Section II].

We will also make use of a certain elementary fact which we give in the following lemma. For convenience, let us make a definition.

Definition 3. We say that a positive integer k has the *lattice preservation property*, or is a *lattice preserver*, if for every lattice point X for which $\frac{1}{k}X$ has integer length, the point $\frac{1}{k}X$ is also a lattice point.

For example, it is easy to see that 2 and 3 are lattice preservers. Notice that the set of lattice preservers is closed under multiplication. Hence, for example, 4 and 6 are lattice preservers. Recall that a *hypotenuse number* is a positive integer that occurs as the length of the hypotenuse of some Pythagorean triangle. It is well known that hypotenuse numbers are those numbers that have a prime factor congruent to 1 modulo 4 [32].

Lemma 8. *A positive integer k is a lattice preserver if and only if k is not a hypotenuse number. So k is a lattice preserver if and only if k has no prime factor congruent to 1 modulo 4.*

Proof. If k is a hypotenuse number, say $k^2 = x^2 + y^2$, then $\frac{1}{k}(x, y)$ has length 1 but it is not a lattice point. So hypotenuse numbers are not lattice preservers. Conversely, if k is not a lattice preserver (so $k > 2$), then there exists a lattice point (x, y) such that $(x, y)/k$ has integer length, a say, but is not a lattice point. We may assume without loss of generality that $\gcd(x, y, k) = 1$. We have $x^2 + y^2 = k^2a^2$. Write $x'^2 + y'^2 = k^2a'^2$ where $x' = x/\gcd(x, y, a)$, etc. So $\gcd(x', y', ka') = 1$ and hence x', y', ka' is a primitive Pythagorean triple. So by [32, Theorem 3.20] for example, all the odd prime factors of k are congruent to 1 modulo 4 and k is not divisible

by 4. So as $k > 2$, we conclude that k has at least one prime factor congruent to 1 modulo 4 and so k is a hypotenuse number. \square

Recall that by Remark 9, when working with tangential LEQs we may suppose without loss of generality that c is even when $\sigma = \tau = 2$ and that c is not divisible by 3 when σ or τ equals 3.

Proof of Theorem 2. (a). Suppose $t \in \{2, 3, 5, 9\}$. Notice that $a + c = b + d$ and so from hypothesis (i), $(d - a)t > -(a + c)$. Adding hypothesis (ii) gives $2dt > 0$, so $d > 0$. Furthermore, Equation (3) gives $(v + u)(v - u) = v^2 - u^2 > 0$, so as $v = (a + tb)/2 > c(t - 1)/2 > 0$ by condition (i) of our hypotheses, $v + u$ and $v - u$ are both necessarily positive. That is, $a, b > 0$. So, in all cases, a, b, c, d are all positive.

The basic idea of the proof is to apply Lemma 7 to obtain integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = p^2 + q^2, \quad tb = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = v - \frac{t-1}{2}c, \quad pn - qm = -2t. \quad (32)$$

Then we consider the Gaussian integers $z := p + qi$, $w := m + ni$, and let

$$A = z^2, \quad B = z^2 - \frac{1}{t}w^2, \quad C = \frac{1}{t(t-1)}(tz - w)^2. \quad (33)$$

We call this the *general case*. Unfortunately, as we will see below, this procedure is not always possible, and we will require two variations on this approach.

(Let us explain, in parenthesis, how the proposal of vertices of (33) can be understood. Obviously, A, B are suggested by (32). For a tangential LEQ, the areas K_O, K_A are determined by σ, τ and the side lengths, by Remark 10. Then Equation (7) enables one to express C in terms of A and B . This gives a formula for C that must hold if this construction is to produce a tangential LEQ. We suppress this derivation of the formula for C , and focus on showing that it has the required properties).

First suppose that $t = 2$. Then Equation (3) is $16 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - \frac{1}{2}c)^2$. Clearly $\gcd(4, u, v, c)$ is either 1, 2 or 4, so we may apply Lemma 7, and obtain the general case of the equations of (32) and (33).

Now, suppose that $t = 3$. Then Equation (3) is $6^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2$. As c is not divisible by 3 by assumption, $\gcd(6, u, v, c)$ is 1 or 2, and we may again apply Lemma 7 and obtain the general case of (32) and (33).

Now, suppose that $t = 5$. Then Equation (3) is $10^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 2c)^2$, and as $\gcd(10, u, v, c)$ is 1, 2, 5 or 10, we could apply Lemma 7 in all cases. In fact, for reasons that will become apparent later in the proof, we will directly apply Lemma 7, and obtain the general case, only in the cases where u, v, c are not all divisible by 5, so $\gcd(10, u, v, c) = 1$ or 2. Note that u, v, c are all divisible by 5 precisely when a

and c are divisible by 5. In this case, let $\frac{u}{5} = u', \frac{v}{5} = v', \frac{c}{5} = c'$. Thus Equation (3) can be written as $4 + u'^2 = v'^2 - (v' - 2c')^2$, and applying Lemma 7, we have integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = 5(p^2 + q^2), \quad b = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = \frac{1}{5}(v - 2c), \quad pn - qm = -2.$$

Then let $z := p + qi, w := m + ni$, and set

$$A = 5z^2, \quad B = 5z^2 - w^2, \quad C = \frac{1}{4}(5z - w)^2. \tag{34}$$

We call this the *first exceptional case*.

Now, suppose that $t = 9$. Then Equation (3) is $18^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 4c)^2$. If $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is not 3 or 6, we may apply Lemma 7 and obtain the general case. If instead $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is 3 or 6, which occurs when $\gcd(a, c)$ is divisible by 3 but not 9, let $\frac{u}{3} = u', \frac{v}{3} = v', \frac{c}{3} = c'$. Thus Equation (3) can be written as $36 + u'^2 = v'^2 - (v' - 4c')^2$, and applying Lemma 7, we have integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = 3(p^2 + q^2), \quad 3b = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = \frac{1}{3}(v - 4c), \quad pn - qm = -6.$$

Then let $z := p + qi, w := m + ni$, and set

$$A = 3z^2, \quad B = 3z^2 - \frac{1}{3}w^2, \quad C = \frac{1}{24}(9z - w)^2. \tag{35}$$

We call this the *second exceptional case*.

We now proceed to show that the points O, A, B, C define a tangential LEQ $OABC$ with successive side lengths a, b, c, d for which $(\sigma, \tau) = (\frac{t}{t-1}, t)$. We first treat the general case of the equations of (32) and (33), and deal with the two exceptional cases later. So we are assuming that for $t = 5$, the integers u, v, c are not all divisible by 5, and for $t = 9$, we have that $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is not 3 or 6.

Note that from the equations of (32), OA has length $p^2 + q^2 = a$ and $A - B = \frac{1}{t}w^2$, which has length $\frac{1}{t}(m^2 + n^2) = b$. It remains to verify the following 7 requirements:

- (Ra) $C - B$ has length c , and OC has length d ,
- (Rb) the quadrilateral $OABC$ has no self-intersections,
- (Rc) $OABC$ is equable,
- (Rd) the points A, B, C are not colinear,
- (Re) B is the only point at which the angle may be reflex,
- (Rf) for $OABC$, one has $\tau = t$,

(Rg) B and C are lattice points.

Let us make some preliminary calculations. Substituting $z = p + qi, w = m + ni$ and using the equations of (32), one has

$$z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w = 2(qm - pn)i = 4ti, \tag{36}$$

$$z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w = 2(pm + qn) = 2v - (t - 1)c = a + c + t(b - c). \tag{37}$$

Consequently,

$$z^2\bar{w}^2 - \bar{z}^2w^2 = (z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w)(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w) = 4t(a + c + t(b - c))i. \tag{38}$$

Now, consider the signed areas K_O, K_A, K_C, K_B . Recall that if Z, W are points in the complex plane, the triangle OZW has signed area $i(Z\bar{W} - \bar{Z}W)/4$. Using Equation (38), we have $4tK_A = i(-z^2\bar{w}^2 + \bar{z}^2w^2) = 4t(a + c + t(b - c))$, so

$$K_A = a + tb - (t - 1)c. \tag{39}$$

Using $z\bar{z} = a, w\bar{w} = tb$ and Equations (36) and (37), one has

$$\begin{aligned} 4(t - 1)t^2K_C &= i((tz^2 - w^2)\overline{(tz - w)^2} - (tz - w)^2\overline{(tz^2 - w^2)}) \\ &= it(z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w)(-2t(a + b) + (t + 1)(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w)) \\ &= -4t^2(-2t(a + b) + (t + 1)(a + c + t(b - c))) \\ &= 4t^2(t - 1)(a - tb + (t + 1)c), \end{aligned}$$

so

$$K_C = a - tb + (t + 1)c. \tag{40}$$

Using $z\bar{z} = a$ and Equations (36) and (37), one has

$$\begin{aligned} 4t(t - 1)K_O &= i(z^2\overline{(tz - w)^2} - (tz - w)^2\bar{z}^2) = i(z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w)(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w - 2ta) \\ &= -4t(a + c + t(b - c) - 2ta) = 4t((2t - 1)a - tb + (t - 1)c), \end{aligned}$$

so

$$K_O = \frac{1}{t - 1}((2t - 1)a - tb + (t - 1)c). \tag{41}$$

Before calculating K_B , note that $t(t - 1)(C - B) = (tz - w)^2 - (t - 1)(tz^2 - w^2) = t(z - w)^2$, so

$$C - B = \frac{1}{t - 1}(z - w)^2. \tag{42}$$

Thus, using $w\bar{w} = tb$ and Equations (36) and (37), one has

$$\begin{aligned} 4t(t - 1)K_B &= i((z - w)^2\bar{w}^2 - \overline{(z - w)^2}w^2) = i(-z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w)(2tb - z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w) \\ &= 4t(2tb - (a + c + t(b - c))) = 4t(-a + tb + (t - 1)c), \end{aligned}$$

so

$$K_B = \frac{1}{t-1}(-a + tb + (t-1)c). \tag{43}$$

We now prove the requirements (Ra) – (Rg).

(Ra). From Equation (42), we have, using Equation (37),

$$\begin{aligned} (t-1)\|C - B\| &= \|z - w\|^2 = z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w \\ &= a + tb - (a + c + t(b - c)) = (t-1)c, \end{aligned}$$

as required. Using Equation (37) again, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} t(t-1)\|C\| &= \|tz - w\|^2 = t^2z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - tz\bar{w} - t\bar{z}w = t^2a + tb - t(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w) \\ &= t^2a + tb - t(a + tb - (t-1)c) \\ &= (t^2 - t)a - (t^2 - t)b + t(t-1)c = t(t-1)d, \end{aligned}$$

as required.

(Rb). To verify that the quadrilateral $OABC$ has no self-intersections, it suffices to show that the respective signed areas K_A, K_C of triangles OAB, OBC are both positive. The hypothesis (i) gives $tb + a - (t-1)c > 0$, so $K_A > 0$ by Equation (39). Hypothesis (i) also gives $a - tb + (t+1)c > 0$, so $K_C > 0$ by Equation (40).

(Rc). From Equations (39) and (40), we have $K_A + K_C = 2(a + c)$, as required.

(Rd). To verify that the points A, B, C are not colinear, it suffices to show that $K_B \neq 0$. But by Equation (43), $(t-1)K_B = -a + tb + (t-1)c \neq 0$, by hypothesis (iii).

(Re). To see that B is the only point at which the angle may be reflex, it remains to show that $K_O > 0$. The hypothesis (ii) gives $(2a + c - b)t > a + c$, from which we have $(2t - 1)a - tb + (t-1)c > 0$, so $K_O > 0$ by Equation (41).

(Rf). If $a \neq d$, then Equations (17) and (39) give

$$\tau = \frac{K_A - (a + c)}{a - d} = \frac{a + tb - (t-1)c - a - c}{a - d} = \frac{t(b - c)}{a - d} = t.$$

Thus by Lemma 6, $\sigma = \frac{t}{t-1}$.

If $a \neq b$, then Equations (16) and (41) give

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= \frac{K_O - (a + c)}{a - b} = \frac{(2t - 1)a - tb + (t-1)c - (t-1)(a + c)}{(t-1)(a - b)} \\ &= \frac{ta - tb}{(t-1)(a - b)} = \frac{t}{t-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus by Lemma 6, $\tau = t$.

Finally, if $a = d$ and $a = b$, then $OABC$ is a rhombus and $a = b = c = d$. But if $a = b$, then $u = \frac{t-1}{2}a, v = \frac{t+1}{2}a$, and so by Equation (3), $a = c$ would give

$(2t)^2 + \frac{(t-1)^2}{4}a^2 = \frac{(t+1)^2}{4}a^2 - a^2$, so $a^2 = \frac{4t^2}{t-1}$. For $t = \frac{9}{8}, \frac{5}{4}, \frac{3}{2}, 2, 3, 5, 9$, this would give respectively $a^2 = \frac{81}{2}, 25, 18, 16, 18, 25$, which is impossible for $t = \frac{9}{8}, \frac{3}{2}, 3, 9$. For $t = 2$ we have $a = 4$, so $OABC$ is the 4×4 square, which has $(\sigma, \tau) = (2, 2)$, by Remark 10. For $t = 5$ and $\frac{5}{4}$, we have $a = 5$, so $OABC$ is the rhombus of side length 5, which has $(\sigma, \tau) = (\frac{5}{4}, 5)$ and $(5, \frac{5}{4})$, respectively, again by Remark 10.

(Rg). We now come to the most delicate part of the proof. Note that requirements (Ra)–(Re) were simply equations or inequalities, and did not use the values of t , or the fact that certain variables are integers. Requirement (Rf) did use these facts, but only in a very simple manner.

First suppose $t = 2$. So $B = z^2 - \frac{1}{2}w^2$ and $C = \frac{1}{2}(2z - w)^2$. Now, z^2, w^2 are lattice points. And from above, $\frac{1}{2}w^2$ has integer length b . So by Lemma 8, $\frac{1}{2}w^2$ is a lattice point. Thus B is a lattice point. Similarly, $(2z - w)^2$ is a lattice point and $C = \frac{1}{2}(2z - w)^2$ has integer length c , so by Lemma 8, C is a lattice point.

Now, suppose $t = 3$. So $B = z^2 - \frac{1}{3}w^2$ and $C = \frac{1}{6}(3z - w)^2$. Now, z^2, w^2 are lattice points. And from above, $\frac{1}{3}w^2$ has integer length b . So by Lemma 8, $\frac{1}{3}w^2$ is a lattice point. Thus B is a lattice point. Similarly, $(3z - w)^2$ is a lattice point and $C = \frac{1}{6}(3z - w)^2$ has integer length c , so by Lemma 8, C is a lattice point.

Now, suppose $t = 5$. So $B = z^2 - \frac{1}{5}w^2$ and $C = \frac{1}{20}(5z - w)^2$, where $w = m + ni$. We claim that in the general case, m, n are multiples of 5. First note that Equation (3) can be written as $10^2 + (v - 2c)^2 = (v + u)(v - u)$. So as 5 divides $v + u = 5b$, it follows that $v - 2c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Hence, from the equations of (32),

$$ma = m(p^2 + q^2) = p(pm + qn) - q(pn - qm) = p(v - 2c) + 10q \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

Similarly, $na \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. So if $a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, we have $m, n \equiv 0$ as required. If $a \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then as $v - 2c = \frac{5b+a-4c}{2} = \frac{5(b-c)+a+c}{2}$, and $v - 2c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, so 5 divides $a + c$, and thus $c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and hence $v \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. So, as $v + u = 5b$, we have that 5 divides u, v, c . But this is the first exceptional case, contrary to our current assumption.

As m, n are multiples of 5, let $m = 5m', n = 5n', w' = m' + n'i$. So $B = z^2 - 5w'^2$, which is obviously a lattice point, and $C = \frac{5}{4}(z - w')^2$, which is a lattice point by Lemma 8.

Now, suppose $t = 9$. So $B = z^2 - \frac{1}{9}w^2$ and $C = \frac{1}{72}(9z - w)^2$. Now, z^2, w^2 are lattice points. And from above, $\frac{1}{9}w^2$ has integer length b . So by Lemma 8, $\frac{1}{9}w^2$ is a lattice point. Thus B is a lattice point. Similarly, $(9z - w)^2$ is a lattice point and $C = \frac{1}{72}(9z - w)^2$ has integer length d . Hence, as $72 = 2^3 \cdot 3^2$ is a lattice preserver, C is a lattice point by Lemma 8. This completes requirement (Rg).

We now treat the first exceptional case. So $t = 5$ and u, v, c are all divisible by 5. In the preliminary calculations part of the argument, analogous to Equations (36),

(37) and (38), one has:

$$z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w = 4i, \tag{44}$$

$$z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w = \frac{1}{5}(a + c) + (b - c), \tag{45}$$

$$z^2\bar{w}^2 - \bar{z}^2w^2 = \left(\frac{4}{5}(a + c) + 4(b - c)\right)i. \tag{46}$$

For the areas, using the above three expressions and $z\bar{z} = a/5, w\bar{w} = b$, we find exactly the same formulas for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C as before; that is, we obtain Equations (41), (39), (43) and (40), respectively, with $t = 5$.

Analogous to Equation (42), one has

$$C - B = \frac{5}{4}(z - w)^2. \tag{47}$$

For the proof of requirement (Ra), we have from Equation (47), using Equation (45),

$$\begin{aligned} 4\|C - B\| &= 5\|z - w\|^2 = 5(z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w) \\ &= a + 5b - (a + c + 5(b - c)) = 4c, \end{aligned}$$

as required. Using Equation (45) again, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} 4\|C\| &= \|5z - w\|^2 = 5^2z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - 5z\bar{w} - 5\bar{z}w = 5a + b - 5(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w) \\ &= 5a + b - ((a + c) + 5(b - c)) = 4a - 4b + 4c = 4d, \end{aligned}$$

as required.

As requirements (Rb)–(Rf) only rely on the expressions for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C , and as these are unchanged, the proofs of these parts need no amendment. It remains to verify requirement (Rg). But $B = 5z^2 - w^2$, which is obviously a lattice point, and $C = \frac{1}{4}(5z - w)^2$, which is a lattice point by Lemma 8.

Finally, we treat the second exceptional case. So $t = 9$ and $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is 3 or 6. In the preliminary calculations part of the argument, analogous to Equations (36), (37) and (38), one has:

$$\begin{aligned} z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w &= 12i, \\ z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w &= \frac{1}{3}(a + 9b - 8c), \\ z^2\bar{w}^2 - \bar{z}^2w^2 &= 4(a + 9b - 8c)i. \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

For the areas, using the above three expressions and $z\bar{z} = a/3, w\bar{w} = 3b$, we find the exactly same formulas for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C as before; that is, we obtain Equations (41), (39), (43) and (40), respectively, with $t = 9$.

Analogous to Equation (42), one has

$$C - B = \frac{3}{8}(z - w)^2. \tag{49}$$

For the proof of requirement (Ra), we have from Equation (49), using Equation (48),

$$\begin{aligned} 8\|C - B\| &= 3\|z - w\|^2 = 3(z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w) \\ &= 3(a/3 + 3b - (a + 9b - 8c)/3) = a + 9b - (a + 9b - 8c) = 8c, \end{aligned}$$

as required. Using Equation (48) again, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} 24\|C\| &= \|9z - w\|^2 = 9^2z\bar{z} + w\bar{w} - 9z\bar{w} - 9\bar{z}w = 27a + 3b - 9(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w) \\ &= 27a + 3b - 3(a + 9b - 8c) = 24a - 24b + 24c = 24d, \end{aligned}$$

as required.

As requirements (Rb)–(Rf) only rely on the expressions for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C , and as these are unchanged, the proofs of these parts need no amendment. It remains to verify requirement (Rg). Now, A, z, w are lattice points. Thus, as $A - B = \frac{1}{3}w^2$ is a lattice point by Lemma 8, so B is a lattice point. Finally, $C = \frac{1}{24}(9z - w)^2$ is a lattice point by Lemma 8 since $24 = 2^3 \cdot 3$ is a lattice preserver.

This completes the proof of Part (a).

(b). Suppose $s \in \{3, 5, 9\}$. By hypothesis, b and c are positive. Further, Equation (3) gives $(v + u)(v - u) = v^2 - u^2 > 0$, so as v is positive by condition (i) of our hypotheses, $v + u$ and $v - u$ are both necessarily positive. That is, $a, d > 0$. So, in all cases, a, b, c, d are all positive.

We now proceed exactly as we did in case (a) by considering a general case and two exceptional cases. The first exceptional case is where $s = 5$ and the integers u, v, c are all divisible by 5. The second exceptional case is where $s = 9$ and $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is either 3 or 6. In the general case, we apply Lemma 7 to obtain integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = p^2 + q^2, \quad sd = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = v - \frac{s-1}{2}c, \quad pn - qm = 2s. \tag{50}$$

Then we consider the Gaussian integers $z := p + qi, y := m + ni$, and let

$$A = z^2, \quad B = z^2 - \frac{1}{s(s-1)}(sz - y)^2, \quad C = \frac{1}{s}y^2. \tag{51}$$

Note that A is a lattice point, and OA has length a , while OC has length d (we will see later that C is a lattice point). For $t = \frac{s}{s-1}$, let

$$w := \frac{sz - y}{s-1}.$$

Notice that w has length (i.e., norm) given by

$$\begin{aligned} (s-1)^2\|w\|^2 &= s^2a + sd - s(z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y) = s^2a + sd - s(2v - (s-1)c) \\ &= s^2a + sd - s(sd + a - (s-1)c) = s(s-1)(a - d + c) = s(s-1)b. \end{aligned}$$

So $\frac{s-1}{s}w^2$ has length b . Observe that for $t = \frac{s}{s-1}$, we have $B = z^2 - \frac{1}{t}w^2$ and $A - B = \frac{1}{t}w^2$ has length b , exactly as in case (a). Moreover, we can write

$$C = \frac{1}{s}(sz - (s-1)w)^2 = \frac{(s-1)^2}{s} \left(\frac{s}{s-1}z - w \right)^2 = \frac{1}{t(t-1)}(tz - w)^2,$$

which is the same formula as in (33), in case (a). Now, compute:

$$\begin{aligned} z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w &= \frac{-1}{s-1}(z\bar{y} - \bar{z}y) = \frac{-1}{s-1}2(qm - pn)i = \frac{s}{s-1}4i = 4ti, \\ z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w &= \frac{1}{s-1}(z\overline{(sz-y)} + \bar{z}(sz-y)) = \frac{1}{s-1}(2sa - z\bar{y} - \bar{z}y) \\ &= \frac{1}{s-1}(2sa - (2v - (s-1)c)) = \frac{1}{s-1}(2sa - sd - a + (s-1)c) \\ &= a + c + \frac{s}{s-1}(a-d) = a + c + t(a-d) = a + c + t(b-c), \\ z^2\bar{w}^2 - \bar{z}^2w^2 &= (z\bar{w} - \bar{z}w)(z\bar{w} + \bar{z}w) = 4t(a + c + t(b-c))i, \end{aligned}$$

which are exactly the same as stated in Equations (36), (37) and (37) of case (a). It follows that the areas K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C are given by the case (a) formulas (41), (39), (43) and (40), respectively. Thus the proof of requirements (Ra)–(Rf) hold by the arguments used in case (a) and it remains to verify (Rg).

Let us first suppose $s = 5$. So $C = \frac{1}{5}y^2$, where $w = m + ni$. We claim that m, n are multiples of 5. First note that Equation (3) can be written as $10^2 + (v - 2c)^2 = (v + u)(v - u)$. So as 5 divides $v + u = 5d$, it follows that $v - 2c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Hence, from (32),

$$ma = m(p^2 + q^2) = p(pm + qn) - q(pn - qm) = p(v - 2c) - 10q \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

Similarly, $na \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. So if $a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, we have $m, n \equiv 0$ as required. If $a \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then as $v - 2c = \frac{5d+a-4c}{2} = \frac{5(d-c)+a+c}{2}$, and $v - 2c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, so 5 divides $a + c$, and thus $c \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and hence $v \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. So, as $v + u = 5d$, we have that 5 divides u, v, c . But this is the first exceptional case, contrary to our current assumption.

As m, n are multiples of 5, let $m = 5m', n = 5n', y' = m' + n'i$. So $C = 5y'^2$, which is obviously a lattice point. Furthermore, for $s = 5$, one has from (51) that

$$A - B = \frac{1}{20}5(z - y')^2 = \frac{1}{4}(z - y')^2.$$

So as $A - B$ has integer length b , and $(z - y')^2$ is a lattice, so $A - B$ is a lattice point by Lemma 8, and hence B is a lattice point.

Now, suppose $s = 3$ or 9 . As y is a lattice point and $C = \frac{1}{s}y^2$ has length d , so C is a lattice point when $s = 3$ or 9 , by Lemma 8. For $s = 3$, we have $A - B = \frac{1}{6}(3z - y)^2$

and for $s = 9$, we have $A - B = \frac{1}{72}(9z - y)^2$. In both cases, $A - B$ is a lattice point by Lemma 8, and hence B is a lattice point.

We now treat the first exceptional case. So $t = 5$ and u, v, c are all divisible by 5. Let $\frac{u}{5} = u', \frac{v}{5} = v', \frac{c}{5} = c'$. Thus Equation (3) can be written as $4 + u'^2 = v'^2 - (v' - 2c')^2$, and applying Lemma 7, we have integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = 5(p^2 + q^2), \quad d = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = \frac{1}{5}(v - 2c), \quad pn - qm = 2.$$

Then let $z := p + qi, y := m + ni$, and set

$$A = 5z^2, \quad B = 5z^2 - \frac{1}{4}(5z - y)^2, \quad C = y^2. \tag{52}$$

We remark that B has other useful expressions:

$$B = y^2 - \frac{5}{4}(z - y)^2 = \frac{1}{4}(-y^2 + 10yz - 5z^2).$$

Note that A has length a and C has length d . Moreover, $A - B = \frac{1}{4}(5z - y)^2$ and has length

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{4}(5z - y)\overline{(5z - y)} &= \frac{1}{4}(5a + d - 5(z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y)) = \frac{1}{4}(5a + d - (5d + a - 4c)) \\ &= \frac{1}{4}(4a - 4d + 4c) = b, \end{aligned}$$

and $C - B = \frac{5}{4}(z - y)^2$ has length

$$\frac{5}{4}(z - y)\overline{(z - y)} = \frac{5}{4}\left(\frac{1}{5}a + d - (z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y)\right) = \frac{1}{4}(a + 5d - (5d + a - 4c)) = c.$$

So requirement (Ra) is satisfied. Moreover, $A = 5z^2$ and $C = y^2$ are obviously lattice points, $-y^2 + 10yz - 5z^2$ is a lattice point and $B = \frac{1}{4}(-y^2 + 10yz - 5z^2)$ has integer length b , so B is a lattice point by Lemma 8. So requirement (Rg) is satisfied.

For our preliminary calculations we will use z and y , rather than z and w as we did before. We have

$$\begin{aligned} z\bar{y} - \bar{z}y &= -2(pn - qm)i = -4i, \\ z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y &= \frac{1}{5}(5d + a - 4c) = \frac{1}{5}(6a - 5b + c), \\ z^2\bar{y}^2 - \bar{z}^2y^2 &= \frac{-4}{5}(6a - 5b + c)i. \end{aligned}$$

These relations are also different from the Equations (44), (45) and (46) we obtained in the first exceptional case of case (a). Nevertheless, using the above three relations together with the equations of (52), we find exactly the same formulas

for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C as before; that is, we obtain Equations (41), (39), (43), (40), respectively, with $t = \frac{5}{4}$. As requirements (Rb)–(Rf) only rely on the expressions for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C , and as these are unchanged, the proofs of these parts need no amendment.

Finally, we treat the second exceptional case. So $s = 9$ and $\gcd(18, u, v, c)$ is 3 or 6. Let $\frac{u}{3} = u', \frac{v}{3} = v', \frac{c}{3} = c'$. Thus Equation (3) can be written as

$$36 + u'^2 = v'^2 - (v' - 4c')^2,$$

and applying Lemma 7, we have integers p, q, m, n such that

$$a = 3(p^2 + q^2), \quad 3d = m^2 + n^2, \quad pm + qn = \frac{1}{3}(v - 4c), \quad pn - qm = 6.$$

Then let $z := p + qi, y := m + ni$, and set

$$A = 3z^2, \quad B = 3z^2 - \frac{1}{24}(9z - y)^2, \quad C = \frac{1}{3}y^2.$$

Observe that

$$B = \frac{1}{3}y^2 - \frac{3}{8}(z - y)^2 = \frac{1}{24}(-y^2 + 18yz - 9z^2).$$

Note that A has length a and C has length d . Moreover, $A - B = \frac{1}{24}(9z - y)^2$ and has length

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{24}(9z - y)\overline{(9z - y)} &= \frac{1}{24}(27a + 3d - 9(z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y)) = \frac{1}{8}(9a + d - (9d + a - 8c)) \\ &= \frac{1}{8}(8a - 8d + 8c) = b, \end{aligned}$$

and $C - B = \frac{3}{8}(z - y)^2$ has length

$$\frac{3}{8}(z - y)\overline{(z - y)} = \frac{3}{8}\left(\frac{1}{3}a + 3d - (z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y)\right) = \frac{1}{8}(a + 9d - (9d + a - 8c)) = c.$$

So requirement (Ra) is satisfied. Obviously A is a lattice point, and B, C are lattice points by Lemma 8. So requirement (Rg) is satisfied.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} z\bar{y} - \bar{z}y &= -2(pn - qm)i = -12i, \\ z\bar{y} + \bar{z}y &= \frac{1}{3}(9d + a - 8c) = \frac{1}{3}(10a - 9b + c), \\ z^2\bar{y}^2 - \bar{z}^2y^2 &= -4(10a - 9b + c)i. \end{aligned}$$

Using these relations together with the equations of (52), we find exactly the same formulas for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C as before; that is, we obtain Equations (41), (39), (43), (40), respectively, with $t = \frac{9}{8}$. As requirements (Rb)–(Rf) only rely on the expressions for K_O, K_A, K_B, K_C , and as these are unchanged, the proofs of these parts need no amendment.

This completes the proof of Part (b), and the theorem. □

Proof of Corollary 2. We use the terminology and results from the proof of Theorem 2. By Remark 6, $\lambda = \frac{1}{\sigma}$, so

$$I = \frac{(A + C) + (\sigma - 1)B}{2\sigma} = \frac{(\tau - 1)(A + C) + B}{2\tau}.$$

First suppose $\tau = 2$. Then $I = \frac{A+C+B}{4}$, so by (33),

$$I = \frac{z^2 + z^2 - \frac{1}{2}w^2 + \frac{1}{2}(2z - w)^2}{4} = z^2 - \frac{zw}{2}.$$

Now, $z^2 = A$ is a lattice point and $\frac{zw}{2} = \frac{1}{2}((pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i)$. We have $zw = (pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i$ and by (32), we have $2b = m^2 + n^2$. So if b is even, then $m^2 + n^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and hence m, n are both even. In this case $\frac{zw}{2}$ is a lattice point, and hence I is a lattice point. So we may assume that b is odd and that m, n are both odd. Then by (32), modulo 2, we have $pn + qm \equiv pm - qn \equiv pn - qm = -4 \equiv 0$. So once again, I is a lattice point.

Now, suppose $\tau = 3$. Then $I = \frac{2(A+C)+B}{6}$, so by (33),

$$I = \frac{2z^2 + \frac{1}{3}(3z - w)^2 + z^2 - \frac{1}{3}w^2}{6} = z^2 - \frac{zw}{3}.$$

We have $zw = (pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i$ and by (32), we have $3b = m^2 + n^2$. So $m^2 + n^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and hence m, n are divisible by 3. So zw is divisible by 3 and thus I is a lattice point.

Similarly, if $\sigma = 3$. Then $I = \frac{(A+C)+2B}{6}$, so by (51),

$$I = \frac{z^2 + \frac{1}{3}y^2 + 2z^2 - \frac{1}{3}(3z - y)^2}{6} = \frac{zy}{3}.$$

We have $zy = (pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i$ and by (50), we have $3d = m^2 + n^2$. So $m^2 + n^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and hence m, n are divisible by 3. So zy is divisible by 3 and thus I is a lattice point.

Now, suppose $\tau = 5$. Then $I = \frac{4(A+C)+B}{10}$. First assume that $\frac{5d+2}{2}, \frac{5d-2}{2}, c$ are not all divisible by 5, so we are in the general case. Then by (51),

$$I = \frac{4z^2 + \frac{1}{5}(5z - w)^2 + z^2 - \frac{1}{5}w^2}{10} = z^2 - \frac{zw}{5}.$$

We have $zw = (pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i$. It was proved in the proof of Theorem 2 that in the general case, m, n are divisible by 5. So zw is divisible by 5 and thus I is a lattice point. Now, consider the exceptional case. By (34),

$$I = \frac{4(A + C) + B}{10} = \frac{20z^2 + (5z - w)^2 + 5z^2 - w^2}{10} = 5z^2 - zw,$$

which is clearly a lattice point.

Now, suppose $\sigma = 5$. Then $I = \frac{(A+C)+4B}{10}$. First assume that $\frac{5b+2}{2}, \frac{5b-2}{2}, c$ are not all divisible by 5, so we are in the general case. Then by (33),

$$I = \frac{z^2 + \frac{1}{5}y^2 + 4z^2 - \frac{1}{5}(5z - y)^2}{10} = \frac{zw}{5}.$$

We have $zw = (pm - qn) + (pn + qm)i$. It was proved in the proof of Theorem 2 that in the general case, m, n are divisible by 5. So zw is divisible by 5 and thus I is a lattice point. Now, consider the exceptional case. By (52),

$$I = \frac{(A + C) + 4B}{10} = \frac{5z^2 + y^2 + 20z^2 - (5z - y)^2}{10} = zy,$$

which is clearly a lattice point. □

Example 1. The convex tangential LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (40, 9), (36, 12), (35, 12)$ and side lengths $41, 5, 1, 37$, has incenter $(\frac{106}{3}, 10)$, by Proposition 3. Similarly, the concave tangential LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (16, 63), (12, 60), (11, 60)$ and side lengths $65, 5, 1, 61$, has a non-lattice point incenter $(\frac{38}{3}, 58)$. Notice that by Proposition 5, one finds that $\lambda = \frac{8}{9}$ in both of these examples; that is, $\tau = 9$.

Example 2. The proof of Theorem 2 was complicated by the two exceptional cases. Let us show that such cases really do occur. Further, one might wonder whether it is possible to remove this inconvenience by taking a reflection in the line $y = x$ and thus interchanging a with d and b with c . Our examples show that this is not always possible.

Consider the tangential LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (35, 120), (32, 116), (32, 126)$. It has $\tau = 5$ and the side lengths a, b, c, d are $125, 5, 10, 130$, respectively. Here $u = (5b - a)/2 = -50, v = (5b - a)/2 = 75, c = 10$. So u, v, c are all divisible by 5, which is the first exceptional case. Interchanging a with d and b with c would give new values $(u, v, c) = (-40, 90, 5)$ but again u, v, c are all divisible by 5. Similarly, consider the tangential LEQ with vertices $(0, 0), (231, 108), (228, 108), (240, 117)$. It has $\tau = 9$ and the side lengths a, b, c, d are $255, 3, 15, 267$, respectively. Here $u = (9b - a)/2 = -114, v = (9b - a)/2 = 141$. So $\gcd(18, u, v, c) = 3$, which is the second exceptional case. Interchanging a with d and b with c would give new values $(u, v, c) = (-66, 201, 15)$ but again $\gcd(18, u, v, c) = 3$.

2.6. Infinite Families of Tangential LEQs

As we saw in Subsection 2.2, the four infinite families $K1 - K4$ of kites from [4, Theorem 1] gave examples of tangential LEQs with (σ, τ) equal to $(5, 5/4), (5/4, 5), (2, 2)$ and $(9/8, 9)$, respectively. Also in Subsection 2.2, we exhibited an infinite nested family of tangential LEQs with $(\sigma, \tau) = (3, 3/2)$. In this final subsection we exhibit infinite families with $(\sigma, \tau) = (3/2, 3)$ and $(9, 9/8)$, thus showing that there are infinitely many tangential LEQs in each of the seven cases of Theorem 1. The

method employed can also be used to give further examples in the cases where (σ, τ) is $(5, 5/4), (5/4, 5), (2, 2), (9/8, 9)$ and $(3, 3/2)$. While by no means comprehensive, we hope the examples in this subsection will convey the impression that tangential LEQs are quite abundant.

First observe that for $\tau = 3$, Equation 1 of Theorem 1 is:

$$6^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2. \tag{53}$$

So this equation can be solved by fixing u , and then expressing $6^2 + u^2$ as a difference of two squares. Recall that an integer can be written as a difference of two squares if and only if it is odd or a multiple of 4; see sequence A100073 in OEIS [37]. Clearly $6^2 + u^2 \not\equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, for all u . Thus for every integer value of u , there are integers v, c for which $6^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2$. (Note that we are interested in solutions $v \in \mathbb{N}$ and $u \in \mathbb{Z}$). However, we must also impose the restrictions of Theorem 2. We require $u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $c > 0$, c is not divisible by 3, as well as the three conditions (i) – (iii):

$$(i) \ 3|c - b| < a + c, \quad (ii) \ 3(a + d) > a + c, \quad (iii) \ 3(b + c) \neq a + c.$$

For convenience we separate (i) into two conditions:

$$(ia) \ 3(c - b) < a + c, \quad (ib) \ 3(b - c) < a + c.$$

Notice that the conditions can be rewritten in terms of $u = \frac{3b-a}{2}, v = \frac{3b+a}{2}$ as:

$$(ia) \ c < v, \quad (ib) \ u < 2c, \quad (ii) \ 3u < (2v + c), \quad (iii) \ u \neq -c.$$

It is not true that for every integer value of u , there are integers v, c for which $6^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - c)^2$ and the above restrictions hold. For example, for $u = 4$, the only solutions are $v = 14, c = 2$ and $v = 14, c = 26$, but (ib) fails for the first solution and (ia) fails for the second.

One infinite family of solutions is as follows: for any negative integer x , let $u = 6x - 1$. Then it is easy to check that $v = 6(3x^2 - x + 3) + 1, c = 1$ is a solution to Equation (53). Note that $u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Condition (ia) is true for all x . Conditions (ib) and (iii) hold as $x < 0$. Condition (ii) can be written as $6x^2 - 5x + 7 > 0$, which is true for all real x . Notice that this infinite family has the values:

$$a = 18x^2 - 12x + 19, \quad b = 6x^2 + 6, \quad c = 1, \quad d = 12x^2 - 12x + 14.$$

Another infinite family of solutions is obtained by taking $c = 2$ and for any integer $x \leq -3$, letting $u = 6x - 2$ and $v = 9x^2 - 6x + 11$. This family has the values:

$$a = 9x^2 - 12x + 13, \quad b = 3x^2 + 3, \quad c = 2, \quad d = 6x^2 - 12x + 12.$$

We now turn to $(\sigma, \tau) = (9, 9/8)$. First observe that for $\sigma = 9$, Equation (2) of Theorem 1 is:

$$18^2 + u^2 = v^2 - (v - 4c)^2. \tag{54}$$

We require $u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{9}$ and $c > 0$, as well as the four conditions:

- (ia) $9(d - a) < 8(a + c)$, (ib) $9(a - d) < 8(a + c)$,
- (ii) $9(a + d) > 8(a + c)$, (iii) $9(a + 2c - d) \neq 8(a + c)$,

which can be rewritten in terms of $u = \frac{9d-a}{2}, v = \frac{9d+a}{2}$ as:

- (ia) $8v + 4c > 9u$, (ib) $u > -4c$, (ii) $v > 4c$, (iii) $u \neq 5c$.

One infinite family of solutions is as follows. For any integer $x > 1$, let $u = 6x - 1$. Then it is easy to check that $v = 6(3x^2 - x + 27) + 1, c = 1$ is a solution to Equation (54). Note that $u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{9}$. Condition (ia) is true for all x . Conditions (ib) and (iii) hold as $x > 1$. Condition (ii) can be written as $6x^2 - 2x + 53 > 0$, which is true for all real x . Notice that this infinite family has the values:

$$a = 2(9x^2 - 6x + 82), \quad b = 16x^2 - 12x + 147, \quad c = 1, \quad d = 2x^2 + 18.$$

3. Extangential Quadrilaterals

3.1. Basic Notions for Extangential LEQs

An *extangential* quadrilateral is a quadrilateral with an *excircle*, that is, a circle exterior to the quadrilateral that is tangent to the extensions of all four sides [21, 22, 24]. Analogous to Pitot’s Theorem, one has the following result [36]: a quadrilateral with successive side lengths a, b, c, d is extangential if and only if it has no pair of parallel sides and

$$|a - c| = |b - d|.$$

As for Pitot’s Theorem, the above criteria is usually only stated for convex quadrilaterals, but also holds in the concave case. Indeed, if $OABC$ is a concave quadrilateral with reflex angle at B , let A' (respectively C') denote the point of intersection of the side OA (respectively OC) and the extension of side BC (respectively AB). Let a, b, c, d denote the lengths of OA, AB, BC, CO , respectively, and similarly, let a', b', c', d' denote the lengths of $OA', A'B, BC', C'O$. Then $a + b = c + d$ if and only if $a' + b' = c' + d'$. This follows from a result sometimes referred to Urquhart’s quadrilateral theorem, which has a long and interesting history; see [36, 34, 17].

A quadrilateral $OABC$ with successive side lengths a, b, c, d can have at most one excircle and when one exists, its radius r_e , called the *exradius*, is given by the formula $r_e = \frac{K}{|a-c|}$ [21, Theorem 8]. By relabelling the vertices if necessary, we

will suppose throughout this paper that the excircle lies outside the vertex B . In particular, the extangential hypothesis is now $a + b = c + d$, and from the proof of [21, Theorem 8], one has $a > c$ and

$$r_e = \frac{K}{a - c}. \tag{55}$$

For an extangential quadrilateral, one of the diagonals L separates the sides into two pairs of equal sum, and the excircle is located outside one of the vertices joined by L (for kites L is the axis of symmetry). In fact, of these two vertices, the excircle is located outside the vertex at which the quadrilateral makes the largest angle [21]. For concave extangential quadrilaterals, the excircle is located outside the vertex with the reflex angle. Obviously, extangential quadrilaterals cannot have a pair of parallel sides; in particular, no trapezoid is extangential and no parallelogram is extangential even though parallelograms satisfy the $a + b = c + d$ condition.

We remark that there is a strong relationship between tangential and extangential quadrilaterals. Recall from Equation (4) that a quadrilateral $OABC$ is tangential if and only if $a + c = b + d$. If $OABC$ is a convex quadrilateral, and if B' denotes the reflection of B in the perpendicular bisector of AC , then the quadrilateral $OAB'C$ is extangential if and only if $OABC$ is tangential. Moreover, equability is preserved by this construction. However, notice that if $OABC$ is a LEQ, $OAB'C$ may fail to have its vertices on lattice points, as in Figure 7. When $OABC$ is concave, the same construction can be made, but it can happen that $OAB'C$ has self-intersections, as in Figure 8.

Analogous to Proposition 1, we have the following result; its proof is very similar to that of Proposition 1.

Proposition 6. *If $OABC$ is extangential with excircle outside B , then $OABC$ is a kite if and only if the diagonal OB divides $OABC$ into two triangles of equal area.*

Proof. Obviously, if $OABC$ is a kite, then its axis of symmetry diagonal divides $OABC$ into two triangles of equal area. Conversely, applying Heron’s formula to triangle OAB gives

$$\begin{aligned} 16K_A^2 &= (a + b + p)(a + b - p)(a - b + p)(-a + b + p) \\ &= -(a^2 - b^2)^2 + 2(a^2 + b^2)p^2 - p^4. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, from triangle OBC

$$16K_C^2 = -(c^2 - d^2)^2 + 2(c^2 + d^2)p^2 - p^4.$$

Hence, subtracting,

$$2(a^2 + b^2 - c^2 - d^2)p^2 = 16(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a^2 - b^2)^2 - (c^2 - d^2)^2. \tag{56}$$

Figure 7: Tangential to extangential convex quadrilaterals.

Figure 8: Self-intersections can occur in the concave case.

Notice that, using $a + b = c + d$,

$$a^2 + b^2 - c^2 - d^2 = (a - d)(a + d) + (b - c)(b + c) = 2(a - c)(a - d),$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (a^2 - b^2)^2 - (c^2 - d^2)^2 &= (a - b)^2(a + b)^2 - (d - c)^2(c + d)^2 \\ &= 4(a - c)(a - d)(a + b)^2. \end{aligned}$$

So Equation (56) gives

$$(a - c)(a - d)p^2 = 4(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a - c)(a - d)(a + b)^2. \tag{57}$$

Now, assume that $K_A = K_C$. Then Equation (57) gives $(a - c)(a - d)p^2 = (a - c)(a - d)(a + b)^2$. Notice that $p = \pm(a - b)$ is impossible, as otherwise the triangle OAB would be degenerate. Hence, either $a = d$ or $a = c$. If $a = c$, then by the extangential hypothesis, $b = d$ and so $OABC$ is a parallelogram, which is impossible. So $a = d$. Note that as $K_A = K_C$, the points A, C are equidistant from the line through O, B . So the triangles OAB and OBC are congruent, and hence $OABC$ is a kite. \square

Like the incenter of a tangential quadrilateral, the excenter of an extangential quadrilateral lies on the Newton line $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{L}}$ joining the midpoints of the two diagonals. We have not seen this stated explicitly in the literature, but the proof in the tangential case is readily adapted. For example, the vector proof of Anne’s Theorem given in [13, Lemma 1] is valid as is, for signed areas, as the authors indicate, and then [13, Theorem 3] can be easily modified, with two positive areas and two negative areas. Since the excenter I_e lies on the Newton line, I_e is of the form $\lambda_e M_A + (1 - \lambda_e) M_O$ for some $\lambda_e \in [0, 1]$, where we recall M_A, M_O refer to the midpoints of the diagonals AC, OB , respectively.

For the rest of this subsection, $OABC$ denotes an extangential (convex or concave) quadrilateral, with vertices in counterclockwise cyclic order, and a, b, c, d denote the lengths of the sides OA, AB, BC, CO , respectively. We suppose furthermore that the excircle lies outside the vertex B . In particular, the extangential hypothesis is now $a + b = c + d$, and from the proof of [21, Theorem 8], one has $a > c$.

Remark 12. By reflecting in the line $y = x$ if necessary, we may always assume that $a \geq d$. In this case, we have $a - b \geq d - b = a - c > 0$; thus $a > b$. Hence, $a = \max\{a, b, c, d\}$. Similarly, $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$.

For tangential quadrilaterals, equability is equivalent to the condition that the inradius is 2. For extangential quadrilaterals, the equability condition of Equation (55) is equivalent to the condition

$$r_e = \frac{2(a + b)}{a - c}. \tag{58}$$

Note that if $OABC$ is not a kite, then by Proposition 6, $K_A \neq \frac{K}{2}$ and $K_O \neq \frac{K}{2}$. So, for equable extangential quadrilaterals that are not kites, $K_A \neq a + b$ and $K_O \neq a + b$. In fact, one has $K_O \neq a + b$ even when $OABC$ is a kite (with its excircle outside the vertex B). Indeed, otherwise $OABC$ would be a rhombus, and no rhombus is extangential. This will be important in Proposition 10 below.

Analogous to many results for tangential quadrilaterals, there are very similar results for extangential quadrilaterals. Indeed, analogous to Propositions 2, 3, 4 and 5 of Section 2, we have the following four analogous propositions. We omit the proofs which are essentially the same as those of the propositions of Section 2.

Proposition 7. *If $OABC$ is extangential, then $OABC$ is a kite if and only if the Newton line \mathcal{N}_C contains one of the diagonals.*

Proposition 8. *If $OABC$ is extangential, we have the following two expressions for the excenter I_e :*

$$(a) \quad I_e = \frac{r_e}{2} \frac{aC + dA}{K_O}, \quad (b) \quad I_e = A + \frac{r_e}{2} \frac{a(B - A) + bA}{K_A}.$$

Proposition 9. *If $OABC$ is extangential, we have:*

$$(K_A - \frac{r_e}{2}(a - b))(K_O - \frac{r_e}{2}(a + d)) = \frac{r_e^2}{4}(ac - bd).$$

Proposition 10. *If $OABC$ is extangential but is not a kite, we have the following two expressions for the coordinate λ_e :*

$$(a) \quad \lambda_e = \frac{r_e}{2} \cdot \frac{a + b}{K_O - (a + b)}, \quad (b) \quad \lambda_e = 1 - \frac{r_e}{2} \cdot \frac{c - b}{K_A - (a + b)}.$$

Furthermore, the first of the above expressions for λ_e is valid if $OABC$ is a kite.

Example 3. Apart from the rhombus of side length 5 ($K1$, $n = 2$) and the 4×4 square ($K3$, $n = 1$), the lattice equable kites of [4, Theorem 1] are extangential. For each pair n and j , to determine the exradius $r_{e,n,j}$, the excenter $I_{e,n,j}$ and the parameter $\lambda_{e,n,j}$, one can employ Equation (58) and Propositions 8 and 10. Here $I_e = \lambda_e M + (1 - \lambda_e) \frac{B}{2}$, where $M = M_A$. We omit the details, which are completely routine. The results are given in Table 3. Notice that unlike the incenters, the excenters are not necessarily lattice points.

Case	Equation	M	B	r_e	$I_{e,n,j}$	$\lambda_{e,n,j}$
$K1$	$n^2 - 5j^2 = 4$	$\frac{1}{2}(n + 5j)(2, 1)$	$n(2, 1)$	$\frac{2n}{j}$	$\frac{n(n+j)}{2j}(2, 1)$	$\frac{n^2}{5j^2}$
$K2$	$n^2 - 5j^2 = 1$	$(2n + 5j)(2, 1)$	$4n(2, 1)$	$\frac{n}{j}$	$\frac{n(n+2j)}{j}(2, 1)$	$\frac{n^2}{5j^2}$
$K3$	$n^2 - 2j^2 = 1$	$(n + 2j)(2, 2)$	$4n(1, 1)$	$\frac{2n}{j}$	$\frac{2n(n+j)}{j}(1, 1)$	$\frac{n^2}{2j^2}$
$K4$	$2n^2 - j^2 = 1$	$(4n + 3j)(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2})$	$12n(1, 1)$	$\frac{3n}{j}$	$\frac{3n(3n+2j)}{j}(1, 1)$	$\frac{2n^2}{j^2}$

Table 3: The four kite families.

Example 4. Consider the convex extangential LEQ shown on the left of Figure 10; its vertices are $(0, 0)$, $(21, 20)$, $(20, 20)$, $(0, 5)$ and the side lengths are 29, 1, 25, 5. The

Figure 9: Kite with side lengths 3 and 15 (K4, $n = j = 1$).

exradius is $r_e = \frac{K}{a-c} = 15$. By Proposition 8, the excenter I_e is $(15, 35)$, and by Proposition 10, the coordinate λ_e of the excenter is 10.

Similarly, a concave extangential LEQ is shown on the right of Figure 10; its vertices are $(0, 0), (12, 5), (10, 5), (6, 8)$ and the side lengths are 13, 2, 5, 10. The exradius is $r_e = \frac{K}{a-c} = \frac{15}{4}$. By Proposition 8, the excenter I_e is $\frac{5}{4}(9, 7)$, and by Proposition 10, the coordinate λ_e of the excenter is $\frac{25}{16}$.

3.2. Lemmata for Extangential LEQs

For this subsection, $OABC$ denotes a non-kite extangential quadrilateral with successive sides a, b, c, d and with its excircle outside the vertex B , so $a > c$. In particular, it has exradius $r_e = \frac{2(a+b)}{a-c}$. As explained in Remark 12, we may assume $a = \max\{a, b, c, d\}$ and $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$.

The approach adopted in this subsection is the same as that of Subsection 2.3, and the results obtained are analogous, but the calculations are often more complicated. For the convenience of the reader, we repeat Equations (11) and (12):

$$p^2 = a^2 + b^2 \pm 2\sqrt{a^2b^2 - (2K_A)^2}, \tag{59}$$

$$q^2 = a^2 + d^2 \pm 2\sqrt{a^2d^2 - (2K_O)^2}, \tag{60}$$

where p, q are the lengths of the diagonals OB, AC , respectively. As O, A, B, C are lattice points, p^2, q^2 are integers, so by Lemma 1, the integers $a^2b^2 - (2K_A)^2$ and $a^2d^2 - (2K_O)^2$ are squares.

Figure 10: Extantential LEQs; convex(left) and concave(right).

Lemma 9. *One has*

$$p^2 = \frac{8(a+b)(K_A - K_C)}{(a-c)(a-d)} + (a+b)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad q^2 = \frac{8(K_O - K_B)}{a-c} + (a-d)^2.$$

Proof. As $OABC$ is not a kite, by hypothesis, we have $a \neq d$. Arguing exactly as in Proposition 6 we reobtain Equation (57):

$$(a-c)(a-d)p^2 = 4(K_A^2 - K_C^2) + (a-d)(a-c)(a+b)^2,$$

and since $OABC$ is extantential and hence not a parallelogram, $a \neq c$. Thus, as $K_A^2 - K_C^2 = (K_A + K_C)(K_A - K_C) = 2(a+b)(K_A - K_C)$, we obtain the required formula for p^2 .

Similarly, by applying Heron's formula to triangles OAC and BCA , we obtain

$$2(d^2 - c^2 + a^2 - b^2)q^2 = 16(K_O^2 - K_B^2) + (d^2 - a^2)^2 - (b^2 - c^2)^2.$$

Simplifying as in Proposition 6 gives

$$(a-c)(a+b)q^2 = 8(a+b)(K_O - K_B) + (a+b)(a-c)(a-d)^2,$$

from which the required formula for q^2 follows. □

Remark 13. From the above lemma, using Equation (59),

$$\frac{8(a+b)(K_A - (a+b))}{(a-c)(a-d)} = \frac{p^2 - (a+b)^2}{2} = -ab \pm \sqrt{a^2b^2 - (2K_A)^2},$$

which is an integer by Lemma 1. Similarly, $\frac{8(K_O - (a+b))}{a-c}$ is an integer.

Lemma 10. *The integer $abcd - 4(a + b)^2$ is a square, and*

$$K_A = (a + b) + (a - c)(a - d)(a + b) \frac{-(ab + cd) \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2},$$

$$K_O = (a + b) + (a - c) \frac{ad + bc \mp 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16 + (a - c)^2},$$

where the signs of the square roots in the formulas for K_O and K_A are opposite.

Remark 14. In the statement of the above lemma, the terms

$$ab + cd \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad ad + bc \mp 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}$$

are strictly positive. Indeed, using $d = a + b - c$, by the arithmetic mean–geometric mean inequality, $ab + cd \geq 2\sqrt{abcd} > \sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}$. In particular, $K_A < \frac{K}{2} = a + b$ if and only if $a > d$, which is opposite to the situation for tangential LEQs; see Remark 4.

Proof of Lemma 10. From Lemma 9 and Equation (60),

$$\frac{4(K_O - K_B)}{a - c} - ad = \frac{q^2 - a^2 - d^2}{2} = \pm\sqrt{a^2d^2 - (2K_O)^2},$$

so setting $s := \frac{K_O - (a+b)}{a-c}$, squaring, and using $K_O + K_B = 2(a + b)$ gives

$$\alpha s^2 - 2\beta s + \gamma = 0,$$

where

$$\alpha = 16 + (a - c)^2, \quad \beta = ad + bc, \quad \gamma = (a + b)^2.$$

Thus, as $\beta^2 - \alpha\gamma = 4(abcd - 4(a + b)^2)$ (using $a + b = c + d$ again), we have

$$s = \frac{ad + bc \pm 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16 + (a - c)^2},$$

which gives the required formula for K_O . In particular, as s is rational, $abcd - 4(a + b)^2$ is a square, as claimed.

The formula for K_A is similarly obtained by equating p^2 from Lemma 9 and Equation (59). We have

$$\frac{4(a + b)(K_A - K_C)}{(a - c)(a - d)} + ab = \frac{p^2 - a^2 - b^2}{2} = \pm\sqrt{a^2b^2 - (2K_A)^2}.$$

Define $t := \frac{(a+b)(K_A - (a+b))}{(a-c)(a-d)}$. One obtains $\bar{\alpha}t^2 + 2\bar{\beta}t + \bar{\gamma} = 0$, where

$$\bar{\alpha} = 16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2, \quad \bar{\beta} = (a + b)^2(ab + cd), \quad \bar{\gamma} = (a + b)^4.$$

One has

$$\bar{\beta}^2 - \bar{\alpha}\bar{\gamma} = 4(a+b)^4(abcd - 4(a+b)^2),$$

so

$$t = \frac{-(a+b)^2(ab+cd) \pm 2(a+b)^2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a+b)^2}}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2},$$

which gives the required formula for K_O .

It remains to see that the signs of the square roots in the formulas for K_O and K_A are opposite. Let $R = 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a+b)^2}$. Obviously, we may assume that $R \neq 0$ and $a \neq c$. Let us write

$$K_A = (a+b) + (a-c)(a-d)(a+b) \frac{-(ab+cd) + \delta_A R}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2},$$

$$K_O = (a+b) + (a-c) \frac{ad+bc + \delta_O R}{16 + (a-c)^2},$$

where δ_A, δ_O are each ± 1 . Using $a+b = c+d$,

$$K_A - \frac{(a+b)(a-b)}{a-c}$$

$$= (a+b) \left(\frac{b-c}{a-c} + (a-c)(a-d) \frac{-(ab+cd) + \delta_A R}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2} \right)$$

$$= \frac{(a+b)(d-a)}{a-c} \cdot \frac{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(ac+bd) - (a-c)^2\delta_A R}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2},$$

$$K_O - \frac{(a+b)(a+d)}{a-c} = -\frac{(a+b)(c+d)}{a-c} + (a-c) \frac{ad+bc + \delta_O R}{16 + (a-c)^2}$$

$$= \frac{-1}{a-c} \cdot \frac{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(ac+bd) - (a-c)^2\delta_O R}{16 + (a-c)^2}.$$

Notice also that $(a+b)(d-a) = bd - ac$. Hence, by Proposition 9,

$$\frac{X - (a-c)^2\delta_A R}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2} \cdot \frac{X - (a-c)^2\delta_O R}{16 + (a-c)^2} = (a+b)^2, \tag{61}$$

where $X = 16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(ac+bd)$. Now, substituting $d = a+c-b$ one finds that

$$\frac{X - (a-c)^2\delta_A R}{16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(a-d)^2} \cdot \frac{X + (a-c)^2\delta_A R}{16 + (a-c)^2} = (a+b)^2.$$

Subtracting from Equation (61) gives

$$(X - (a-c)^2\delta_A R) \cdot (a-c)^2(\delta_A + \delta_O)R = 0. \tag{62}$$

Note that $X - (a-c)^2\delta_A R \neq 0$ as otherwise $X^2 = (a-c)^4R^2$ which would give

$$(16(a+b)^2 + (a-c)^2(ac+bd))^2 - (a-c)^4(abcd - 4(a+b)^2) = 0,$$

and hence

$$(a + b)^2(16 + (a - c)^2)(16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(b - c)^2) = 0,$$

which is impossible. So from Equation (62), we have $\delta_A = -\delta_O$, as claimed. \square

Lemma 11. *The sign of the square root in the formulas for K_O is positive if and only if B lies within the circumcircle of the triangle OAC ; in particular, the sign for K_O is positive if $OABC$ is concave.*

Proof. In the notation of the above proof, let $x = \delta_O 2\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}$, so

$$K_A = (a + b) + (a - c)(a - d)(a + b) \frac{-(ab + cd) - x}{16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2},$$

$$K_O = (a + b) + (a - c) \frac{ad + bc + x}{16 + (a - c)^2}.$$

From a standard criteria for a point to be within the circumcircle of a triangle (see [16]), B is inside the circumcircle of the triangle OAC if and only if

$$p^2 K_O < d^2 K_A + a^2 K_C. \tag{63}$$

Now, $d^2 K_A + a^2 K_C = K_A(d^2 - a^2) + 2a^2(a + b)$, and by Lemma 9,

$$K_O p^2 = K_O \left(\frac{16(a + b)(K_A - (a + b))}{(a - c)(a - d)} + (a + b)^2 \right).$$

So Condition (63) can be written as $E > 0$ where

$$E = K_A(d^2 - a^2) + 2a^2(a + b) - K_O \left(\frac{16(a + b)(K_A - (a + b))}{(a - c)(a - d)} + (a + b)^2 \right).$$

Substituting the formulas for K_O, K_A and x , one finds upon simplification that

$$E = 2\delta_O(a + b)\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}.$$

Hence, as claimed, $\delta_O > 0$ if and only if B is inside the circumcircle of the triangle OAC . \square

Definition 4. Let

$$\Sigma = 8 \cdot \frac{ad + bc + 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16 + (a - c)^2},$$

$$T = 8(a + b)^2 \cdot \frac{ab + cd + 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}}{16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2},$$

where $\delta = 1$ if B lies within the circumcircle of the triangle OAC , and $\delta = -1$ otherwise.

Remark 15. Observe that Σ and T are positive integers. Indeed, from Lemma 10,

$$\Sigma = \frac{8(K_O - (a + b))}{a - c}, \quad T = \frac{8(a + b)((a + b) - K_A)}{(a - c)(a - d)}, \quad (64)$$

which are integers by Remark 13, and they are positive by Remark 14. Furthermore, from Lemma 2,

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{2}(q^2 - (a - d)^2), \quad T = \frac{1}{2}((a + b)^2 - p^2).$$

In the notation of the proof of Lemma 10,

$$\alpha\Sigma^2 - 16\beta\Sigma + 64\gamma = 0, \quad (65)$$

where $\alpha = 16 + (a - c)^2$, $\beta = ad + bc$, $\gamma = (a + b)^2 = (c + d)^2$, and

$$\bar{\alpha}T^2 - 16\bar{\beta}T + 64\bar{\gamma} = 0,$$

where $\bar{\alpha} = 16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2$, $\bar{\beta} = (a + b)^2(ab + cd)$, and $\bar{\gamma} = (a + b)^4$.

Lemma 12. For Σ, T as defined in Definition 4, the following relations hold:

(a) $\Sigma T = 8\frac{(a+b)^2}{(a-c)^2}(T - \Sigma)$,

(b) $2\Sigma T = (a + b)^2(\Sigma - 8) - (b - c)^2T$.

Proof. (a). As in the proof of Lemma 11, let $x = 2\delta\sqrt{abcd - 4(a + b)^2}$. Then cross-multiplying, the required identity is $E = 0$, where

$$E = (ad + bc + x)(16(a + b)^2 + (a - c)^2(a - d)^2) - (a + b)^2(ab + cd + x)(16 + (a - c)^2) + (a - c)^2(ad + bc + x)(ab + cd + x).$$

Expanding and using $d = a + c - b$, one has

$$E = (a - c)^2(4(4(a + b)^2 - abcd) + x^2).$$

Then replacing x^2 by $4(abcd - 4(a + b)^2)$ gives $E = 0$, as required.

(b). From Definition 4, since $(a - c)^2 = (a - c)(d - b) = ad + bc - ab - cd$,

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b)^2(16 + (a - c)^2)\Sigma - (16(a + b)^2 + (b - c)^2(a - c)^2)T \\ = 8(a + b)^2(ad + bc - ab - cd) = 8(a + b)^2(a - c)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Part (b) follows by applying Part (a). □

Remark 16. As Σ and T are positive, Lemma 12(a) gives $\Sigma < T$. Furthermore, as $T - \Sigma < T$, Lemma 12(a) gives $\Sigma < 8\frac{(a+b)^2}{(a-c)^2}$, and Lemma 12(b) gives $2T < (a + b)^2\frac{\Sigma - 8}{\Sigma} < (a + b)^2$. In particular, $\Sigma > 8$.

Remark 17. From Equation (64),

$$K_O = (a + b) + \frac{1}{8}(a - c)\Sigma, \tag{66}$$

$$K_A = (a + b) - \frac{(a - c)(a - d)}{8(a + b)}T. \tag{67}$$

Then by Proposition 10, the parameter λ_e and the exradius r_e are related to Σ by

$$\lambda_e \cdot \Sigma = 8 \frac{(a + b)^2}{(a - c)^2} = 2r_e^2.$$

Using Lemma 12(a), we can also write

$$\lambda_e = \frac{T}{T - \Sigma}.$$

Remark 18. We have the non-degeneracy condition $K_B \neq 0$ as otherwise ABC would be colinear. Thus $K_O \neq 2(a + b)$ and Equation (66) gives $\Sigma \neq 8\frac{a+b}{a-c}$. Hence, by Lemma 12(a), we have

$$\Sigma(T - \Sigma) \neq 8T.$$

Notice also that $OABC$ is concave if and only if $K_O > 2(a + b)$, that is, from Equation (64), when $\Sigma > 8\frac{a+b}{a-c}$.

Lemma 13. For Σ, T as defined in Definition 4, one has $(c - b)T < (a - b)\Sigma$.

Proof. From the assumption that the vertices O, A, B, C are positively oriented and the assumption that if $OABC$ is concave then the reflex angle is at B , we have $K_A > 0$. So Equation (67) gives $8(a + b)^2 > (a - c)(a - d)T$. Lemma 12(a) gives $8(a + b)^2 = (a - c)^2 \frac{\Sigma T}{T - \Sigma}$. Hence, as $T - \Sigma > 0$ by Remark 16, and using $a + b = c + d$, we obtain $(a - c)\Sigma > (c - b)(T - \Sigma)$. Rearranging this gives the required result. \square

Lemma 14. The integers Σ and T , defined in Definition 4, both divide $8(a + b)^2$.

Proof. From Equation (65), $\frac{1}{16}\alpha\Sigma^2 - \beta\Sigma + 4\gamma = 0$, where $\alpha = 16 + (a - c)^2$, $\beta = ad + bc$, $\gamma = (a + b)^2$. So $\frac{1}{16}\alpha\Sigma^2$ is an integer, and hence $\frac{1}{16}(a - c)^2\Sigma^2$ is an integer. So $\frac{1}{4}(a - c)\Sigma$ is an integer, and hence $\frac{1}{4}\alpha\Sigma$ is an integer. Hence, as

$$16(a + b)^2 = 16\gamma = (-\frac{1}{4}\alpha\Sigma + 4\beta)\Sigma,$$

Σ divides $16(a + b)^2$. So if Σ is odd, then Σ divides $(a + b)^2$. If Σ is even, then as $\frac{1}{32}\alpha\Sigma^2 - \frac{1}{2}\beta\Sigma + 2\gamma = 0$, so $\frac{1}{32}\alpha\Sigma^2$ is an integer, and hence $\frac{1}{32}(a - c)^2\Sigma^2$ is an integer. It follows that $\frac{1}{64}(a - c)^2\Sigma^2$ is an integer. So $\frac{1}{8}(a - c)\Sigma$ is an integer, and hence $\frac{1}{8}\alpha\Sigma$ is an integer. Hence, as

$$8(a + b)^2 = (-\frac{1}{8}\alpha\Sigma + 2\beta)\Sigma,$$

Σ divides $8(a + b)^2$.

By Lemma 12(a), we have $8(a + b)^2(\frac{1}{\Sigma} - \frac{1}{T}) = (a - c)^2$. Since $8(a + b)^2\frac{1}{\Sigma}$ is an integer, it follows that $8(a + b)^2\frac{1}{T}$ is also an integer. \square

3.3. Explicit Examples of Extangential LEQs

In this subsection we exhibit non-kite extangential LEQs in the three cases with (Σ, T) equal to $(9, 18)$, $(18, 50)$ and $(45, 50)$, respectively. Let us define $h := \frac{a+b}{a-c}$, so that $h = \sqrt{\Sigma T / (8(T - \Sigma))}$ by Lemma 12(a). Note that $h > 1$, but as we will see, h may fail to be an integer.

We have

$$b = (h - 1)a - hc. \tag{68}$$

In particular, $b > 0$ gives $a > \frac{h}{h-1}c$ and since $b \leq c$, we have $a \leq \frac{h+1}{h-1}c$. From Equation (65), $\alpha\Sigma^2 - 16\beta\Sigma + 64\gamma = 0$, where $\alpha = 16 + (a - c)^2$, $\beta = ad + bc$, $\gamma = (a + b)^2 = (c + d)^2$. Using Equation (68), substituting $d = a + b - c$ and solving for a gives

$$a = \frac{64ch^2 - 16c\Sigma + c\Sigma^2 \pm 4\sqrt{2c^2\Sigma(8h^2 - \Sigma)(\Sigma - 8) - (\Sigma - 8h)^2\Sigma^2}}{(\Sigma - 8h)^2}.$$

We claim that $\frac{64ch^2 - 16c\Sigma + c\Sigma^2}{(\Sigma - 8h)^2} > \frac{h+1}{h-1}c$. Indeed, cross multiplying and simplifying, the claim is $(8h^2 - \Sigma)(\Sigma - 8) > 0$, which is true since $\Sigma < 8h^2$ by Remark 16 and $\Sigma > 8$, also by Remark 16. Hence, since $a \leq \frac{h+1}{h-1}c$, it follows that

$$a = \frac{64ch^2 - 16c\Sigma + c\Sigma^2 - 4\sqrt{2c^2\Sigma(8h^2 - \Sigma)(\Sigma - 8) - (\Sigma - 8h)^2\Sigma^2}}{(\Sigma - 8h)^2}. \tag{69}$$

We first classify the extangential LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$. Note that this is one of two cases in Theorem 3(a). Suppose we have an extangential LEQ with $a > c \geq b$ and $\Sigma = 9, T = 18$. So $h = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma T}{8(T - \Sigma)}} = \frac{3}{2}$, and from Equation (68),

$$b = \frac{1}{2}(a - 3c). \tag{70}$$

Hence, $a > 3c$ and since $b \leq c$, we have $a \leq 5c$. From Equation (69),

$$a = 9c - 4\sqrt{2c^2 - 9}. \tag{71}$$

Working modulo 3, the fact that $2c^2 - 9$ is a square gives us that c is divisible by 3, say $c = 3v$. Then v satisfies the negative Pell equation

$$u^2 - 2v^2 = -1, \tag{72}$$

for some positive integer u . Then Equations (70) and (71) give

$$(a, b, c, d) = 3(9v - 4u, 3v - 2u, v, 11v - 6u). \tag{73}$$

It is well known that the solutions (u_j, v_j) to Equation (72) are given recursively by

$$u_{j+1} = 3u_j + 4v_j, \quad v_{j+1} = 2u_j + 3v_j, \tag{74}$$

with initial values $(u_1, v_1) = (1, 1)$.

We now define the vertices of our quadrilaterals. Let

$$\begin{aligned} A_j &= \frac{3}{2}(9u_j - 8v_j - 7, 9u_j - 8v_j + 7), \\ B_j &= 6(3u_j - 3v_j - 2, 3u_j - 3v_j + 2), \\ C_j &= \frac{3}{2}(11u_j - 12v_j - 7, 11u_j - 12v_j + 7). \end{aligned}$$

Note that A_j, B_j, C_j are lattice points as u_j, v_j are odd, as one can see from the recursive formula (74). We will consider the quadrilateral $OA_jB_jC_j$. Let a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j denote the lengths of the sides $OA_j, A_jB_j, B_jC_j, C_jO_j$, respectively. The distance a_j is given by

$$\begin{aligned} a_j^2 &= \frac{9}{4}((9u_j - 8v_j - 7)^2 + (9u_j - 8v_j + 7)^2) = \frac{9}{2}(81u_j^2 - 144u_jv_j + 64v_j^2 + 49) \\ &= \frac{9}{2}(81u_j^2 - 144u_jv_j + 64v_j^2 + 49(2v_j^2 - u_j^2)) \quad (\text{by Equation (72)}) \\ &= \frac{9}{2}(32u_j^2 - 144u_jv_j + 162v_j^2) \\ &= 9(9v_j - 4u_j)^2. \end{aligned}$$

So $a_j = 3(9v_j - 4u_j)$. Similarly, the other side lengths are as follows:

$$b_j = 3(3v_j - 2u_j), \quad c_j = 3v_j, \quad d_j = 3(11v_j - 6u_j),$$

as anticipated by Equation (73). So the perimeter of $OA_jB_jC_j$ is $a_j + b_j + c_j + d_j = 36(2v_j - u_j)$.

The area of OA_jB_j is $\frac{1}{2}\|\overrightarrow{OA_j} \times \overrightarrow{OB_j}\| = 9(5v_j - 3u_j)$. The area of OB_jC_j is $\frac{1}{2}\|\overrightarrow{OB_j} \times \overrightarrow{OC_j}\| = 9(3v_j - u_j)$. Notice in passing that the signed areas of OA_jB_j and OB_jC_j are both positive, as one can see recursively using Equation (74), so $OA_jB_jC_j$ has no self-intersection. The area of $OA_jB_jC_j$ is $9(5v_j - 3u_j) + 9(3v_j - u_j) = 36(2v_j - u_j)$, so $OA_jB_jC_j$ has equal area and perimeter, i.e., it is equable. Thus $OA_jB_jC_j$ is a LEQ. Furthermore, $OA_jB_jC_j$ is extangential because $a_j + b_j = c_j + d_j$.

The first member of this family, corresponding to the initial condition $(u_1, v_1) = (1, 1)$, is the kite with side lengths 15, 3, 3, 15 shown in Figure 9. The vertices and

u_j	v_j	A_j	B_j	C_j	a_j	b_j	c_j	d_j
7	5	(24,45)	(24,48)	(15,36)	51	3	15	39
41	29	(195,216)	(204,228)	(144,165)	291	15	87	219
239	169	(1188,1209)	(1248,1272)	(891,912)	1695	87	507	1275
1393	985	(6975,6996)	(7332,7356)	(5244,5265)	9879	507	2955	7431

Table 4: Four members of the $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$ family.

side lengths of the next four members of this family are given in Table 4. The case $(u_2, v_2) = (7, 5)$ of the family is shown in Figure 11.

The exradius of $OA_jB_jC_j$ is $r_{e,j} = \frac{K(OA_jB_jC_j)}{a_j - c_j}$. Substituting the values gives $r_{e,j} = 3$ for each j . Then by Proposition 8, the excenter is $I_{e,j} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{a_j C_j + d_j A_j}{K(OA_jC_j)}$, which simplifies to $15(1, -1) + 21(u_j + 7v_j)(1, 1)$. In particular, the excenter of each family member is a lattice point. By Proposition 10, the coordinate $\lambda_{e,j}$ of the excenter is $\lambda_{e,j} = \frac{3(a_j + b_j)}{2K(OA_jC_j) - 3(a_j - c_j)}$. Substituting the values gives $\lambda_{e,j} = 2$ for each j .

Remark 19. By Remark 18, an extangential LEQ $OABC$ is concave if and only if $\Sigma > 8\frac{a+b}{a-c}$; that is, if and only if $\Sigma > 8h$. For the above family, with $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$, we have $h = \frac{3}{2}$. So all members of this family are convex.

Now, suppose we have an extangential LEQ with $a > c \geq b$ and $\Sigma = 18, T = 50$. Note that this is the other case in Theorem 3(a). So $h = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma T}{8(T - \Sigma)}} = \frac{15}{8}$ and Equation (68) gives

$$b = \frac{1}{8}(7a - 15c). \tag{75}$$

Hence, $a > 15/7c$ and since $b \leq c$, we have $a \leq 23c/7$. From Equation (69),

$$a = 29c - 12\sqrt{5c^2 - 4}. \tag{76}$$

So c satisfies the Pell-like equation

$$u^2 - 5c^2 = -4, \tag{77}$$

for some positive integer u . Then Equations (75) and (76) give

$$(a, b, c, d) = (29c - 12u, \frac{1}{2}(47c - 21u), c, \frac{1}{2}(103c - 45u)). \tag{78}$$

From [28], the solutions to Equation (77) are $(u_j, c_j) = (L_{2j-1}, F_{2j-1})$, where L_j is the j -th Lucas number and F_j is the j -th Fibonacci number. (Recall that the Lucas and Fibonacci numbers satisfy the same recurrence relation but with different initial conditions: $F_1 = F_2 = 1$ while $L_1 = 1, L_2 = 3$). Hence, Equation (78) gives the potential solutions

$$(a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) = F_{2j-1}(29, \frac{47}{2}, 1, \frac{103}{2}) - L_{2j-1}(12, \frac{21}{2}, 0, \frac{45}{2}). \tag{79}$$

Figure 11: The case $j = 2$ of the $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$ family.

From Lemma 13, $T(c - b) < \Sigma(a - b)$. So $50(c - b) < 18(a - b)$ and thus from Equations (75) and (76), $51c > 23u$, which is

$$51F_{2j-1} > 23L_{2j-1}. \tag{80}$$

Now, $F_6 = 8, L_6 = 18$ and $F_7 = 13, L_7 = 29$, and thus $51F_6 < 23L_6$ and $51F_7 < 23L_7$. It follows from the Lucas and Fibonacci recurrence relation that Inequality (80) only holds for $j = 1, 2, 3$. For $i = 1, 2$ one finds using Equation (79) that $a_j < d_j$, contrary to our hypothesis. So the only possibility is $j = 3$, which gives the solution $(a, b, c, d) = (13, 2, 5, 10)$, which is the concave LEQ that we saw in Subsection 3.2, shown on the right of Figure 10.

Now, suppose we have an extangential LEQ with $a > c \geq b$ and $\Sigma = 45, T = 50$.

Note that this is the case $m = 3$ in Theorem 3(b). So $h = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma T}{8(T-\Sigma)}} = \frac{15}{2}$ and Equation (68) gives

$$b = \frac{1}{2}(13a - 15c). \tag{81}$$

Hence, $a > 15/13c$ and since $b \leq c$, we have $a \leq 17c/13$. From Equation (69),

$$a = \frac{1}{5}(109c - 12\sqrt{74c^2 - 25}). \tag{82}$$

So c satisfies the Pell-like equation

$$W^2 - 74c^2 = -25, \tag{83}$$

for some positive integer W . The solutions to this equation are not readily enumerated, and moreover, some solutions do not result in LEQs. For example, for the solution $W = 5927, c = 689$, one obtains the non-integer value $a = \frac{3977}{5}$ from Equation (82). We will restrict ourselves to constructing a particular infinite family of LEQs for which c is divisible by 5. Set $w = 5u, c = 5v$, so that Equation (82) gives the negative Pell equation $u^2 - 74v^2 = -1$. Let us denote its solutions (u_j, v_j) , where $(u_1, v_1) = (43, 5)$ and $(u_2, v_2) = (318157, 36985)$. So

$$u_j^2 - 74v_j^2 = -1.$$

The solutions (u_j, v_j) are well known; see entries A228546 and A228547 in [37]. In particular, they satisfy the second order recurrence relation

$$X_{j+2} = 7398X_{j+1} - X_j. \tag{84}$$

It follows from this recurrence relation and the initial conditions that u_j is divisible by 43 and v_j is divisible by 5 for all j . Let $x_j = u_j/43, y_j = v_j/5$, so

$$43^2x_j^2 - 74 \cdot 25y_j^2 = -1,$$

and $(x_1, y_1) = (1, 1)$ and $(x_2, y_2) = (7399, 7397)$. Note that (x_j, y_j) also satisfies the recurrence relation of Equation (84). We have $c_j = 25y_j$ and from Equation (82), $a_j = \frac{1}{5}(109c_j - 60u_j) = -12 \cdot 43x_j + 545y_j$. Then from Equation (81), $b_j = \frac{1}{2}(13a_j - 15c_j) = -3354x_j + 3355y_j$. Thus, as $d_j = a_j + b_j - c_j$,

$$(a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) = -x_j(516, 3354, 0, 3870) + y_j(545, 3355, 25, 3875). \tag{85}$$

In particular, (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) are determined by the recurrence relation (84) with $(a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1) = (29, 1, 25, 5)$ and $(a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2) = (213481, 689, 184925, 29245)$. The first three members of this family are shown in Table 5.

We have shown above that if an extangential LEQ with side lengths a, b, c, d has $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ and c is divisible by 5, then $(a, b, c, d) = (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j)$ for some

a_j	b_j	c_j	d_j
29	1	25	5
213481	689	184925	29245
1579332409	5097221	1368075125	216354505

Table 5: Side lengths of three members of the $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ family.

j , where (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) is given by Equation (85). We now show that conversely, for each j , the 4-tuples (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) given by Equation (85) are realized by the side lengths of an extangential LEQ. We mention in passing that the difficulty in determining suitable vertices is two-fold. Firstly, the quadrilaterals in this family grow so fast that we only had three examples to base our study on, and secondly, the pattern of the vertex coordinates is considerably more complicated than in the $(\Sigma, T) = (8, 18)$ family exhibited above.

To define the vertices, we will employ the following two first-order recurrence relations in two variables

$$x_{j+1} = 78x_j + 25y_j, \quad y_{j+1} = 25x_j + 8y_j, \tag{86}$$

$$x_{j+1} = 68x_j + 35y_j, \quad y_{j+1} = 35x_j + 18y_j, \tag{87}$$

under various initial conditions. We identify the 2-tuple $(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ with the Gaussian integer $x + yi \in \mathbb{C}$, and we use the notations interchangeably, according to convenience. Consider the following families, for all $j \geq 1$:

- (a) $z_{a,j} = x_{a,j} + y_{a,j}i$ satisfies Equation (86) with $z_{a,1} = 5 + 2i$,
- (b) $z_{b,j} = x_{b,j} + y_{b,j}i$ satisfies Equation (86) with $z_{b,1} = i$,
- (c) $z_{c,j} = x_{c,j} + y_{c,j}i$ satisfies Equation (87) with $z_{c,1} = 2 + i$,
- (d) $z_{d,j} = x_{d,j} + y_{d,j}i$ satisfies Equation (87) with $z_{d,1} = 1$.

Let $\rho : \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^2$ denote the reflection in the line $y = x$, so $\rho(x, y) = (y, x)$ or equivalently $\rho(z) = i\bar{z}$, where \bar{z} denotes the complex conjugate of z . Let ρ^j denote the j -th iterate of ρ under composition, so $\rho^j = \rho$ if j is odd and $\rho^j = \text{id}$ otherwise. We now define the vertices. Set

$$A_j = \rho^{j+1}z_{a,j}^2, \quad B_j = A_j + \rho^{j+1}z_{b,j}^2, \quad C_j = 5\rho^jz_{d,j}^2, \quad B'_j = C_j + 5\rho^jz_{c,j}^2.$$

The first three members of this family are shown in Table 6; the LEQ given in the first row is shown on the left of Figure 10.

We will establish the following properties:

- (i) $B_j = B'_j$ for all j ,

A_j	B_j	C_j
(21, 20)	(20, 20)	(0, 5)
(124080, 173719)	(124480, 174280)	(16995, 23800)
(1285155641, 917968320)	(1289303420, 920931020)	(176054900, 125753505)

Table 6: Vertices of three members of the $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ family.

- (ii) The areas K_{A_j}, K_{C_j} of triangles OA_jB_j and B_jC_jO are positive (and hence $OA_jB_jC_j$ is a non-self-intersecting, positively oriented quadrilateral),
- (iii) $OA_jB_jC_j$ has the side lengths a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j given by Equation (85),
- (iv) $a_j + b_j = c_j + d_j$; i.e., $OA_jB_jC_j$ is extangential,
- (v) $a_j + b_j + c_j + d_j = K_{A_j} + K_{C_j}$; i.e., $OA_jB_jC_j$ is equable.

The proofs of these properties will use the following technical results.

Lemma 15. *Suppose the sequence $z_j = (x_j, y_j)$ satisfies either Equation (86) or Equation (87). Then for all $j \geq 1$,*

- (a) $z_{j+2} = 86z_{j+1} + z_j$,
- (b) $|z_{j+2}^2| = 7398|z_{j+1}^2| - |z_j^2|$ (i.e., $|z_j^2|$ satisfies Equation (84)),
- (c) $z_{a,j+2}^2 = 7398z_{a,j+1}^2 - z_{a,j}^2 + (-1)^j(17500 - 24500i)$,
- (d) $z_{b,j+2}^2 = 7398z_{b,j+1}^2 - z_{b,j}^2 + (-1)^j(2500 - 3500i)$,
- (e) $z_{c,j+2}^2 = 7398z_{c,j+1}^2 - z_{c,j}^2 - (-1)^j(700 - 500i)$,
- (f) $z_{d,j+2}^2 = 7398z_{d,j+1}^2 - z_{d,j}^2 - (-1)^j(4900 - 3500i)$.

Proof. (a). It is easy to see that if z_j (regarded as a 2-tuple) satisfies the relation $z_{j+1} = Mz_j$, where

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ \gamma & \delta \end{pmatrix},$$

then $z_{j+2} = \text{tr}(M)z_{j+1} - \det(M)z_j$. The result follows as $68 + 18 = 78 + 8 = 86$ and $68 \cdot 18 - 35^2 = 78 \cdot 8 - 25^2 = -1$.

- (b). From (a) we have $|z_{j+2}^2| = (86x_{j+1} + x_j)^2 + (86y_{j+1} + y_j)^2$, so

$$|z_{j+2}^2| = 86^2|z_{j+1}^2| + |z_j^2| + 172(x_{j+1}x_j + y_jy_j).$$

Assume first that Equation (86) holds. Then using Equation (86) twice,

$$\begin{aligned} |z_{j+1}^2| - |z_j^2| &= (x_{j+1}^2 + y_{j+1}^2) - (x_j^2 + y_j^2) \\ &= (68^2 + 35^2 - 1)x_j^2 + (35^2 + 18^2 - 1)y_j^2 + 2 \cdot (68 + 18) \cdot 35x_jy_j \\ &= 86(68x_j^2 + 70x_jy_j + 18y_j^2) \\ &= 86(x_{j+1}x_j + y_{j+1}y_j), \end{aligned}$$

so $|z_{j+2}^2| = (86^2 + 2)|z_{j+1}^2| - |z_j^2| = 7398|z_{j+1}^2| - |z_j^2|$, as required. A similar argument applies when Equation (87) holds.

(c). From (a) we have $z_{a,j+2}^2 = 7396z_{a,j+1}^2 + 172z_{a,j+1}z_{a,j} + z_{a,j}^2$. So we are required to show that $172z_{a,j+1}z_{a,j} + 2z_{a,j}^2 = 2z_{a,j+1}^2 + (-1)^j(17500 - 24500i)$, or equivalently, using Equation (86), $5x_{a,j}^2 - 14x_{a,j}y_{a,j} - 5y_{a,j}^2 = 35(-1)^j$, for all j . In matrix notation, the condition is $z_j Q z_j^t = 35(-1)^j$, where $z_j = (x_{a,j}, y_{a,j})$, z^t denotes the transpose of z , and

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & -7 \\ -7 & -14 \end{pmatrix}.$$

One readily verifies that this condition holds for $j = 1$, where $z_1 = (5, 2)$. Now, using Equation (86) and setting $M = \begin{pmatrix} 78 & 25 \\ 25 & 8 \end{pmatrix}$, we have $z_{j+1} Q z_{j+1}^t = (z_j M) Q (M z_j^t) = -z_j Q z_j^t$, since $M Q M = -Q$. So the required result follows by induction. This proves (c).

Part (d) is proven in the same manner; only the initial condition is different. For parts (e) and (f), one repeats the argument using the matrices

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & -5 \\ -5 & -7 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M = \begin{pmatrix} 68 & 35 \\ 35 & 18 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Once again, the argument works because $M Q M = -Q$. □

Remark 20. It is well known that if a sequence r_j satisfies a second-order homogeneous recurrence relation, then r_j^2 satisfies a third-order recurrence relation, but in certain exceptional circumstances, r_j^2 may satisfy a second-order recurrence relation, which is typically non-homogeneous [11]. In this respect, Lemma 15 is perhaps somewhat surprising.

(i). We have $B_1 = (5 + 2i)^2 + i^2 = 20 + 20i$ and $B'_1 = 5\rho((2 + i)^2 + 1^2) = B_1$, while $B_2 = \rho((78 \cdot 5 + 25 \cdot 2 + (25 \cdot 5 + 8 \cdot 2)i)^2 + (25 + 8i)^2) = 124480 + 174280i$, and $B'_2 = 5((68 \cdot 2 + 35 + (35 \cdot 2 + 18)i)^2 + (68 + 35i)^2) = B_2$. From Lemma 15(c) and (d), we have for all j ,

$$\begin{aligned} B_{j+2} &= 7398\rho(B_{j+1}) - B_j + (-1)^j \rho^{j+1}(17500 - 24500i + 2500 - 3500i) \\ &= 7398\rho(B_{j+1}) - B_j + (-1)^j \rho^{j+1}(20000 - 28000i), \end{aligned}$$

and from Lemma 15(e) and (f), we have

$$\begin{aligned} B'_{j+2} &= 7398\rho(B'_{j+1}) - B_j - (-1)^j 5\rho^j(700 - 500i + 4900 - 3500i) \\ &= 7398\rho(B_{j+1}) - B_j - (-1)^j \rho^j(28000 - 20000i) = B_{j+2}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $B_j = B'_j$ for all j .

(ii). Regarding A_j and B_j as complex numbers, one has $K_{A_j} = \frac{i}{4}(A_j\overline{B_j} - \overline{A_j}B_j)$. Hence, when j is odd,

$$K_{A_j} = \frac{i}{4}(z_{a,j}^2\overline{z_{b,j}^2} - \overline{z_{a,j}^2}z_{b,j}^2) = (x_{a,j}y_{b,j} - x_{b,j}y_{a,j})(x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + y_{a,j}y_{b,j}),$$

while when j is even,

$$\begin{aligned} K_{A_j} &= \frac{i}{4}(\rho(z_{a,j}^2)\rho(\overline{z_{b,j}^2}) - \rho(\overline{z_{a,j}^2})\rho(z_{b,j}^2)) = \frac{i}{4}(\overline{z_{a,j}^2}z_{b,j}^2 - z_{a,j}^2\overline{z_{b,j}^2}) \\ &= -(x_{a,j}y_{b,j} - x_{b,j}y_{a,j})(x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + y_{a,j}y_{b,j}). \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see that $x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + y_{a,j}y_{b,j} > 0$. Moreover, $x_{a,j}y_{b,j} - x_{b,j}y_{a,j}$ is the area K_j of the parallelogram P_j spanned by $z_{a,j}$ and $z_{b,j}$. So we are required to show that $(-1)^{j+1}K_j > 0$ for all j . For $j = 1$, one has $K_1 = 5$. Furthermore, P_{j+1} is the image of P_j under the linear transformation with matrix $M = \begin{pmatrix} 78 & 25 \\ 25 & 8 \end{pmatrix}$, which has determinant -1 . Hence, $K_j = (-1)^{j+1}5$, giving the required result.

A similar reasoning applies for K_{C_j} . Here

$$K_{C_j} = (-1)^j 25 \frac{i}{4}(z_{c,j}^2\overline{z_{d,j}^2} - \overline{z_{c,j}^2}z_{d,j}^2) = (-1)^j 25 (x_{c,j}y_{d,j} - x_{d,j}y_{c,j})(x_{c,j}x_{d,j} + y_{c,j}y_{d,j}).$$

Setting $K_j = x_{c,j}y_{d,j} - x_{d,j}y_{c,j}$, one argues as before, using $K_1 = -4$ and the fact that $\begin{pmatrix} 68 & 35 \\ 35 & 18 \end{pmatrix}$ has determinant -1 .

(iii). As observed above, the lengths (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j) are determined by the recurrence relation of Equation (84) with

$$(a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1) = (29, 1, 25, 5) \text{ and } (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2) = (213481, 689, 184925, 29245).$$

The side OA_j has length $|z_{a,j}^2|$. Hence, as $|z_{a,1}^2| = 29$ and from Equation (86), $|z_{a,2}^2| = (78 \cdot 5 + 25 \cdot 2)^2 + (25 \cdot 5 + 8 \cdot 2)^2 = 213481$, so Lemma 15(b) gives $|OA_j| = a_j$ for all j . By the same reasoning, the sides A_jB_j, B_jC_j, C_jO have lengths b_j, c_j, d_j , respectively.

(iv). We have $a_j + b_j = |z_{a,j}^2| + |z_{b,j}^2|$ and $c_j + d_j = (|z_{c,j}^2| + |z_{d,j}^2|)$. So $a_j + b_j$ and $c_j + d_j$ satisfy the recurrence relation of Equation (84), by Lemma 15(b). Hence, since $a_1 + b_1 = 30 = c_1 + d_1$ and $a_2 + b_2 = 214170 = c_2 + d_2$, we have $a_j + b_j = c_j + d_j$ for all j , as required.

(v). As we saw above, $a_j + b_j + c_j + d_j$ satisfies recurrence relation (84) and $a_1 + b_1 + c_1 + d_1 = 60$ and $a_2 + b_2 + c_2 + d_2 = 428340$. From above,

$$K_{A_j} = (-1)^{j+1} \frac{i}{4}(z_{a,j}^2\overline{z_{b,j}^2} - \overline{z_{a,j}^2}z_{b,j}^2), \quad K_{C_j} = (-1)^j 25 \frac{i}{4}(z_{c,j}^2\overline{z_{d,j}^2} - \overline{z_{c,j}^2}z_{d,j}^2).$$

One finds easily that $K_{A_1} + K_{C_1} = 60$ and $K_{A_1} + K_{C_1} = 428340$. So it remains to show that $K_{A_j} + K_{C_j}$ satisfies Equation (84). In fact, we will show that K_{A_j} and

K_{C_j} both satisfy Equation (84). As we saw in the proof of property (ii),

$$K_{A_j} = (-1)^{j+1}(x_{a,j}y_{b,j} - x_{b,j}y_{a,j})(x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + y_{a,j}y_{b,j}),$$

and $(-1)^{j+1}(x_{a,j}y_{b,j} - x_{b,j}y_{a,j}) = 5$. So we will show that $r_j := x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + y_{a,j}y_{b,j}$ satisfies Equation (84). Using Equation (86) three times, we have

$$\begin{aligned} r_{j+2} &= 6709x_{a,j+1}x_{b,j+1} + 2150x_{b,j+1}y_{a,j+1} + 2150x_{a,j+1}y_{b,j+1} + 689y_{a,j+1}y_{b,j+1} \\ &= 49633181x_{a,j}x_{b,j} + 15905700x_{b,j}y_{a,j} + 15905700x_{a,j}y_{b,j} + 5097221y_{a,j}y_{b,j} \\ &= 7398r_{j+1} - r_j, \end{aligned}$$

as required. The proof that K_{C_j} satisfies Equation (84) is obtained in exactly the same manner, using Equation (87).

Remark 21. We have just determined all extangential LEQs with side lengths a, b, c, d that have $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ and c is divisible by 5. However, there are extangential LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ for which c is not divisible by 5. Here are two examples: the LEQ with vertices $A = (6300, 4505)$, $B = (6320, 4520)$, $C = (861, 620)$ and side lengths 7745, 25, 6709, 1061, and the LEQ with vertices $A = (33303495, 46624900)$, $B = (33410980, 46775380)$, $C = (4562280, 6387199)$ and side lengths 57297505, 184925, 49633181, 7849249.

Remark 22. By Remark 18, an extangential LEQ $OABC$ is concave if and only if $\Sigma > 8\frac{a+b}{a-c} = 8h$. As we saw above, for extangential LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$, we have $h = \frac{15}{2}$. So all extangential LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (45, 50)$ are convex.

3.4. Theorem 3 from Theorem 4

As in the previous subsection, let $OABC$ be a non-kite extangential LEQ with sides a, b, c, d and with its excircle outside the vertex B . As explained in Remark 12, we may assume $a = \max\{a, b, c, d\}$ and $b = \min\{a, b, c, d\}$. We introduce some new variables.

Definition 5. Let $x = a + b, y = a - c, z = c - b$. By Lemma 14, Σ and T both divide $8x^2$. Define k by $8x^2 = kT$. By Remark 16, $\Sigma < T$. Let $\Sigma' = T - \Sigma$.

From our previous observations we now extract four important consequences.

- By Lemma 12(b), $16\Sigma x^2 = kx^2(\Sigma - 8) - 8x^2z^2$, so $\Sigma = \frac{8(k+z^2)}{k-16}$. In particular, $k > 16$.
- By Lemma 12(a), $8x^2\Sigma' = y^2\Sigma T = \frac{1}{k}8x^2y^2\Sigma$, so $\Sigma' = \frac{y^2\Sigma}{k}$ and thus $T = \Sigma + \Sigma' = \frac{(k+y^2)\Sigma}{k}$.
- From the definitions, $x = \sqrt{\frac{k(\Sigma+\Sigma')}{8}}$.

- By Lemma 13, $(c - b)T < (a - b)\Sigma$, so by (b), $z(k + y^2) < k(y + z)$ and hence $yz < k$.

It follows that the hypotheses of Theorem 4 are satisfied. So one of the following holds:

- (a) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (9, 9), (12, 24), (16, 16), (24, 12), (10, 40), (40, 10)$ or $(18, 32)$,
- (b) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (5m^2, 5)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 10n^2 = -1$ and $(5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$,
- (c) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (m^2, 1)$ for some integer m for which there exists integers n, Y, Z such that $m^2 - 2n^2 = -1$ and $(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$.

In case (a), we have

$$(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18), (12, 36), (16, 32), (24, 36), (10, 50), (40, 50) \text{ or } (18, 50).$$

Note that in the cases $(\Sigma, T) = (12, 36), (16, 32), (24, 36), (10, 50), (40, 50)$, we have $\Sigma(T - \Sigma) = 8T$, so these are all degenerate cases which are excluded by Remark 18. Thus $(\Sigma, T) = (9, 18)$ or $(18, 50)$, as required.

In case (b), we have $(\Sigma, T) = (5m^2, m^2 + 5)$, and in case (c), we have $(\Sigma, T) = (m^2, m^2 + 1)$, as required.

3.5. Proof of Theorem 4

The proof of Theorem 4 will occupy us for most of the rest of this paper. The general strategy is to analyse the different possibilities for the ratio Σ'/Σ . Suppose $\Sigma' = \frac{u}{v}\Sigma$, where $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$. From the definition of Σ' , we have $vy^2 = uk$. Then the assumption $k > yz$ gives $vy^2 > uyz$ so $vy > uz$. From the definition of x , we have

$$x = \sqrt{\frac{k(\Sigma + \Sigma')}{8}} = \sqrt{\frac{y^2(u + v)\Sigma}{8u}}. \tag{88}$$

From the definition of Σ , we have

$$\Sigma(vy^2 - 16u) = 8(uz^2 + vy^2). \tag{89}$$

Throughout this subsection, we use the following notation.

Definition 6. For an integer n , we let $f(n)$ denote the square-free part of n , and write $n = f(n)s^2(n)$.

Since $vy^2 = uk$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$, we have that $f(u)s(u)$ divides y , say $y = f(u)s(u)y'$. So $vy > uz$ gives

$$vy' > s(u)z. \tag{90}$$

Furthermore, $y^2 = f(u)uy'^2$ and Equation (89) gives

$$\Sigma(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 8(z^2 + vf(u)y'^2), \tag{91}$$

and from Equation (88) we have

$$x = \sqrt{\frac{y'^2 f(u)(u+v)\Sigma}{8}}. \tag{92}$$

We split the problem up into 6 cases:

1. u is odd, v is even and the 2-adic order of v is even.
2. u is odd, v is even and the 2-adic order of v is odd.
3. u is even, v is odd and the 2-adic order of u is even.
4. u is even, v is odd and the 2-adic order of u is odd.
5. u and v are both odd and the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is even.
6. u and v are both odd and the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is odd.

In each case, we make several change of variables. These will be introduced as we go along, but for the convenience of the reader, we summarize the main variables in Table 7.

Case	Σ	w	y	z
1	$2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$f(v)s(v)w'$	$f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$f(v)s(v)f(u)z''$
2	$2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$\frac{1}{2}f(v)s(v)w'$	$\frac{1}{2}f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$\frac{1}{2}f(v)s(v)f(u)z''$
3	$2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$f(v)s(v)w'$	$f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$\frac{1}{4}f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$
4	$\frac{1}{2}f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$f(v)s(v)w'$	$f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$\frac{1}{2}f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$
5	$2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$f(v)s(v)w'$	$f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$
6	$\frac{1}{2}f(u+v)f(u)w^2$	$f(v)s(v)w'$	$f(u)s(u)f(v)y''$	$f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$

Table 7: Variable changes.

Remark 23. There are 29 lemmas in the following proof. For each of these, the stated result is only valid under the assumptions of the particular case (1 through 6) in which the lemma occurs. In each lemma, the function f is defined in Definition 6, the variables u, v are as defined at the start of this subsection, and the variables w' and y'' are given in Table 7 for the particular case in question.

Case 1. Assume u is odd, v is even and the 2-adic order of v is even.

We will show that in this case, $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (40, 10)$ is the only possibility.

As x is an integer, and as $u, u + v$ are relatively prime odd integers, from Equation (92) we can write $\Sigma = 2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$, for some w . Note v divides Σ as

$v\Sigma' = u\Sigma$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$. So v divides $2w^2$, and thus as the 2-adic order of v is even, v divides w^2 . Hence, $f(v)s(v)$ divides w . Thus, setting $w = f(v)s(v)w'$ we have $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$ and Equation (91) gives

$$f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 4(z^2 + vf(u)y'^2). \tag{93}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $4z^2$, so $f(v)s(v)f(u)$ divides $2z$, say $2z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$. So Inequality (90) gives $2vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$ and hence

$$2s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z', \tag{94}$$

and Equation (93) gives

$$f(u + v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = f(v)f(u)z'^2 + 4y'^2. \tag{95}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides $4y'^2$. Since the 2-adic order of v is even, $f(v)$ is odd, so $f(v)$ divides y' . Let $y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (94) gives $2f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z'$, and Equation (95) gives $f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = f(u)z'^2 + 4f(v)y''^2$. From this last equation, notice that as v is even and $f(u)$ is odd, z' must be even, say $z' = 2z''$. Then Inequality (94) gives $f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z''$ and so

$$vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z''^2, \tag{96}$$

and Equation (95) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = 4(f(u)z''^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{97}$$

Note that from the left-hand side of Equation (97), we have

$$vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16.$$

Furthermore, Inequality (96) and Equation (97) give

$$uf(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) < 4(v + u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{f(v + u)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{98}$$

A slightly weaker but useful consequence is

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{99}$$

We will use Inequalities (98) and (99) repeatedly to derive contradictions with the fact that, being a positive integer, $w' \geq 1$. Note that Inequality (98) is only useful when we know something about $f(u + v)$, so Inequality (99) will be more commonly applied. Even so, we sometimes only have information about $uf(u)$, and not about $f(u)$, for which we use the trivial bound $f(u) \geq 1$.

v	4	12	16	20	28	36	44	48	52	64	80	100
$f(v)$	1	3	1	5	7	1	11	3	13	1	5	1
$vf(v)$	4	36	16	100	196	36	484	144	676	64	400	100
$vf^2(v)$	4	108	16	500	1372	36	5324	432	8788	64	2000	100

Table 8: The first twelve even positive integers with even 2-adic order.

Remark 24. The first twelve possible values of v are shown in Table 8. Notice that the sequence $vf(v)$ is not monotonically increasing in v . By the Case 1 hypothesis, v is divisible by 4, so $v \geq 4$. It is easy to verify that the following hold:

- if $v > 4$, then $v \geq 12, vf(v) \geq 16$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 16$,
- if $vf^2(v) \geq 16$, then either $v = 16$ or $vf(v) \geq 36$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 36$,
- if $vf^2(v) \geq 36$, then either $v = 36$ or $vf(v) \geq 64$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 64$,
- if $vf^2(v) \geq 64$, then either $v = 64$ or $vf(v) \geq 100$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 100$.

Note also that if $u > 1$, then $u \geq 3$ and $uf(u) \geq 9$.

Lemma 16. *Either $u = 1$ or $v = 4$ or $y'' = 1$.*

Proof. It suffices to note that if $u > 1, v > 4$ and $y'' > 1$, then Inequality (99) would give

$$w^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{16} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{16 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{25}{27} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 17. *We have $y'' \neq 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $y'' = 1$. Then Inequality (96) gives $vf(v) > uf(u)z''^2 \geq uf(u)$. Also, from Inequality (94), $vf^2(v)f(u) > 16$. So if $v = 4$, then $vf(v) = vf^2(v) = 4$ and hence $f(u) > 4$, contradicting the fact that $vf(v) > uf(u)$. Hence, $v > 4$ and so, by Remark 24, $vf^2(v) \geq 16$. By Remark 24 again, if $vf^2(v) = 16$, then $v = 16$, in which case $vf^2(v)f(u) > 16$ gives $f(u) \geq 3$, so $u \geq 3$ and $uf(u) \geq 9$. Then Inequality (99) would give

$$w^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{48} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{48 - 16} \right) = \frac{19}{24} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Thus $vf(v) > 16$ and hence $vf^2(v) \geq 36$ and $vf(v) \geq 36$, by Remark 24. Then if $u > 1$ one would have $u \geq 3$ and $uf(u) \geq 9$ and Inequality (99) would give

$$w^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{36 - 16} \right) = 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $u = 1$. Then Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{36 - 16} \right) = \frac{37}{5},$$

and hence $w' = 1$ or 2 . Now, Equation (97) gives

$$f(1 + v)w'^2(vf^2(v) - 16) = 4(z''^2 + f(v)). \tag{100}$$

By Remark 24, if $vf^2(v) \geq 36$, then either $v = 36$, or $vf(v) \geq 64$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 64$. If $v = 36$, then Inequality (98) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{37} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{36 - 16} \right) = \frac{1}{5},$$

which is a contradiction. So $vf(v) \geq 64$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 64$. Now, if $vf^2(v) = 64$, then Inequality (98) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{65} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{64} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{64 - 16} \right) = \frac{1}{12},$$

which is a contradiction. So by Remark 24, $vf(v) \geq 100$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 100$. Notice that $f(v) = 1, 3$ or $f(v) \geq 5$. If $f(v) \geq 5$, then Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{100} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{100 - 16} \right) = 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) = 1$ or 3 . If $f(v) = 3$, then Equation (100) gives $f(1+v)w'^2(9v-16) = 4z''^2+12$, with $w' = 1$ or 2 , so modulo 3 , $-f(1+v) \equiv z''^2$. But if $f(v) = 3$, then $v + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Hence, since $v + 1 = f(v + 1)s^2(v + 1)$, we have $f(v + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. But then $-1 \equiv z''^2 \pmod{3}$, which is impossible. So $f(v) = 1$ and hence v is an even square, $v = 4n^2$ say. Notice that as $vf^2(v) \geq 100$ and $f(v) = 1$, we have $n \geq 5$. Equation (100) gives $f(1 + 4n^2)w'^2(4n^2 - 16) = 4z''^2 + 4$, hence

$$f(1 + 4n^2)w'^2(n^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 1.$$

This is impossible modulo 4 if $w' = 2$, so $w' = 1$. So

$$f(1 + 4n^2)(n^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 1. \tag{101}$$

Note that $f(1 + 4n^2) \neq 1$ since otherwise $1 + 4n^2$ would be a square, which is impossible. So, as the prime divisors of $1^2 + (2n)^2$ are all congruent to 1 modulo 4 , we have $f(1 + 4n^2) \geq 5$. Now, Inequality (96) gives $4n^2 > z''^2$. Hence, Equation (101) gives

$$5(n^2 - 4) \leq f(1 + 4n^2)(n^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 1 < 4n^2 + 1.$$

Thus $n^2 < 21$, but this is impossible as $n \geq 5$. Hence, $y'' = 1$ is not possible. \square

Lemma 18. *If $u = 1$, then $v = 4$.*

Proof. Suppose $u = 1$ and $v > 4$. So $vf(v) \geq 16$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 16$, by Remark 24. From Lemma 17, $y'' \geq 2$. Then Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{16} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{16 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{17}{3},$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . Note that if $f(v) \geq 5$, then $v \geq 20$, $vf(v) \geq 100$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 500$, so Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{100} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{500 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{105}{124} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) = 1$ or 3 . First suppose that $f(v) = 3$. Then $v \geq 12$, $vf(v) \geq 36$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 108$, so Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{108 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{3}{2},$$

so $w' = 1$. As $f(v) = 3$, v has the form $12n^2$, for some n . Then Equation (97) gives $f(1 + 12n^2)(108n^2y''^2 - 16) = 4z''^2 + 12y''^2$, so

$$f(1 + 12n^2)(27n^2y''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 3y''^2.$$

But then modulo 3, since $f(1 + 12n^2) \equiv 1$, we have $-1 \equiv z''^2$, which is impossible. So $f(v) = 1$. In this case, v is an even square; i.e., it has the form $4n^2$, for some n . Then Equation (97) gives $f(1 + 4n^2)w'^2(4n^2y''^2 - 16) = 4z''^2 + 4y''^2$, so

$$f(1 + 4n^2)w'^2(n^2y''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + y''^2, \tag{102}$$

where from above, $w' = 1$ or 2 . First suppose that $w' = 2$. Then modulo 4 we have $0 \equiv z''^2 + y''^2$, so y'' and z'' are both even, say $y'' = 2y'''$ and $z'' = 2z'''$. So we have $f(1 + 4n^2)(4n^2y'''^2 - 4) = z'''^2 + y'''^2$, which modulo 4 gives $0 \equiv z'''^2 + y'''^2$. So y''' and z''' are both even, say $y''' = 2y_4$ and $z''' = 2z_4$. So we have

$$f(1 + 4n^2)(4n^2y_4^2 - 1) = z_4^2 + y_4^2.$$

But now, arguing modulo 4 again, we have $-1 \equiv z_4^2 + y_4^2$, which is impossible. Hence, $w' = 1$. Thus Equation (102) gives

$$f(1 + 4n^2)(n^2y''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + y''^2. \tag{103}$$

Note that we can write $1 + 4n^2 = f(1 + 4n^2)m^2$, for $m := s(1 + 4n^2)$. Notice also from Inequality (96) and Equation (103), $f(1 + 4n^2)(n^2y''^2 - 4) < (4n^2 + 1)y''^2$, so

$$n^2 - \frac{4}{y''^2} < \frac{4n^2 + 1}{f(1 + 4n^2)} = m^2.$$

Thus, as $y'' \geq 2$, we have $n^2 - 1 \leq n^2 - \frac{4}{y''^2} < m^2$, so $n^2 \leq m^2$, and hence $n \leq m$. Then we have

$$f(1 + 4n^2) = \frac{1 + 4n^2}{m^2} \leq \frac{1}{m^2} + 4.$$

If $m = 1$ then $n = 1$ and so $v \not\geq 4$, which is a contradiction. So $f(1 + 4n^2) < 5$. Thus, as $f(1 + 4n^2)$ is odd, $f(1 + 4n^2) = 3$. But this would imply that $1 + 4n^2$ is divisible by 3 and hence $1 + n^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, which is impossible. \square

From Lemma 16, either $u = 1, v = 4$ or $y'' = 1$. We saw in Lemma 17 that $y'' \neq 1$, and in Lemma 18 that if $u = 1$, then $v = 4$. So it remains to consider the situation where $v = 4$. Assume for the moment that $y'' = 2$. From Inequality (94), $vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16$, which gives $f(u) > 1$, so $f(u) \geq 3$. From Inequality (96), $16 > uf(u)z''^2$ which implies $f(u) < 5$. Hence, $f(u) = 3$ and again Inequality (96) gives $z'' = 1$. But then substituting $f(u) = 3, v = 4, y'' = 2, z'' = 1$ in Equation (97) gives

$$f(u + 4)w'^2(4 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 - 16) = 4(3 + 4) \quad \text{and so} \quad 8f(u + 4)w'^2 = 7,$$

which is impossible. Hence, $y'' \geq 3$.

If $f(u) \geq 3$, Inequality (99) would give

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{4 \cdot 27 \cdot 3^3 - 4} \right) = \frac{21}{23} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 1$. Then Inequality (99) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{4 \cdot 9 - 16} \right) = 9,$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . As $f(u) = 1$, u is a square. First suppose $u > 1$. So $u \geq 9$. Since u is a square, $u + 4$ cannot be a square and thus $f(u + 4) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (98) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{4 \cdot 3^3 - 4} \right) = \frac{13}{15} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $u = 1$. Now, Equation (97) gives $5w'^2(4y''^2 - 16) = 4z''^2 + 4y''^2$, so $5w'^2(y''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + y''^2$. If $w' = 2$ we have $19y''^2 = z''^2 + 80$. But modulo 19 this gives $z''^2 \equiv -4$, which is impossible. So $w' = 1$ and we have $4y''^2 = z''^2 + 20$ and so z'' is even, say $z'' = 2z'''$, and then $y''^2 = z'''^2 + 5$. It follows that $z''' = 2$ and $y'' = 3$. This is the required solution: $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2 = 40$ and $\Sigma' = u\Sigma/v = 10$.

Case 2. Assume u is odd, v is even and the 2-adic order of v is odd.

We will show that in this case, $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (24, 12)$ is the only possibility.

As x is an integer, from Equation (92) we can write $\Sigma = 2f(u+v)f(u)w^2$, for some w . Since v divides Σ , it follows that v divides $2w^2$, and as the 2-adic order of v is odd, $f(v)s(v)$ divides $2w$. Thus, setting $2w = f(v)s(v)w'$, then we have $2\Sigma = f(u+v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$ and Equation (91) gives

$$f(u+v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 16(z^2 + vf(u)y'^2). \tag{104}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $16z^2$, so $f(v)s(v)f(u)$ divides $4z$, say $4z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$. So Inequality (90) gives $4vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$ and hence

$$4s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z', \tag{105}$$

and Equation (104) gives

$$f(u+v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = f(v)f(u)z'^2 + 16y'^2. \tag{106}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides $16y'^2$. Since the 2-adic order of v is odd, $f(v)$ divides $2y'$. Let $2y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (105) gives $2f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z'$, and Equation (106) gives $f(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64) = 4f(u)z'^2 + 16f(v)y''^2$. From this last equation, notice that as $v, f(v)$ are even and $f(u)$ is odd, z' must be even, say $z' = 2z''$. So we have $f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z''$ and so

$$vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z''^2, \tag{107}$$

and

$$f(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64) = 16(f(u)z''^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{108}$$

Note that from the left-hand side of Equation (108), we have

$$vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 64. \tag{109}$$

Furthermore, Inequality (107) and Equation (108) give

$$uf(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64) < 16(v+u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{f(u+v)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64} \right) \tag{110}$$

and consequently

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64} \right). \tag{111}$$

Lemma 19. *We have $f(v) = 2$.*

Proof. Assume that $f(v) > 2$. So $f(v) \geq 6, vf(v) \geq 36, vf^2(v) \geq 216$. We first show that $f(u) = 1$. Indeed, if $f(u) > 1$, then $f(u) \geq 3, uf(u) \geq 9$ and for all y'' , Inequality (111) would give

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 6} + \frac{1}{36 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{216 \cdot 3 - 64} \right) = \frac{36}{73} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 1$. Hence, u is a square. Moreover, Equation (108) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)y''^2 - 64) = 16(z''^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{112}$$

Since $f(v)$ is even and square-free, the five smallest possible values of $f(v)$ are 2, 6, 10, 14, 22. If $f(v) > 14$, then $f(v) \geq 22$, so $v \geq 22$ and for all u, y'' , Inequality (111) would give

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{22} + \frac{1}{22^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{22^3 - 64} \right) = \frac{1012}{1323} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) \leq 14$. Now, suppose $f(v) = 14$. Here $v \geq 14$ and Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{14^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{14^3 - 64} \right) = \frac{84}{67} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Furthermore, v is divisible by 7, so as $\gcd(u, v) = 1$ and u is a square, $u + v \equiv 1, 2$ or $4 \pmod{7}$, and thus $f(u + v) \equiv 1, 2$ or $4 \pmod{7}$. Modulo 7, Equation (112) gives $-f(u + v) \equiv 2z''^2$, so $z''^2 \equiv 3, 6, 5$, respectively, but these congruences have no solutions. So $f(v) \neq 14$.

Now, suppose $f(v) = 10$. Here Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{10^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{10^3 - 64} \right) = \frac{220}{117} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Then Equation (112) gives $f(u + v)(100vy''^2 - 64) = 16(z''^2 + 10y''^2)$. We have $v = 10m^2$, for some m . So

$$f(u + 10m^2)(125(my'')^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 10y''^2). \tag{113}$$

As $f(u) = 1$, we have $u = n^2$, for some odd n . First suppose $f(n^2 + 10m^2) = 1$. So $n^2 + 10m^2 = r^2$, for some odd r . Then $1 + 2m^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and hence m must be even, say $m = 2m'$. So Equation (113) gives $250(m'y'')^2 - 4 = z''^2 + 10y''^2$ and hence z'' is even, say $z'' = 2z'''$. So $125(m'y'')^2 - 2 = 2z'''^2 + 5y''^2$. But one readily verifies that modulo 16, this equation has no solution for m', y'', z''' . Thus $f(n^2 + 10m^2) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{10^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{10^3 - 64} \right) = \frac{220}{351} < 1,$$

v	2	8	18	32	50	72	98	128	162	200
$vf(v)$	4	16	36	64	100	144	196	256	324	400
$vf^2(v)$	8	32	72	128	200	288	392	512	648	800

Table 9: The first ten positive integers v with $f(v) = 2$.

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) \neq 10$.

Now, suppose $f(v) = 6$. Here Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{6^3 - 64} \right) = \frac{84}{19} < 5,$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . Furthermore, v is divisible by 3, so as $\gcd(u, v) = 1$ and u is a square, $u + v \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and thus $f(u + v) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Hence, modulo 3, Equation (112) gives $-1 \equiv z''^2$, which is impossible. So $f(v) \neq 6$. \square

Remark 25. By the previous lemma, $f(v) = 2$. So v has the form $v = 2m^2$ for some m . The first ten possible values of v are shown in Table 9. In particular, $v \geq 2, vf(v) \geq 4$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 8$. Furthermore, here are some obvious useful facts:

- (a) If $v > 32$, then $vf(v) \geq 100, vf^2(v) \geq 200$, while $v \leq 32$ only for $v = 2, 8, 18$ and 32 .
- (b) If $v > 98$, then $vf(v) \geq 256, vf^2(v) \geq 512$, while $v \leq 98$ only for $v = 2, 8, 18, 32, 50, 72$ and 98 .
- (c) If $u > 1$, then $u \geq 3$ and $uf(u) \geq 9$. Furthermore, if $u > 3$ and $u \neq 9$, then $uf(u) \geq 25$. And if $u > 5$ and $u \neq 25$, then $uf(u) \geq 49$.

Lemma 20. *Either $u = 1$ or $v = 2$ or $y'' = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $u > 1$ and $y'' \geq 2$. We will show that $v = 2$. Let us assume for the moment that $v > 98$, so $vf(v) \geq 256, vf^2(v) \geq 512$ by Remark 25(b). We also have $uf(u) \geq 9$ by Remark 25(c). Then using $f(u) \geq 1$, Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{256} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{512 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{274}{279} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $v \leq 98$, and thus, as mentioned in the above remark, $v = 2, 8, 18, 32, 50, 72$ or 98 . Our goal is to exclude the last 6 of these 7 possible v -values. We will first consider the cases $u = 3$ and $u = 9$. Note that of our 6 v -values of interest, we need only consider the ones relatively prime to 3; that is, $8, 32, 50, 98$. For these four v -values, if $u = 3$, then $\frac{16}{f(3+v)} \left(\frac{1}{9f(v)} + \frac{1}{3vf(v)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{3vf^2(v)y''^2 - 64} \right)$ takes the respective values $\frac{2}{15}, \frac{2}{69}, \frac{4}{219}, \frac{4}{435}$, and as these values are all

less than 1, we obtain a contradiction from Inequality (110). Similarly, if $u = 9$, then $\frac{16}{f(9+v)}(\frac{1}{9f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)})(1 + \frac{64}{vf^2(v)2^2-64})$ takes the respective values $\frac{2}{9}, \frac{2}{63}, \frac{4}{207}, \frac{4}{423}$, and as these values are also all less than 1, we again obtain a contradiction from Inequality (110). So we may assume that $u > 3$ and $u \neq 9$. Then by Remark 25(c), we have $uf(u) \geq 25$ and for the five v -values $v = 18, 32, 50, 72, 98$, respectively, one finds that $16(\frac{1}{25f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)})(1 + \frac{64}{vf^2(v)2^2-64})$ takes the values $\frac{172}{175}, \frac{114}{175}, \frac{12}{23}, \frac{194}{425}, \frac{492}{1175}$. As these values are all less than 1, we obtain a contradiction from Inequality (111). It remains to treat the case $v = 8$, with $u > 3$ and $u \neq 9$. First note that in this case, $uf(u) \geq 25$ by Remark 25(c), and if $f(u) > 1$, then $f(u) \geq 3$. But then Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{16 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{32 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{98}{125} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So we may assume $f(u) = 1$, i.e., u is a square. But then, as $u > 1$, $u + 8$ is not a square and so $f(u + 8) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{16} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{32 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{22}{25} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $v = 8$ is impossible. Thus $v = 2$. □

Lemma 21. *If $y'' = 1$, then $u = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $y'' = 1$, and arguing by contradiction, suppose $u > 1$. Note that Inequality (107) gives $vf(v) > uf(u)z''^2 \geq uf(u)$. Also, by Inequality (109), $vf^2(v)f(u) > 64$. So if $v = 2$, then $vf^2(v) = 8$ and hence $f(u) > 8$, contradicting the fact that $vf(v) > uf(u)$. Hence, $v > 2$. By Lemma 19, $f(v) = 2$. So, as $v > 2$, we have $v = 2m^2$ for some $m \geq 2$. Notice also that if $m = 2$, then $vf^2(v) = 32$, and so $vf^2(v)f(u) > 64$ gives $f(u) > 1$.

If $m \geq 11$, then as $uf(u) \geq 9$ by Remark 25(c), Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4m^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8m^2 - 64} \right) = \frac{1004}{1017} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So we need only consider $2 \leq m \leq 10$. First consider $u = 3$ and $u = 9$. The numbers $v = 2m^2$ with $2 \leq m \leq 10$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$ are given by $m = 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10$. For $u = 3$ and $m = 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10$, the values of $\frac{16}{f(3+2m^2)}(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4m^2})(1 + \frac{64}{8m^2 \cdot 3 - 64})$ are respectively

$$\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{30}, \frac{4}{201}, \frac{4}{417}, \frac{1}{138}, \frac{1}{219}.$$

As these values are all less than 1, we obtain a contradiction from Inequality (110). Now, let $u = 9$. Here $f(u) = 1$ and so, as we observed at the beginning of this

proof, $m > 2$. For $m = 4, 5, 7, 8, 10$, the values of $\frac{16}{f(9+2m^2)}(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4m^2})(1 + \frac{64}{8m^2-64})$ are, respectively,

$$\frac{1}{18}, \frac{4}{153}, \frac{4}{369}, \frac{1}{126}, \frac{1}{207}.$$

As these values are all less than 1, we again obtain a contradiction from Inequality (110).

From what we have just shown, we may suppose that $u \geq 5$ and $u \neq 9$, so $uf(u) \geq 25$, by Remark 25(c). If $m \geq 5$, then Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 25 - 64} \right) = \frac{12}{17} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. It remains to treat the cases $m = 2, 3, 4$ for $u \geq 5$ and $u \neq 9$.

If $u = 5$, then for $m = 2, 3, 4$, the values of $\frac{16}{f(5+2m^2)}(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{5 \cdot 4m^2})(1 + \frac{64}{8m^2 \cdot 5 - 64})$ are respectively $\frac{1}{15}, \frac{4}{185}, \frac{1}{90}$, which is impossible by Inequality (110). Similarly, if $u = 25$, then for $m = 3, 4$, the values of $\frac{16}{f(25+2m^2)}(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4m^2})(1 + \frac{64}{8m^2-64})$ are respectively $\frac{4}{25}, \frac{1}{50}$, which is again impossible by Inequality (110). For $m = 2$ we do not need to consider $u = 25$ as $f(25) = 1$ and as we observed at the beginning of this proof, $f(u) > 1$ for $m = 2$. Thus for $m = 2, 3, 4$, we may assume that $u > 5$ and $u \neq 25$.

For $m = 4$ with $u > 5$ and $u \neq 25$, we have $uf(u) \geq 49$ by Remark 25(c), so Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{64} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{64 \cdot 2 - 64} \right) = \frac{81}{98} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

It therefore remains to treat the cases $m = 2, 3$ for $u \geq 7$ and $u \neq 25$. First let $m = 2$. Then as we saw at the beginning of the proof, $f(u) \geq 3$. If $f(u) \geq 5$, then as $uf(u) \geq 49$, Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{16 \cdot 5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{32 \cdot 5 - 64} \right) = \frac{89}{147} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. If $f(u) = 3$, then u is divisible by 3, so $u + v = u + 8 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, and hence $u + v$ is not a square, and neither is it divisible by 3. So $f(u+v) \neq 1$, and consequently $f(u+v) \geq 5$. Thus, using $uf(u) \geq 49$ and $f(u) = 3$, Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{16 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{32 \cdot 3 - 64} \right) = \frac{73}{245} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So the case $m = 2$ is also impossible.

Finally, let $m = 3$. If $f(u) \geq 3$, then as $uf(u) \geq 49$, Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{36 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{72 \cdot 3 - 64} \right) = \frac{412}{931} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. If $f(u) = 1$, then u is a square, so $u + v = u + 18$ is not a square. Thus $f(u + v) \neq 1$. Furthermore, u is not divisible by 3 since $v = 18$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$. So $u + 18$ is not divisible by 3. Hence, $f(u + v) \geq 5$. Furthermore, as $uf(u) \geq 49$ and $f(u) = 1$, we have $u \geq 49$. Thus Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{u \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{72 - 64} \right) = \frac{4(u + 18)}{5u}.$$

As $w' \geq 1$, we obtain $u < 72$, and so as u is an odd square with $u \geq 49$, we have $u = 49$. But then $f(u + v) = 57$ and Inequality (110) gives a contradiction, as

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{67} \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{72 - 64} \right) = \frac{4}{49} < 1.$$

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 22. *We have $y'' \neq 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $y'' = 1$, so by the above lemma, $u = 1$. In this case, Equation (108) gives

$$f(1 + v)w'^2(vf^2(v) - 64) = 16(z''^2 + f(v)). \tag{114}$$

From Lemma 19, $f(v) = 2$, so v has the form $v = 2m^2$ for some m . Then Equation (114) gives $f(1 + v)w'^2(8m^2 - 64) = 16z''^2 + 32$, so

$$f(1 + 2m^2)w'^2(m^2 - 8) = 2z''^2 + 4. \tag{115}$$

Notice that the 2-adic order is exactly 2, since on the right hand side it is 1 or 2 and on the left hand side at least 2. So z'' is even, say $z'' = 2z'''$. Suppose that m is even and write $m = 2m'$. After replacing and dividing by 4 one gets $f(1 + 8m'^2)w'^2(m'^2 - 2) = 2z'''^2 + 1$, so w' and m' are both odd. Observed modulo 8 this gives a contradiction, since the LHS is -1 and the RHS is 1 or 3 modulo 8. Hence, m must be odd and thus, from Equation (115), w' is necessarily even, say $w' = 2w''$, giving

$$f(1 + 2m^2)w''^2(m^2 - 8) = 2z'''^2 + 1. \tag{116}$$

From Inequality (107), we have $m > z'''$. Thus, Equation (116) gives

$$w''^2 < \frac{2m^2 + 1}{f(1 + 2m^2)(m^2 - 8)}. \tag{117}$$

Notice that from Equation (116), we have $m^2 > 8$, so $m \geq 3$ and is odd. If $m = 3$, then Inequality (117) gives $w''^2 < \frac{19}{19} = 1$, a contradiction. If $f(1 + 2m^2) = 3$, then

$\frac{2m^2+1}{3(m^2-8)} \leq 1$ for $m \geq 5$, which is another contradiction. Finally, if $f(1+2m^2) = 1$ then $w''^2 < \frac{2m^2+1}{m^2-8} \leq 3$ for $m \geq 5$ and so $w'' = 1$. Replacing each of $f(1+2m^2)$ and w'' by the value 1 in Equation (116) gives $m^2 = 2z''^2 + 9$, which modulo 3 implies either $1 \equiv 0$ or $1 \equiv 2$. \square

Lemma 23. *If $v = 2$, then $u = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose that $v = 2$ and $u > 1$. So by Remark 25(c), $uf(u) \geq 9$. From the previous lemma, $y'' \geq 2$. Assume for the moment that $y'' = 2$. By Inequality (109), $v f^2(v) f(u) y''^2 > 64$, which gives $f(u) > 2$, so $f(u) \geq 3$. Now, from Inequality (107), we have $uf(u) z''^2 < v f(v) y''^2 = 16$. So $uf(u) \geq 9$ gives $z' = 1$, and then $uf(u) < 16$ and $f(u) \geq 3$ give $u = 3$. Then $f(u+v) = 5$ and so Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{4}{3} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. But then, by Equation (108), $5(8 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 - 64) = 16(3z''^2 + 8)$, which has no integer solution for z'' . So $y'' \geq 3$.

Note that if $f(u) \geq 7$, then $u \geq 7$ and by Inequality (111)

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 7} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 7 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = \frac{324}{385} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So it suffices to deal with the three cases $f(u) = 1, 3, 5$. First suppose $f(u) = 5$. So $uf(u) \geq 25$. As $f(u) = 5$ and $v = 2$, we have $u+v \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$ and hence $u+v$ is not a square. So $f(u+v) \geq 3$. Hence, by Inequality (110)

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 5 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = \frac{84}{185} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) \neq 5$. Now, suppose $f(u) = 3$. So $uf(u) \geq 9$. We have $u+v \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and hence $u+v$ is not a square. So $f(u+v) \geq 3$. But $f(u+v) \neq 3$, because $u+v \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. So $f(u+v) \geq 5$. Hence, by Inequality (110),

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 3 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = \frac{12}{19} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) \neq 3$. Finally, suppose $f(u) = 1$. Then Equation (108) gives

$$f(u+v)w'^2(y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2). \tag{118}$$

As $f(u) = 1$, so u is an odd square, say $u = n^2$. Thus, as $u > 1$ by hypothesis, $u \geq 9$. As u is a square, $u+2$ is not a square, so $f(u+v) \geq 3$. By Inequality (110),

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = \frac{44}{3} < 15.$$

So $w' = 1, 2$ or 3 . Suppose for the moment that $y'' = 3$. Then as $f(u + v)$ is odd, w' must be even, by Equation (118), so $w' = 2$. Then Equation (118) gives $2f(u + v) = z''^2 + 18$. It follows that z'' must be even and hence $f(u + v) \geq 11$. But then Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{11} \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = 4,$$

contradicting $w' = 2$. Hence, $y'' \geq 4$.

Note that for $y'' \geq 4$, if $f(u + v) \geq 11$, then Inequality (110) would give

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{11} \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 16 - 64} \right) = \frac{8}{9} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So, as $f(u + v)$ is square-free, $f(u + v) = 3, 5$ or 7 . But then $u + v$ would be divisible by $3, 5, 7$, respectively. Since there is no n for which $n^2 + 2 \equiv 0$ modulo 5 or 7 , we conclude that $f(u + v) = 3$. Thus $n^2 + 2 = u + v$ is divisible by 3 and hence $n^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Thus, for $u > 1$ we have $n > 3$ and thus $u \geq 25$. Then Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 16 - 64} \right) = \frac{72}{25} < 3.$$

So $w' = 1$. But then Equation (118) would give $3(y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$, so $0 = 24 + 2z''^2 + y''^2$, which is obviously impossible. Hence, $u = 1$. \square

Lemma 24. *If $u = 1$, then $v = 2$.*

Proof. Suppose that $u = 1$ and $v > 2$. So by Remark 25, $v \geq 8, vf(v) \geq 16$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 32$. By Lemma 22, $y'' \geq 2$. Then Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{16} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{32 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = 18,$$

so $w' = 1, 2, 3$ or 4 . Lemma 19 and Equation (108) give

$$f(1 + v)w'^2(vy''^2 - 16) = 4(z''^2 + 2y''^2), \tag{119}$$

while, setting $v = 2m^2$, Inequality (107) gives

$$(2m)^2 y''^2 > z''^2. \tag{120}$$

Let us first dispense with the case $v = 8$. Suppose $v = 8$. Then $f(1 + v) = 1$ and substituting in Equation (119), the four possibilities for w' give:

- $w' = 1$: $2(y''^2 - 2) = z''^2 + 2y''^2$, so $-4 = z''^2$, which is obviously impossible.

- $w' = 2$: $8(y''^2 - 2) = z''^2 + 2y''^2$, so $6y''^2 - 16 = z''^2$, which is impossible modulo 3.
- $w' = 3$: $18(y''^2 - 2) = z''^2 + 2y''^2$, so $(4y)''^2 = z''^2 + 6^2$, which is impossible as there is no such Pythagorean triple.
- $w' = 4$: $32(y''^2 - 2) = z''^2 + 2y''^2$, so $30y''^2 - 64 = z''^2$, which is impossible modulo 3.

So $v > 8$ and hence $v \geq 18, vf(v) \geq 36$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 72$. Then Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{72 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{76}{7} < 11,$$

so $w' = 1, 2$ or 3 . Substituting $w' = 3$ in Equation (119) for $v = 18$ and 32 gives respectively

$$19 \cdot 9(9y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2) \text{ and } 33 \cdot 9(8y''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 2y''^2.$$

However, neither of these equations has a solution modulo 64. So $w' = 1$ or 2 for $v = 18$ and 32 . For $v > 32$ we have $v \geq 50$ and Inequality (111) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{100} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{200 \cdot 4 - 64} \right) = \frac{204}{23} < 9,$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . Thus we have $w' = 1$ or 2 for all $v \geq 18$.

First suppose $w' = 2$. Note that if $f(1 + 2m^2) \geq 3$, then Inequality (120) and Equation (119) give

$$12(m^2y''^2 - 8) \leq 4f(1 + 2m^2)(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2) < (8m^2 + 4)y''^2,$$

so $(m^2 - 1)y''^2 < 24$. But for $v \geq 18$, we have $m \geq 3$. So $(m^2 - 1)y''^2 < 24$ gives $y''^2 < 3$, hence $y'' = 1$, contrary to Lemma 22. We conclude that $f(1 + 2m^2) = 1$. Thus Equation (119) gives $4(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$, so

$$2(m^2 - 1)y''^2 = z''^2 + 16.$$

Since $f(1 + 2m^2) = 1$, we have that $1 + 2m^2$ is a square, say $1 + 2m^2 = n^2$. But investigations show that the simultaneous equations $2(m^2 - 1)y''^2 = z''^2 + 16$ and $1 + 2m^2 = n^2$ have no integer solution modulo 128. Hence, $w' = 2$ is impossible.

Finally, suppose $w' = 1$. Note that if $f(1 + 2m^2) \geq 11$, then Inequality (120) and Equation (119) give:

$$11(m^2y''^2 - 8) \leq f(1 + 2m^2)(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2) < (8m^2 + 4)y''^2,$$

so $(3m^2 - 4)y''^2 < 88$. But for $v \geq 18$, we have $m \geq 3$ and so $(3m^2 - 4)y''^2 < 88$ gives $y''^2 < 88/23 < 4$, hence $y'' = 1$, contrary to Lemma 22. So $f(1+2m^2) = 1, 3, 5$ or 7.

For $f(1 + 2m^2) = 7$, Equation (119) gives $7(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$, which has no solution modulo 49. So $f(1 + 2m^2) \neq 7$.

For $f(1 + 2m^2) = 5$, Equation (119) gives $5(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$, which has no solution modulo 25. So $f(1 + 2m^2) \neq 5$.

For $f(1 + 2m^2) = 1$ and 3, the calculation is slightly more complicated. For $f(1 + 2m^2) = 1$ we consider the pair of the simultaneous equations $m^2y''^2 - 8 = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$ and $1 + 2m^2 = n^2$, while for $f(1 + 2m^2) = 3$ we consider the pair of the simultaneous equations $3(m^2y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2)$ and $1 + 2m^2 = 3n^2$. In both cases one finds that the pair of equations has no solution modulo 64. Thus $w' = 1$ is also impossible. \square

Given the above lemmas, it remains to treat the case where $u = 1, v = 2$ and $y'' \geq 2$. By Inequality (109), $vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 64 > 0$, so $y''^2 > 8$. Thus $y'' \geq 3$. Then Inequality (110) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{64}{8 \cdot 9 - 64} \right) = 36,$$

so $w' \leq 5$. Equation (108) gives

$$3w'^2(y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2), \tag{121}$$

One finds that for $w' = 1, 3$ and 5, Equation (121) has no solution modulo 64. So $w' = 2$ or 4.

For $w' = 4$, Inequality (107) and Equation (121) give $48(y''^2 - 8) = 2(z''^2 + 2y''^2) < 12y''^2$, so $3y''^2 < 32$. Thus, as $y'' \geq 3$, we have $y'' = 3$, and Equation (121) gives $z''^2 = 6$, which is obviously impossible. So $w' = 2$.

Finally, for $w' = 2$, Equation (121) has a unique positive integer solution: $y'' = z'' = 4$. From the definitions, for $u = 1, v = 2$, we have $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)vf(v)w'^2/4 = 6w'^2 = 24$. Consequently, $\Sigma' = u\Sigma/v = 12$. This is the required case 2 solution.

Case 3. Assume u is even, v is odd, and the 2-adic order of u is even.

We will show that in this case, $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (10, 40)$ and $(18, 32)$ are the only two possibilities.

As x is an integer, from Equation (92) we can write $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)w^2$. Note v divides Σ , so v divides w^2 , and hence $f(v)s(v)$ divides w . Thus, setting $w = f(v)s(v)w'$ we may write $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$. Then Equation (91) gives

$$f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y''^2 - 16) = 4(z^2 + vf(u)y''^2). \tag{122}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $16z^2$, so $f(v)s(v)f(u)$ divides z , say $z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$. So Inequality (90) gives $vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$ and hence

$$s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z', \tag{123}$$

and Equation (122) gives

$$f(u+v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 4(f(v)f(u)z'^2 + y'^2). \tag{124}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides y' . Let $y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (123) gives $f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z'$ and so

$$vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2, \tag{125}$$

and Equation (124) gives

$$f(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = 4(f(u)z'^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{126}$$

Remark 26. Note that $v, f(v), f(u)$ and $f(u+v)$ are all odd. It follows from Equation (126) that $w'y''$ is even.

Note that from the left-hand side of Equation (126), we have

$$vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16. \tag{127}$$

Furthermore, Inequality (125) and Equation (126) give

$$uf(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) < 4(v+u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{f(u+v)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right) \tag{128}$$

and consequently

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{129}$$

Remark 27. Note that as u is even and the 2-adic order of u is even, we have $u \geq 4$. The first twelve possible values of u are the same as the v values shown in Table 8.

Lemma 25. *The following conditions hold.*

- (a) *If $f(u) > 1$, then $v = 1$ and $y'' \geq 7$.*
- (b) *$f(u) \leq 3$.*
- (c) *If $y'' \geq 2$, then $f(v) = 1$.*

Proof. (a). Suppose $f(u) > 1$, so $f(u) \geq 3$, $u \geq 12$ and $uf(u) \geq 36$. Suppose also that $v \geq 3$, so $vf(v) \geq 9$. Then for $y'' \geq 1$, Inequality (129) would give

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 3 - 16} \right) = \frac{7}{11} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $v = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 36$, so $y'' \geq 7$.

(b). If $f(u) > 3$, then $f(u) \geq 5$, $u \geq 20$ and $uf(u) \geq 100$. Then for $y'' \geq 7$, Inequality (129) would give

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{20} + \frac{1}{5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5 \cdot 7^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{1029}{1145} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(c). Suppose $y'' \geq 2$ and $f(v) \geq 3$, so $vf(v) \geq 9$. For all $u \geq 4$, Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{27 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{21}{23} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 26. *We have $f(u) = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $f(u) > 1$. By Lemma 25, $y'' \geq 7$, $v = 1$ and $f(u) = 3$, and so $u \geq 12$. Now, Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{3 \cdot 12} + \frac{1}{3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3 \cdot 7^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{637}{393} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Hence, Equation (126) gives

$$f(u + v)(3y''^2 - 16) = 4(3z'^2 + y''^2).$$

Modulo 3 we have $y''^2 \equiv -f(u + v)$. In particular, $f(u + v) = 1$ is impossible. So as $u + v$ is odd and $\gcd(u, u + v) = 1$, we have $f(u + v) \geq 5$. Then Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{5} \left(\frac{1}{3 \cdot 12} + \frac{1}{3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3 \cdot 7^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{637}{1965} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 27. *The following conditions hold.*

- (a) *Either $u = 4$ or $u = 16$.*
- (b) *If $u = 4$, then $v = 1$.*

(c) If $u = 16$, then $v = 9$.

Proof. (a). By Lemma 26, u is an even square, say $u = 4n^2$. Suppose $n \geq 3$, so $u \geq 36$. First suppose that $y'' = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $vf(v) > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 36$. Then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{36} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{36 - 16} \right) = \frac{2}{5} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $y'' \geq 2$ and so by Lemma 25(c), $f(v) = 1$. Suppose for the moment that $v = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 36$. So $y'' \geq 7$. Moreover, $u + v = 4n^2 + 1$ is not a square, and is not divisible by 3. So $f(u + v) \geq 5$. Then Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{5} \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{1813}{1485} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Then Inequality (128) gives

$$f(u + v) < 4 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{1813}{297} < 7,$$

so, as $f(u + v)$ is odd and $f(u + v) \geq 5$, we have $f(u + v) = 5$. Then Equation (126) gives $y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 80$. But we saw above that Inequality (125) gives $y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 36z'^2$. So we have $4z'^2 + 80 \geq 36z'^2$ and hence $2z'^2 < 5$. Thus $z'^2 = 1$. But then $y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 80$ has no integer solution for y'' . Consequently, $v = 1$ is not possible.

As $f(v) = 1$, we now have $v \geq 9$. But then as $y'' \geq 2$, Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = 1,$$

which is a contradiction. We conclude that $u = 4n^2$ with $n \leq 2$.

(b). Let $u = 4$ and assume $v > 1$. First suppose that $y'' = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $vf(v) > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 4$. Hence, $vf(v) \geq 9$. Also, Inequality (127) gives $vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16$, so $vf^2(v) > 16$. So $v \neq 9$, and consequently either $f(v) \geq 3$ or v is an odd square with $v \geq 25$. In either case, $vf^2(v) \geq 25$.

First suppose that v is an odd square with $v \geq 25$. Then $u + v = 4 + v$ is not a square, so $f(u + v) > 1$. Moreover, as v is a square $4 + v \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, so $f(u + v) \neq 3$. Hence, $f(u + v) \geq 5$. Then Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{5} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{29}{45} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

Now, suppose $f(v) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{21}{11} < 2.$$

So $w' = 1$. But as $y'' = 1$, this contradicts Remark 26. We conclude that $y'' = 1$ is not possible.

We now consider $y'' \geq 2$. By Lemma 25(c), $f(v) = 1$. Suppose $v > 1$. Since $f(v) = 1$, v is an odd square. So $4 + v$ is not a square, and hence $f(u + v) \geq 3$. Then as $v \geq 9$, Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{13}{15} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $v = 1$, as required.

(c). Let $u = 16$ and assume $v \neq 9$. First suppose that $y'' = 1$ and that $f(v) = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $vf(v) > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 16$. As $f(v) = 1$, it follows that v is an odd square, and hence $v \geq 25$. Then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{41}{36} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. But as $y'' = 1$, this contradicts Remark 26.

Now, suppose that $y'' = 1$ and that $f(v) > 1$. So $f(v) \geq 3$. If $v = 3$, then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{16 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{27 - 16} \right) = \frac{57}{44} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Once again, this contradicts Remark 26.

If $v > 3$ then we have $v \geq 5$ and so for $f(v) \geq 3$, Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{15} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{45 - 16} \right) = \frac{93}{116} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. We conclude that $y'' = 1$ is not possible.

We now consider $y'' \geq 2$. By Lemma 25(c), $f(v) = 1$. So v is an odd square. Note that if $v \geq 25$, then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{41}{84} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So it remains to eliminate the possibility that $v = 1$.

Let $v = 1$. Then Inequality (125) gives $y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 16$, so $y'' \geq 5$. Also $f(u + v) = 17$. Then Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{17} \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{25}{36} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $v = 9$, as required. □

By the previous lemma, we have $u = 4, v = 1$ or $u = 16, v = 9$. Consider the first case. Here Inequality (127) gives $y''^2 > 16$, so $y'' \geq 5$. Then as $f(u + v) = 5$, Inequality (128) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{5} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{25}{9} < 3,$$

so $w' = 1$. Equation (126) gives $5(y''^2 - 16) = 4(z'^2 + y''^2)$, so $y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 80$, which has the solution $y'' = 12, z' = 4$. From the definitions, $w = f(v)s(v)w' = w'$. Then $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)w^2 = 10$, and $\Sigma' = \frac{u}{v}\Sigma = 4\Sigma = 40$, which is one of the desired solutions.

Now, consider the second case, $u = 16, v = 9$. Here Inequality (127) gives $9y''^2 > 16$, so $y'' \geq 2$. Then Inequality (129) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{5}{4} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Equation (126) gives $(9y''^2 - 16) = 4(z'^2 + y''^2)$, so $5y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 16$. This has infinitely many solutions. From the definitions, $w = f(v)s(v)w' = 3w' = 3$. Then $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)w^2 = 18$, and $\Sigma' = \frac{u}{v}\Sigma = 16\Sigma/9 = 32$, which is the other desired Case 3 solution.

Case 4. Assume u is even, v is odd, and the 2-adic order of u is odd.

We will show that in this case, $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (12, 24)$ is the only possibility.

As x is an integer, from Equation (92) we can write $2\Sigma = f(u + v)f(u)w^2$. Note v divides Σ , so v divides w^2 , and hence $f(v)s(v)$ divides w . Thus, setting $w = f(v)s(v)w'$ we may write $2\Sigma = f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$. Then Equation (91) gives

$$f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 16(z'^2 + vf(u)y'^2). \tag{130}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $16z'^2$, so $f(v)s(v)\frac{f(u)}{2}$ divides z' , say $2z' = f(v)s(v)f(u)z''$. So Inequality (90) gives $2vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z''$ and hence

$$2s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z'', \tag{131}$$

and Equation (130) gives

$$f(u + v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 4(f(v)f(u)z''^2 + 4y'^2). \tag{132}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides y' . Let $y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (131) gives $2f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z''$ and so

$$4vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z''^2, \tag{133}$$

and Equation (132) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = 4(f(u)z''^2 + 4f(v)y''^2). \tag{134}$$

Note that from the left-hand side of Equation (134), we have

$$vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16. \tag{135}$$

Furthermore, Inequality (133) and Equation (134) give

$$uf(u+v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) < 16(v+u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{f(v+u)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right) \tag{136}$$

and consequently

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{137}$$

Lemma 28. *The following conditions hold.*

- (a) $f(v) \leq 5$.
- (b) If $f(v) > 1$, then $f(u) = 2$.
- (c) If $f(v) = 3$, then either $v = 3$ or $u = 2$.

Proof. (a). Suppose that $f(v) \geq 7$. So $vf(v) \geq 7^2$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 7^3$. Also, as the 2-adic order of u is odd, we have $f(u) \geq 2$, so $u \geq 2$ and $uf(u) \geq 4$. Then for all $y'' \geq 1$, Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{4 \cdot 7} + \frac{1}{7^2 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7^3 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{252}{335} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(b). Suppose that $f(v) \geq 3$ and $f(u) > 2$. Then $f(u) \geq 6$, and so $uf(u) \geq 36$. And $vf(v) \geq 9$ and $vf^2(v) \geq 27$. Then for all $y'' \geq 1$, Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{36 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{9 \cdot 6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{27 \cdot 6 - 16} \right) = \frac{36}{73} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(c). Suppose that $f(v) = 3$ and that $v > 3$ and $u > 2$. As $f(v) = 3$, v has the form $v = 3m^2$, for some odd m . By Part (b), $f(u) = 2$, so u has the form $u = 2n^2$, for some integer n . So $v \geq 27$ and $u \geq 8$. Then Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{16 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{3^4 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^5 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{21}{47} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 29. *We have $f(v) = 1$.*

Proof. By Lemma 28(a), $f(v) \leq 5$. First suppose $f(v) = 5$. By Lemma 28(b), $f(u) = 2$. If $u > 2$, then $u \geq 8$ and $uf(u) \geq 16$. Then Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{16 \cdot 5} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5^3 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{5}{9} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $u = 2$. But v has the form $v = 5m^2$, for some odd m , so $u + v = 2 + 5m^2$, and this cannot be a square as $2 + 5m^2 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Hence, $f(u + v) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (136) gives

$$w^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4 \cdot 5} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5^3 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{140}{351} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) \neq 5$.

Now, suppose $f(v) = 3$, so v has the form $v = 3m^2$, for some odd m . By Lemma 28(b), $f(u) = 2$, so u has the form $u = 2n^2$, for some integer n . By Lemma 28(c), either $v = 3$ or $u = 2$. We claim that in both cases, $u + v$ is not a square. Indeed, if $v = 3$, then $u + v = 2n^2 + 3$ is not a square since modulo 8, $2n^2 + 3$ is either 3 or 5, according to whether n is even or odd, but the quadratic residues modulo 8 are 0, 1 and 4. Similarly, if $u = 2$, then $u + v = 2 + 3m^2$ is not a square as $2 + 3m^2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. Thus, in both cases, $f(u + v) > 1$ and so, as $\gcd(u + v, v) = 1$, we have $f(u + v) \geq 5$. Then Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{4 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{12}{19} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 30. *If $y'' > 1$, then $v = 1$.*

Proof. By the previous lemma, $f(v) = 1$, so v is an odd square, say $v = m^2$. Suppose $y'' \geq 2$ and that $v \geq 9$. First suppose that $f(u) > 2$. Then $f(u) \geq 6$ and Inequality (137) give

$$w^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{9 \cdot 6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 6 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{4}{5} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 2$. Hence, u has the form $u = 2n^2$, for some integer n .

Now, suppose for the moment that $v \geq 25$ and that $u \geq 18$. Then $uf(u) \geq 36$ and Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{172}{207} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So either $v = 9$ or $u < 18$. First consider the case where $u < 18$ and $v \geq 25$. There are two possibilities: either $u = 2$ or $u = 8$. If $u = 8$, then $u + v = 8 + m^2$ cannot be a square for $m > 1$. So $f(u + v) \geq 3$. Then $uf(u) = 16$, and Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{11}{23} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. If $u = 2$, then $uf(u) = 4$, and $u + v = 2 + m^2$ cannot be a square. So $f(u + v) \geq 3$. Then Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{36}{23} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. But then Inequality (137) gives

$$f(u + v) < 16 \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{108}{23} < 5.$$

So $f(u + v) = 3$. Then Equation (134) gives $3(2vy''^2 - 16) = 4(2z'^2 + 4y''^2)$, so

$$(3v - 8)y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 24.$$

So as v is odd, y'' must be even, say $y'' = 2y'''$, so $(3v - 8)y'''^2 = z'^2 + 6$. But it is easy to see that as v is an odd square, this equation has no solution modulo 8.

We conclude from the above that $v = 9$. In this case, for $u \geq 2$, Inequality (137) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{44}{7} < 7.$$

Notice that $f(u + v) \neq 3$ since $\gcd(u + v, v) = 1$. So we have three possibilities:

- (a) $f(u + v) = 1$ and $w' = 1$,
- (b) $f(u + v) = 1$ and $w' = 2$,
- (c) $f(u + v) = 5$ and $w' = 1$.

In these cases, Equation (134) gives respectively

$$y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 8, \tag{138}$$

$$7y''^2 = z'^2 + 8, \tag{139}$$

$$37y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 40. \tag{140}$$

However, one finds that Equation (138) has no solution modulo 16, Equation (139) has no solution modulo 32, and Equation (140) has no solution modulo 25. This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 31. *If $y'' = 1$, then $v = 1$.*

Proof. By Lemma 29, $f(v) = 1$, so v is an odd square, say $v = m^2$. Suppose $y'' = 1$ and that $v \geq 9$. First note that if $f(u) > 2$, then $f(u) \geq 6$, and so $uf(u) \geq 36$. Then by Inequality (133), $4v > uf(u)z'^2 \geq uf(u) \geq 36$, so $v > 9$. Thus $v \geq 25$ and then Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 6 - 16} \right) = \frac{124}{201} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 2$. Then Equation (134) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(m^2 - 8) = 4(z'^2 + 2). \tag{141}$$

In particular, as m and $f(u + v)$ are odd, w' must be even. For all $u \geq 2$, Inequality (137) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{9 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = 44.$$

So, as w' is even and $f(u + v)$ is odd and square-free, we have three possibilities:

- (a) $w' = 6$ and $f(u + v) = 1$; here Equation (141) gives $9m^2 = z'^2 + 74$.
- (b) $w' = 4$ and $f(u + v) = 1$; here Equation (141) gives $4(m^2 - 8) = z'^2 + 2$.
- (c) $w' = 2$ and $f(u + v) = 1, 3, 5, 7$; Equation (141) gives $f(u + v)(m^2 - 8) = z'^2 + 2$.

However, in the first two cases, the equation has no solution modulo 4. In the third case we find that for $f(u + v) = 1$ and 5, the equation $f(u + v)(m^2 - 8) = z'^2 + 2$ also has no solution modulo 4, while for $f(u + v) = 7$, the equation $f(u + v)(m^2 - 8) = z'^2 + 2$ has no solution modulo 8. So it remains to treat the case where $f(u + v) = 3$ and $w' = 2$. So it remains to treat the case where $f(u + v) = 3$ and $w' = 2$. Here the equation is $3m^2 = z'^2 + 26$, which actually does have integer solutions. However, notice that for $f(u + v) = 3$, we have $v \neq 9$, since $\gcd(u + v, v) = 1$, so $v \geq 25$. Hence, for $u \geq 2$, Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{25 \cdot 2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 2 - 16} \right) = \frac{36}{17} < 3.$$

But this contradicts the assumption that $w' = 2$. □

By the two preceding lemmas, $v = 1$.

Lemma 32. *We have $y'' > 1$.*

Proof. If $y'' = 1$, then by Inequality (133), we have $uf(u)z'^2 < 4$. But this is impossible as $uf(u) \geq 4$. □

Lemma 33. *If $f(u + 1) > 1$, then $f(u) = 2$.*

Proof. By the previous lemma, we have $y'' \geq 2$. Suppose $f(u + 1) > 1$. Note that if $f(u) \geq 10$, then $f(u + 1) \geq 3$ and Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{10^2} + \frac{1}{10} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{10 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{44}{45} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Furthermore, if $f(u) = 6$ and $y'' \geq 3$, then as $\gcd(u, u + 1) = 1$, we have $f(u + 1) \neq 3$, so $f(u + 1) \geq 5$, and hence Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{6^2} + \frac{1}{6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{6 \cdot 9 - 16} \right) = \frac{84}{95} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Finally, suppose that $f(u) = 6$ and $y'' = 2$. Then $f(u + 1) \geq 5$ and Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{5} \left(\frac{1}{6^2} + \frac{1}{6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{6 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{28}{15} < 2.$$

So $w' = 1$. Then applying Inequality (136) again gives

$$f(u + 1) < 16 \left(\frac{1}{6^2} + \frac{1}{6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{6 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{28}{3} < 10.$$

Thus, as $f(u + 1)$ is odd and square-free and $f(u + 1) \geq 5$, we have $f(u + 1) = 5$ or 7 . Hence, from Equation (134) we have $f(u + 1) = 3z'^2 + 8$, which is impossible for $f(u + 1) = 5$ and 7 . □

Lemma 34. *If $f(u + 1) = 1$, then $f(u) = 2$.*

Proof. Suppose $f(u + 1) = 1$, so $u + 1 = r^2$ for some odd r . So $u \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$. Suppose that $f(u) > 2$. Then $f(u) \geq 6$ and as u is divisible by 8 , $u \geq 24$. So, as $y'' \geq 2$ by Lemma 32, Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{24 \cdot 6} + \frac{1}{6} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{6 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{25}{3} < 9.$$

So $w' = 1$ or 2 . First suppose $w' = 1$. Then Equation (134) gives $(f(u) - 16)y''^2 = 4f(u)z'^2 + 16$. In particular, $f(u) > 16$. Thus, as $f(u)$ is even and square-free, $f(u) \geq 22$. So, as u is divisible by 8 , $u \geq 88$. But then Inequality (137) gives

$$w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{88 \cdot 22} + \frac{1}{22} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{22 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{89}{99} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $w' = 2$. Then Equation (134) gives

$$(f(u) - 4)y''^2 = f(u)z'^2 + 16. \tag{142}$$

By Inequality (133), we have $4y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 24f(u)z'^2$. So Equation (142) gives $(f(u) - 4)y''^2 < \frac{1}{6}y''^2 + 16$ and hence $(6f(u) - 25)y''^2 < 96$. But $f(u) \geq 6$ and $y'' \geq 2$, so in fact, as $f(u)$ is even and square-free, the only possibility is $f(u) = 6$ and $y'' = 2$. Then Equation (142) gives $8 = 6z'^2 + 16$, which is impossible. \square

Lemma 35. *We have $u = 2$.*

Proof. From the two preceding lemmas, we have $v = 1$ and $f(u) = 2$. So u has the form $u = 2n^2$ for some n . Suppose $n > 1$, so $uf(u) \geq 16$. Equation (134) gives

$$f(u + 1)w'^2(y''^2 - 8) = 4(z'^2 + 2y''^2). \tag{143}$$

In particular, $y''^2 > 8$, so $y'' \geq 3$. By Inequality (133), we have $4y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2 \geq 16z'^2$, so $y'' > 2z'$. So when $y'' = 3$ or 4 , we obtain $z' = 1$. Then when $y'' = 4$, Equation (143) gives $2f(u + 1)w'^2 = 33$, which is impossible modulo 2. When $y'' = 3$, Equation (143) gives $f(u + 1)w'^2 = 4 \cdot 19$, which implies necessarily $w' = 2$ and $f(u + 1) = 19$. Moreover the smallest value of u with $f(u) = 2$ and $f(u + 1) = 19$ is $u = 18$. But then $uf(u) \geq 36$ and with $y'' = 3$, Inequality (136) gives

$$f(u + 1)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{2 \cdot 9 - 16} \right) = 76,$$

which gives a contradiction. So we have $y'' \geq 5$. Then for $u \geq 8$, Inequality (136) gives

$$f(u + 1)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{2 \cdot 25 - 16} \right) = \frac{225}{17} < 14.$$

Notice also that Equation (143) can be rearranged to give $(f(u + 1)w'^2 - 8)y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 8f(u + 1)w'^2$, so $f(u + 1)w'^2 > 8$. So $9 \leq f(u + 1)w'^2 \leq 13$, and since $f(u + 1)$ is odd and square-free, we have only the following possibilities:

- (a) $w' = 1$ and $f(u + 1) = 11, 13$; here Equation (143) gives $(f(u + 1) - 8)y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 8f(u + 1)$.
- (b) $w' = 2$ and $f(u + 1) = 3$; here Equation (143) gives $y''^2 = z'^2 + 24$.
- (c) $w' = 3$ and $f(u + 1) = 1$; here Equation (143) gives $y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 72$.

In the first case, with $f(u + 1) = 11$, the equation is $3y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 88$, which has no solution modulo 32. In the first case, with $f(u + 1) = 13$, the equation is $5y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 104$, which has no solution modulo 16. In the third case, the equation is $y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 72$ has no solution modulo 16.

It remains to deal with the second case, where the equation $y''^2 = z'^2 + 24$ has the solution $y'' = 5, z' = 1$. Note that in this case $f(u + 1) = 3$. But $u = 2n^2$ and

the smallest value of $n > 1$ for which $f(u + 1) = 3$ is $n = 11$. Here $u = 242$ and Inequality (136) gives

$$f(u + 1)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{242 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{2 \cdot 25 - 16} \right) = \frac{24300}{2057} < 12,$$

contradicting the assumption that $w' = 2$ and $f(u + 1) = 3$. □

From the preceding lemmas, we have $v = 1$ and $u = 2$. By Inequality (135), we have $2y''^2 > 16$, so $y'' \geq 3$. We have $f(u + v) = 3$ and so Inequality (136) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{2 \cdot 9 - 16} \right) = 36,$$

so $w' \leq 5$. Moreover, Equation (134) gives

$$(3w'^2 - 8)y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 24w'^2, \tag{144}$$

so $w' \geq 2$. So there are four possibilities.

If $w' = 5$, Equation (144) gives $67y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 600$, which has no solutions modulo 32.

If $w' = 4$, Equation (144) gives $10y''^2 = z'^2 + 96$ (which has the solution $y'' = 4, z' = 8$). But by Inequality (133), we have $y'' > z'$, so $10y''^2 = z'^2 + 96$ gives $9y''^2 < 96$, giving $y'' \leq 3$. So, as $y'' \geq 3$, from above, we have $y'' = 3$. But then $10y''^2 = z'^2 + 96$ has no integer solution for z' .

If $w' = 3$, Equation (144) gives $19y''^2 = 4z'^2 + 216$, which has no solution modulo 32.

Finally, if $w' = 2$, Equation (144) gives $y''^2 = z'^2 + 24$, which has the solution $y'' = 5, z' = 1$. Note that in this case

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{2}f(u + v)f(u)v f(v)w'^2 = 3w'^2 = 12,$$

and $\Sigma' = \frac{u}{v}\Sigma = 24$. This is our desired Case 4 solution.

Case 5. Assume u, v are both odd and the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is even.

We will show that there are no solutions in this case.

As x is an integer, from Equation (92) we can write $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)w^2$, for some w . Note v divides Σ , so v divides w^2 , and hence $f(v)s(v)$ divides w . Thus, setting $w = f(v)s(v)w'$ we may write $\Sigma = 2f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$. Then Equation (91) gives

$$f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 4(z^2 + vf(u)y'^2). \tag{145}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $4z^2$, so $f(v)s(v)f(u)$ divides z , say $z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$. So Inequality (90) gives $vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$ and hence

$$s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z', \tag{146}$$

and Equation (145) gives

$$f(u + v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 4(f(v)f(u)z'^2 + y'^2). \tag{147}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides y' . Let $y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (146) gives $f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z'$ and so

$$vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2, \tag{148}$$

and Equation (147) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = 4(f(u)z'^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{149}$$

Now, Inequality (148) and Equation (149) give

$$uf(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) < 4(v + u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{4}{f(v + u)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right)$$

and consequently

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{150}$$

Remark 28. Note that using the hypothesis that the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is even, one has

$$f(u) + f(v) \equiv u + v \equiv 0 \pmod{4}.$$

In particular, $f(u)$ and $f(v)$ are not both 1.

Lemma 36. *The following conditions hold.*

- (a) $f(u) \leq 19$.
- (b) $f(v) \leq 5$.
- (c) *If $y'' > 1$, then $f(u) \leq 7$.*

Proof. (a). For $f(u) \geq 21$, we have $uf(u) \geq 21^2$, so for all $y'' \geq 1$, Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{21^2} + \frac{1}{21} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{21 - 16} \right) = \frac{88}{105} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(b). Suppose $f(v) \geq 7$. Then Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{49} + \frac{1}{7} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{224}{327} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(c). Suppose $y'' \geq 2$ and $f(u) > 7$. As $f(u)$ is a square-free odd number, $f(u) \geq 11$. Then Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{11^2} + \frac{1}{11} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{11 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{48}{77} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 37. *We have $f(v) = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $f(v) > 3$. By Lemma 36(b), $f(v) = 5$. Then by Remark 28, $f(u) \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, and in particular, $f(u) \geq 3$ and so $u \geq 3$. Then Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{25 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{5 \cdot 9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{125 \cdot 3 - 16} \right) = \frac{160}{1077} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) = 1$ or 3 . Suppose that $f(v) = 3$. So $v \geq 3$. By Remark 28, $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Suppose for the moment that $f(u) \geq 5$. Then $u \geq 5$ and Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{5^2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{3^2 \cdot 5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 \cdot 5 - 16} \right) = \frac{96}{595} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 1$.

As u, v are relatively prime, and as v is divisible by 3 since $f(v) = 3$, we have $u \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Furthermore, as $f(u) = 1$, u is a square. So $u \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and thus $u + v \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and hence $f(u + v) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. By Inequality (150),

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{48}{11} < 5,$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . In particular, $w'^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Then using $f(u) = 1$ in Equation (149) gives $f(u + v)w'^2(9vy''^2 - 16) = 4(z'^2 + 3y''^2)$, and modulo 3 we have $z'^2 \equiv -1$, which is impossible. So $f(v) = 1$. □

Lemma 38. *We have $v = 1$.*

Proof. By the previous lemma, $f(v) = 1$, so v is an odd square, $v = m^2$ say. Suppose that $v > 1$, so $v \geq 9$. By Remark 28, $f(u) \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. So $f(u) \geq 3$. Note that if $f(u) \geq 7$, then $u \geq 7$ and so Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{7^2} + \frac{1}{7 \cdot 9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 7 - 16} \right) = \frac{64}{329} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So if $v > 1$, then $f(u) = 3$. In this case, u is divisible by 3 and so as u, v are relatively prime, by hypothesis, we have $v \geq 25$. Then Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3 \cdot 25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 3 - 16} \right) = \frac{112}{177} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Thus $v = 1$. □

Lemma 39. *We have $f(u) = 3$.*

Proof. From the previous lemma, $v = 1$. From Inequality (148) we have $y'' > f(u)z' \geq 1$. So from Lemma 36(c) we have $f(u) \leq 7$. Suppose $f(u) = 7$. Then $u \geq 7$ and from Inequality (148) we have $y'' > 7z' \geq 7$. So $y'' \geq 8$. Then Inequality (150) gives

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{7^2} + \frac{1}{7} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7 \cdot 8^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{128}{189} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) \leq 5$ and since $f(u) \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, we have $f(u) = 3$. □

From the above lemmas, we have $v = 1$ and $f(u) = 3$. From Inequality (148), we have $y'' > f(u)z' \geq 3$. Then by Inequality (150),

$$w'^2 < 4 \left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{48}{11} < 5,$$

so $w' = 1$ or 2 . In particular, $w'^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. As $f(u) = 3$, we have that u is divisible by 3. So $u + v \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and hence $f(u + v) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Substituting $v = 1, f(u) = 3$ in Equation (149) gives $f(u + v)w'^2(3y''^2 - 16) = 4(3z'^2 + y''^2)$, and thus modulo 3 we obtain $y''^2 \equiv -1$, which is impossible. So there are no solutions in Case 5.

Case 6. Assume u, v are both odd and the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is odd.

We will show that in this case, one of the following holds:

- (a) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (9, 9)$ or $(16, 16)$,
- (b) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (m^2, 1)$, for some integer m satisfying the equations $m^2 + 1 = 2n^2$ and $(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$ for some integers n, Y, Z ,

- (c) $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (5m^2, 5)$, for some integer m satisfying the equations $m^2 + 1 = 10n^2$ and $(5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$ for some integers n, Y, Z .

As x is an integer, from Equation (92) we can write $2\Sigma = f(u + v)f(u)w^2$. Note v divides Σ , so v divides w^2 , and hence $f(v)s(v)$ divides w . Thus, setting $w = f(v)s(v)w'$ we may write $2\Sigma = f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2$. Then Equation (91) gives

$$f(u + v)f(u)f(v)vw'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 16(z^2 + vf(u)y'^2). \tag{151}$$

Thus $vf(u)$ divides $16z^2$, so $f(v)s(v)f(u)$ divides z , say $z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$. So Inequality (90) gives $vy' > s(u)f(v)s(v)f(u)z'$ and hence

$$s(v)y' > f(u)s(u)z', \tag{152}$$

and Equation (151) gives

$$f(u + v)f(v)w'^2(vf(u)y'^2 - 16) = 16(f(v)f(u)z'^2 + y'^2). \tag{153}$$

Hence, $f(v)$ divides y' . Let $y' = f(v)y''$. Then Inequality (152) gives $f(v)s(v)y'' > f(u)s(u)z'$ and so

$$vf(v)y''^2 > uf(u)z'^2, \tag{154}$$

and Equation (153) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) = 16(f(u)z'^2 + f(v)y''^2). \tag{155}$$

Note that from the left-hand side of Equation (155), we have

$$vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 > 16. \tag{156}$$

Furthermore, Inequality (154) and Equation (155) give

$$uf(u + v)w'^2(vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16) < 16(v + u)f(v)y''^2.$$

Hence,

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{f(u + v)} \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right) \tag{157}$$

and consequently, as $f(u + v) \geq 2$,

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{uf(u)f(v)} + \frac{1}{vf(v)f(u)} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{vf^2(v)f(u)y''^2 - 16} \right). \tag{158}$$

Remark 29. As the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is odd, one has

$$f(u) + f(v) \equiv u + v \equiv 2 \pmod{4}.$$

Lemma 40. *The following conditions hold.*

- (a) $f(u) \leq 23$.
- (b) $f(v) \leq 7$.
- (c) *If $y'' > 1$, then $f(u) \leq 11$.*

Proof. (a). If $f(u) > 23$, then as $f(u)$ is square-free, $f(u) \geq 29$, so for all $y'' \geq 1$, Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{29^2} + \frac{1}{29} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{29 - 16} \right) = \frac{240}{377} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(b). If $f(v) > 7$, then as $f(v)$ is square-free, $f(v) \geq 11$, and Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{121} + \frac{1}{11} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{11^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{1056}{1315} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction.

(c). If $y'' \geq 2$ and $f(u) \geq 13$, then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{13^2} + \frac{1}{13} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{13 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{112}{117} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 41. *We have $f(v) = 1$.*

Proof. By Lemma 40(b), $f(v) \leq 7$. First suppose $f(v) = 7$. Then by Remark 29, $f(u) \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, and in particular, $f(u) \geq 3$ and so $u \geq 3$. Then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{49 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{7 \cdot 9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{7^3 \cdot 3 - 16} \right) = \frac{560}{3039} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) \leq 5$.

Now, suppose that $f(v) = 5$. Then by Remark 29, $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Suppose for the moment that $f(u) > 1$. Then as u, v are relatively prime and v is divisible by 5, we have $f(u) \geq 13$. So Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{13^2 \cdot 5} + \frac{1}{5^2 \cdot 13} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5^3 \cdot 13 - 16} \right) = \frac{720}{20917} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) = 1$. Hence, u is an odd square. Suppose for the moment that $u > 1$. Then $u \geq 9$ and Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{9 \cdot 5} + \frac{1}{5^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{560}{981} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $u = 1$. Notice that as $f(v) = 5$ we have $v = 5m^2$ for some odd m and so $u + v = 1 + 5m^2$. In particular, $f(u + v) \neq 2$ as otherwise $1 + 5m^2 = 2r^2$ for some r . But this equation has no solution modulo 5. So, as the 2-adic order of $u + v$ is odd, we have $f(u + v) \geq 6$. Then Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{6} \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{5^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5^3 - 16} \right) = \frac{80}{109} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) \neq 5$.

Now, suppose that $f(v) = 3$. By Remark 29, $f(u) \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. So as u, v are relatively prime, and as v is divisible by 3, we have $f(u) \neq 3$, so $f(u) \geq 7$. Then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{7^2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{3^2 \cdot 7} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{3^3 \cdot 7 - 16} \right) = \frac{240}{1211} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(v) = 1$. □

Lemma 42. *If $v = 1$, then $f(u) = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose $v = 1$. From Inequality (154) we have $y'' > f(u)z' \geq 1$. Thus from Lemma 40(c) we have $f(u) \leq 11$. Moreover, as $v = 1$, we have $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, by Remark 29. Thus, as $f(u)$ is square-free, $f(u) \leq 5$. Suppose $f(u) = 5$. Then from Inequality (154) we have $y'' > 5z' \geq 5$. So $y'' \geq 6$. Then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5 \cdot 6^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{432}{205} < 3.$$

So $w' = 1$. Then Equation (155) gives $f(u + v)(5y''^2 - 16) = 16(5z'^2 + y''^2)$, so

$$(5f(u + v) - 16)y''^2 = 80z'^2 + 16f(u + v) > 0.$$

So $f(u + v) > 16/5$. Thus, as $u + v$ is even and square-free, $f(u + v) \geq 6$. Hence, Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{6} \left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{5} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{5 \cdot 6^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{144}{205} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) < 5$ and since $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, we have $f(u) = 1$. □

Lemma 43. *If $v = 1$, then $u = 1$ and $w' = 3$ or 4 .*

Proof. Suppose $v = 1$. By the previous lemma, $f(u) = 1$. Then Equation (155) gives $f(u + v)w'^2(y''^2 - 16) = 16(z'^2 + y''^2)$, and so

$$(f(u + v)w'^2 - 16)y''^2 = 16(z'^2 + f(u + v)w'^2). \tag{159}$$

From Inequality (156), we have $y'' > 4$. Thus $y'' \geq 5$. So Inequality (157) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{u} + 1 \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{16 \cdot 25}{9} \left(\frac{1}{u} + 1 \right). \tag{160}$$

In particular, as $w' \geq 1$ and $u \geq 1$, this gives $f(u + v) < \frac{16 \cdot 25 \cdot 2}{9} = \frac{800}{9}$, so $f(u + v) \leq 88$. Moreover, $f(u + v)$ is even and square-free, and furthermore, as u is an odd square, say $u = n^2$, and $n^2 + 1 = f(u + v)m^2$, where $m = s(u + v)$, we have that -1 is a quadratic residue modulo $f(u + v)$. Hence, as $f(u + v)$ is square-free, $f(u + v)$ cannot be divisible by a prime congruent to 3 modulo 4. It follows that the only possible values of $f(u + v)$ are:

$$2, 10, 26, 34, 58, 74, 82.$$

Notice also that by Equation (159), we have $f(u + v)w'^2 > 16$, so $w' \geq 2$ for $f(u + v) = 10$ and $w' \geq 3$ for $f(u + v) = 2$.

Let us assume for the moment that $u > 1$. So, as $f(u) = 1$, we have $u \geq 9$. Then from Inequality (154), we have $y''^2 > uz'^2 \geq 9z'^2$. Moreover, Inequality (160) gives $f(u + v) < \frac{16 \cdot 25}{9} \left(\frac{1}{9} + 1 \right) = \frac{4000}{81} < 50$, so $f(u + v) \leq 34$. For the resulting four cases of $f(u + v)$ we have:

- (a) If $f(u + v) = 34$, then Inequality (160) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 25}{34 \cdot 9} \left(\frac{1}{9} + 1 \right) = \frac{2000}{1377} < 2$, so $w' = 1$. Then Equation (159) gives $9y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 34)$, which is impossible modulo 3.
- (b) If $f(u + v) = 26$, then Inequality (160) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 25}{26 \cdot 9} \left(\frac{1}{9} + 1 \right) = \frac{2000}{1053} < 2$, so $w' = 1$. Then Equation (159) gives $5y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 26)$. So as $y''^2 > 9z'^2$, we have $45z'^2 < 8(z'^2 + 26)$; i.e., $z''^2 < \frac{8 \cdot 26}{37}$, so $z'' \leq 2$. But $5y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 26)$ has no integer solution for y'' when $z' = 1$ or $z' = 2$.
- (c) If $f(u + v) = 10$, then Inequality (160) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 25}{10 \cdot 9} \left(\frac{1}{9} + 1 \right) = \frac{400}{81} < 5$, so $w' \leq 2$. But $w' \geq 2$ for $f(u + v) = 10$, as we observed above, so $w' = 2$. Then Equation (159) gives $3y''^2 = 2(z'^2 + 40)$, which is impossible modulo 3.
- (d) If $f(u + v) = 2$, then Inequality (160) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 25}{2 \cdot 9} \left(\frac{1}{9} + 1 \right) = \frac{2000}{81} < 25$, so $w' \leq 4$. But $w' \geq 3$ for $f(u + v) = 2$, as we observed above, so $w' = 3$ or 4 .
 - (i) If $w' = 3$, then Equation (159) gives $y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 18)$. But then $y''^2 > 9z'^2$ gives $z'^2 < 8 \cdot 18$, so $z' \leq 11$. But for none of these values does $y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 18)$ have an integer solution for y'' . So this case is impossible.

- (ii) If $w' = 4$, then Equation (159) gives $y''^2 = z'^2 + 32$. But then $y''^2 > 9z'^2$ gives $z'^2 < 4$, so $z' = 1$. However then $y''^2 = z'^2 + 32$ has no integer solution for y'' . So this case is also impossible.

We conclude from the above that $u = 1$. So $f(u + v) = 2$ and Inequality (160) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 25 \cdot 2}{2 \cdot 9} = \frac{400}{9} < 45$, so $w' \leq 6$. But $w' \geq 3$ for $f(u + v) = 2$, as we observed above, so $w' = 3, 4, 5$ or 6 . We will now eliminate the possibilities that $w' = 5$ or 6 .

- (a) If $w' = 5$, then Equation (159) gives $17y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 50)$. From Inequality (154), $y''^2 > uz'^2 \geq z'^2$. So $9z''^2 < 8 \cdot 50$ and hence $z'' \leq 6$. But for none of these values does $17y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 50)$ have an integer solution for y'' . So this case is impossible.
- (b) If $w' = 6$, then Equation (159) gives $7y''^2 = 2(z'^2 + 72)$, which is impossible modulo 7.

□

Lemma 44. *If $v > 1$, then $u = 1$, $w' = 1$ and either $f(u + v) = 2$ or $f(u + v) = 10$.*

Proof. By the previous lemma, $f(v) = 1$, so v is an odd square, $v = m^2$ say. Suppose $m \geq 3$. Note that $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, by Remark 29. If $f(u) \geq 5$, then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{5 \cdot 9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 5 - 16} \right) = \frac{112}{145} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $f(u) < 5$ and since $f(u) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, we have $f(u) = 1$.

First suppose that $v = 9$. Substituting $v = 9, f(u) = 1$ in Equation (155) gives $f(u + v)w'^2(9y''^2 - 16) = 16(z'^2 + y''^2)$, and so

$$(9f(u + v)w'^2 - 16)y''^2 = 16(z'^2 + f(u + v)w'^2).$$

From Inequality (156), we have $9y''^2 > 16$. Thus $y'' \geq 2$. So Inequality (157) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{u} + \frac{1}{9} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{9 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{16 \cdot 9}{5} \left(\frac{1}{u} + \frac{1}{9} \right). \tag{161}$$

Let us assume for the moment that $u > 1$. So, as $f(u) = 1$ and $\gcd(u, v) = 1$, we have $u \geq 25$. Then $w' \geq 1$ and Inequality (161) give $f(u + v) < \frac{16 \cdot 9}{5} \left(\frac{1}{25} + \frac{1}{9} \right) = \frac{544}{125} < 5$ so, as $f(u + v)$ is even and square-free, $f(u + v) = 2$. Then we have $m^2 + 9 = 2n^2$ for some n . But considering this equation modulo 3, it follows that n, m are both divisible by 3, contradicting the hypothesis that $\gcd(u, v) = 1$.

So $u = 1$. Thus, $f(u + v) = u + v = 10$. Furthermore, Inequality (161) gives $w'^2 < \frac{16 \cdot 9}{10 \cdot 5} (1 + \frac{1}{9}) = \frac{16}{5} < 4$, so $w' = 1$, as required.

Now, suppose that $v > 9$, so $v \geq 25$. As $f(u) = 1$, so u, v are both odd squares. First suppose that if $u \geq 49$. Then since $v \geq 25$, Inequality (157) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2 < 16 \left(\frac{1}{49} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{1184}{441} < 3.$$

So necessarily $f(u + v) = 2$ and $w' = 1$. Then Equation (155) gives $vy''^2 - 16 = 8(z'^2 + y''^2)$, so as v is odd, y'' is divisible by 4. But then Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{49} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 4^2 - 16} \right) = \frac{74}{147} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $u = 1, 9$ or 25 . If $u = 25$, then since u, v are relatively prime, we have $v \geq 49$ and thus Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{25} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 - 16} \right) = \frac{592}{825} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $u = 1$ or 9 .

Suppose $u = 9$. Then $u + v = 9 + m^2$, and if $f(u + v) = 2$, then $u + v = 2r^2$, for some r , and thus $9 + m^2 = 2r^2$. Modulo 3 this would give $m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, contradicting the assumption that u, v are relatively prime. Hence, $f(u + v) > 2$. In this case, using again the fact that u, v are relatively prime, we would have $f(u + v) \geq 10$. Thus, if $v \geq 49$, then Inequality (157) would give

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{10} \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 - 16} \right) = \frac{464}{1485} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, $v = 25$. But in this case, $f(u + v) = 34$ and Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{34} \left(\frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{16}{81} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $u \neq 9$.

Finally, suppose $u = 1$. Thus Equation (155) gives

$$f(u + v)w'^2(vy''^2 - 16) = 16(z'^2 + y''^2). \tag{162}$$

First suppose that $v = 25$. Then $f(1 + v) = 26$. Note that if $y'' > 1$, then Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{26} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{16}{21} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So $y'' = 1$. Then Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{26} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{25} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{25 - 16} \right) = \frac{16}{9} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. Substituting in Equation (162) gives $8z''^2 = 109$, which has no integer solution. Hence, $v > 25$ and thus $v \geq 49$.

For $v \geq 49$, Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 - 16} \right) = \frac{400}{33} < 13,$$

so $w' \leq 3$. Suppose for the moment that y'' is odd. Then working modulo 4, as v is odd and $f(u+v) \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, we conclude from Equation (162) that w' is even. So $w' \leq 3$ gives $w' = 2$. Then Equation (162) gives $f(u+v)(vy''^2 - 16) = 4(z''^2 + y''^2)$, and working modulo 4 again gives a contradiction. Thus y'' is even, say $y'' = 2y'''$, and Equation (162) gives

$$f(u+v)w'^2(vy'''^2 - 4) = 4(z''^2 + 4y'''^2). \tag{163}$$

As $y'' = 2y''' \geq 2$, Inequality (158) gives

$$w'^2 < 8 \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{80}{9} < 9,$$

so $w' \leq 2$.

Note that if $f(u+v) \geq 18$, then for $y'' \geq 2$, Inequality (157) would give

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{18} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{80}{81} < 1,$$

which is a contradiction. So as $f(u+v)$ is even and square-free, $f(u+v) = 2, 6, 10$ or 14 . But $u+v = 1+m^2$ and -1 is not a quadratic residue modulo 6 or 14. So $f(u+v) = 2$ or 10 . If $f(u+v) = 10$, then Inequality (157) gives

$$w'^2 < \frac{16}{10} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{49} \right) \left(1 + \frac{16}{49 \cdot 4 - 16} \right) = \frac{16}{9} < 2,$$

so $w' = 1$. We will show that one also has $w' = 1$ when $f(u+v) = 2$. Indeed, suppose $f(u+v) = 2$ and $w' = 2$. Then Equation (163) gives $2(vy'''^2 - 4) = z''^2 + 4y'''^2$. As $f(u+v) = 2$, we have $v = m^2 = 2n^2 - 1$ for some n . So we have

$$2(2n^2 - 3)y'''^2 - 8 = z''^2.$$

However, this equation has no solution for n, y''', z'' modulo 64. So $w' = 1$. □

If $v = 1$, then from Lemma 43, $u = 1$ and $w' = 3$ or 4 . Then Equation (155) gives $w'^2(y''^2 - 16) = 8(z'^2 + y''^2)$.

- (a) If $w' = 3$, then we have $y''^2 = 8(z'^2 + 18)$. This equation has infinitely many solutions. Here $\Sigma = \frac{1}{2}f(u+v)f(u)vf(v)w'^2 = 9$, and $\Sigma' = \Sigma$. So this is one of our desired solutions.
- (b) If $w' = 4$, then we have $y''^2 = z'^2 + 32$. This has two solutions ($y'' = 6, z' = 2$ and $y'' = 9, z' = 7$). Here $\Sigma = \frac{1}{2}f(u+v)f(u)vf(v)w'^2 = 16$, and $\Sigma' = \Sigma$. So this is another one of our desired solutions.

If $v > 1$, then from Lemma 41, $f(v) = 1$ so $v = m^2$ for some odd m , and from Lemma 44, $u = 1, w' = 1$ and either $f(u+v) = 2$ or $f(u+v) = 10$. Then Equation (155) gives $(f(u+v)m^2 - 16)y''^2 = 16f(u+v) + 16z'^2$. Then as m is odd and $f(u+v) = 2$ or 10 , we have that y'' is divisible by 4 , say $y'' = 4Y$. So $(f(u+v)m^2 - 16)Y^2 = f(u+v) + z'^2$. Working modulo 8 we see that Y is necessarily odd and $z'^2 \equiv 0$, so z' is divisible by 4 , say $z' = 4Z$. So we have

$$\left(\frac{f(u+v)}{2}m^2 - 8\right)Y^2 = \frac{f(u+v)}{2} + 8Z^2. \tag{164}$$

Furthermore, $\Sigma = \frac{1}{2}f(u+v)f(u)vf(v)w'^2 = \frac{f(u+v)}{2}m^2$, and $\Sigma' = \frac{u}{v}\Sigma = \frac{f(u+v)}{2}$.

Thus when $f(u+v) = 2$, we have $(\Sigma, \Sigma') = (m^2, 1)$. Furthermore, there exists n such that

$$m^2 + 1 = 2n^2 \text{ and } (m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2, \tag{165}$$

where the latter equation comes from Equation (164). Similarly, when $f(u+v) = 10$, there exists n such that

$$m^2 + 1 = 10n^2 \text{ and } (5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2. \tag{166}$$

So these are the two desired families of solutions. This completes the proof of Theorem 4.

Remark 30. Consider the integers m for which there exists n with $m^2 + 1 = 10n^2$, as in (166). It is easy to see that m is necessarily divisible by 3 . The numbers $m/3$ are well known; see entry A097314 of [37]. The first eight values of m are: $3, 117, 4443, 168717, 6406803, 243289797, 3079535161, 116941239519$.

Remark 31. Suppose that in the case $u = 1, v = m^2$ at the end of the above proof, we have a solution m, n, Y, Z to (165) or (166). From Equation (92), as $y = y' = y'' = 4Y$, and $u + v = 1 + m^2 = f(u+v)n^2$ and $\Sigma = \frac{f(u+v)}{2}m^2$, we have

$$x = \sqrt{\frac{y'^2 f(u)(u+v)\Sigma}{8}} = f(u+v)mnY.$$

Moreover, $z = f(v)s(v)f(u)z' = mz' = 4mZ$ and from Definition 5, $x = a + b, y = a - c, z = c - b$.

For $f(u + v) = 2$, we have $x = 2mnY$ and solving gives, using $d = a + b - c$,

$$\begin{aligned} a &= (mn + 2)Y + 2mZ, & b &= (mn - 2)Y - 2mZ, \\ c &= (mn - 2)Y + 2mZ, & d &= (mn + 2)Y - 2mZ. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that as $m < \sqrt{2}n$, we have $\Sigma = m^2 < 4mn = 8\frac{a+b}{a-c}$. Hence, by Remark 18, all such extangential LEQs (if any exist) are necessarily convex.

Similarly, for $f(u + v) = 10$, we have $x = 10mnY$ and solving gives

$$\begin{aligned} a &= (5mn + 2)Y + 2mZ, & b &= (5mn - 2)Y - 2mZ, \\ c &= (5mn - 2)Y + 2mZ, & d &= (5mn + 2)Y - 2mZ. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that as $m < \sqrt{10}n$, we have $\Sigma = 5m^2 < 20mn = 8\frac{a+b}{a-c}$. Hence, by Remark 18, all such extangential LEQs are necessarily convex.

Remark 32. Note that we now have all the ingredients for the proof of Corollary 3 from the introduction. The proof for the LEQs of Theorem 3 Parts (b) and (c) are given in the previous remark. The proof for the LEQs of Theorem 3 Part (a) were given in Subsection 3.3; see Remark 19 and the analysis of LEQs with $(\Sigma, T) = (18, 50)$.

Remark 33. We mention that in the case $m = 3$ of (166), the equation $(5m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$ gives $37Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$, which is equivalent to Equation (83) in Subsection 3.3; the connection is given by setting $W = 111Y + 52Z$.

Example 5. We now exhibit an extangential LEQ corresponding to the case $m = 117$ of (166). This is the case $n = 37$ in Theorem 3(b). According to [6], the smallest solution to $(5 \cdot 117^2 - 8)Y^2 = 5 + 8Z^2$ is

$$Y = 34884218483995340806373, \quad Z = 3226483779786979759026161.$$

The formulas from Remark 31 give

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 1510135881993200406047678005, & b &= 1936178957897460209165, \\ c &= 1509996345119264424684452513, & d &= 141473052893878823434657. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (640848245491383541211578005, 1367415046112187810865469000), \\ B &= (640849067137238673279485480, 1367416799305572965277883040), \\ C &= (60036158873125939312368, 128102631990427959679265). \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to verify that the points O, A, B, C form the vertices of an extangential LEQ with side lengths a, b, c, d as given above (see the explanation below). This LEQ has $(\Sigma, T) = (5 \cdot 117^2, 5 + 5 \cdot 117^2)$. Note that the perimeter is $a + b + c + d \cong 3.0 \cdot 10^{27}$.

Let us briefly explain how the above vertices were determined. First factor a and note that each prime factor is congruent to 1 modulo 4. Then for each factor α of a , consider all ways of writing α as a sum of two squares: $\alpha = \alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2$, where $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2 > 0$, and using the Pythagorean formula, consider the points $A_\alpha = \frac{a}{\alpha}(\alpha_1^2 - \alpha_2^2, 2\alpha_1\alpha_2)$ and $A_\alpha^* = \frac{a}{\alpha}(2\alpha_1\alpha_2, \alpha_1^2 - \alpha_2^2)$. Let P_a denote the union over α of all the sets $\{A_\alpha, A_\alpha^*\}$. Similarly, construct P_b, P_c and P_d . Then search for members S_a, S_b, S_c, S_d in P_a, P_b, P_c, P_d , respectively, such that $S_a + S_b = S_c + S_d$, and set $A = S_a, B = S_a + S_b, C = S_c$. By construction, the resulting quadrilateral $OABC$ has side lengths a, b, c, d . The extangential condition, $a + b = c + d$, is verified directly from the above values of a, b, c, d . Finally, check that

$$\det[S_a, S_b] > 0 \text{ and } \det[S_c, S_d] > 0,$$

which shows that $OABC$ is positively oriented and has no self-intersection, and check that the equability condition is satisfied, i.e.,

$$a + b + c + d = \frac{1}{2}(\det[S_a, S_b] + \det[S_c, S_d]).$$

3.6. Comments on the Open Problem

In this subsection we make some comments on the Open Problem stated in the Introduction. Suppose we have integers m, n, Y, Z such that the following two equations hold:

$$m^2 = 2n^2 - 1, \tag{167}$$

$$(m^2 - 8)Y^2 = 1 + 8Z^2. \tag{168}$$

For convenience, set $M = m^2 - 8$. We first make some elementary observations:

1. From Equation (167), m is odd. Then working modulo 4, as $m^2 = 2n^2 - 1$ and m odd, n is also odd, and hence from Equation (168), Y and M are also odd.
2. Working modulo 3, $2n^2 - 1 \equiv \pm 1$. So from Equation (167), m is not divisible by 3. Thus $m^2 \equiv 1$, so from Equation (167) again, n is not divisible by 3. Hence, $M \equiv 2$. Thus, from Equation (168), Y is necessarily divisible by 3, and Z is not divisible by 3.
3. Working modulo 7, the quadratic residues are 0, 1, 2 and 4. So $2n^2 - 1$ is 0, ± 1 or 3. So as $m^2 = 2n^2 - 1$, we conclude that m^2 is 0 or 1. Then $M \equiv -1$ or 0.

i	μ_i	Factorization of $M_i = 49\mu_i^2 - 8$	Factors mod 8
0	1	41	1
1	199	23·239·353	7·7·1
2	39401	79·103·599·15607	7·7·7·7
3	7801199	47·6771937·9369319	7·1·7
4	1544598001	41·45245801·63018038201	1·1·1
5	305822602999	41·71·239·424577·865087·17934071	1·7·7·1·7·7
6	60551330795801	223·2297·37223·302663·3553471·8761009	7·1·7·7·7·1

Table 10: The first 7 solutions to $m^2 = 2n^2 - 1$ with $m \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$.

But if $M \equiv 0$ then Equation (168) gives $Z^2 \equiv -1$, which is impossible. So m is divisible by 7.

- The prime divisors of $m^2 - 8$ are all congruent to 1 modulo 8. Indeed, suppose p is a prime divisor of $m^2 - 8$. Then $8 \equiv m^2 \pmod{p}$. But it is well known that 8 is a quadratic residue modulo an odd prime p if and only if p is congruent to 1 or 7 modulo 8. So p is congruent to 1 or 7 modulo 8. But by Equation (168), p is also a prime divisor of $1 + 8Z^2$, so $-2 \equiv (4Z)^2 \pmod{p}$. But it is well known that -2 is a quadratic residue modulo an odd prime p if and only if p is congruent to 1 or 3 modulo 8. Hence, p is congruent to 1 modulo 8.

Let $m = 2r + 1$. Then $m^2 = 2n^2 - 1$ gives $4r^2 + 4r + 2 = 2n^2$, so $r^2 + (r + 1)^2 = n^2$. So the solutions (m, n) to Equation (167) correspond to Pythagorean triangles $(r, r + 1, n)$ whose base and height differ by 1. These triangles are well known; see entry A001652 of [37]. In particular, it is well known that the solutions r_0, r_1, r_2, \dots satisfy $r_i = 6r_{i-1} - r_{i-2} + 2$ with $r_0 = 0, r_1 = 3$. Let us denote the corresponding values of m by $m_i = 2r_i + 1$. So $m_i = 6m_{i-1} - m_{i-2}$ with $m_0 = 1, m_1 = 7$. As we saw in observation 3 above, we are only interested in values of m that are divisible by 7. Note that modulo 7, $m_i \equiv -m_{i-1} - m_{i-2}$, so $m_{i+1} \equiv -m_i - m_{i-1} \equiv m_{i-2}$. So, as $m_0 \equiv 1, m_1 \equiv 0, m_2 \equiv -1$, we are only interested in the values m_{1+3i} . Set $\mu_i := \frac{1}{7}m_{1+3i}$. The sequence $\mu_0, \mu_1, \mu_2, \dots$ is also well known; see entry A097732 of [37]. In particular, it is known to satisfy the relation $\mu_i = 198\mu_{i-1} - \mu_{i-2}$, with $\mu_0 = 1, \mu_1 = 199$.

Table 10 shows the first 7 values of μ_i and the prime divisors of the corresponding values of $M_i = 49\mu_i^2 - 8$. Notice that only for $\mu_0 = 1$ and $\mu_4 = 1544598001$ is every prime divisor of M_i congruent to 1 modulo 8, as required by Observation 4 above. So the other cases of Table 10 cannot be solutions to Equation (168).

Notice that for $MY^2 = 1 + 8Z^2$ we have $2MY^2 = X^2 + 2$, for $X = 4Z$. By [30, Theorem 5], $2MY^2 = X^2 + 2$ has no solution if the continued fraction expansion of $\sqrt{2M}$ has odd period length. In fact, this is the case for $m = 7\mu_0 = 7$ ($M = 41$); the continued fraction expansion of $\sqrt{82}$ is $9, \overline{18}$, which has odd period length $\ell(\sqrt{82}) =$

1. This shows that for $m = 7$, Equation (168) has no solutions. Another proof that Equation (168) has no solutions for $m = 7$ is given by using [40, Theorem 8] or [43]. According to these results, $MY^2 - 2W^2 = 1$ has no solution if $R^2 - 2MS^2 = -1$ has a solution. And in fact, for $M = 41$ ($m = 7$), $R^2 - 2MS^2 = -1$ has the solution $R = 9, S = 1$.

From Table 10, we see that the next potential solution would be for $m = 7\mu_4$. Here, already, the numbers are very large, and we have been unable to determine the continued fraction expansion of $\sqrt{2M_4}$. To see that there are no solutions for $m = 7\mu_4$, we require a deeper result, due to Wei. As we observed above, if we have a solution M, Y, Z to Equation (168), then $2MY^2 = X^2 + 2$, where $X = 4Z$.

Proposition 11 ([41, Prop. 4.4]). *Suppose that $M = p_1p_2 \dots p_j$, where $p_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ for each i . If the equation $2MY^2 = X^2 + 2$ has an integer solution X, Y , then*

$$\prod_{i=1}^j \left(\frac{2}{p_i}\right)_4 = 1,$$

where $(\cdot)_4$ denotes the quartic residue symbol (see [27, Chap. 5]).

Recall that $(\frac{2}{p_i})_4 = \pm 1$ and $(\frac{2}{p_i})_4 \equiv 2^{(p_i-1)/4} \pmod{p_i}$. From Table 10, we have $M_4 = p_1p_2p_3$, where $p_1 = 41, p_2 = 45245801, p_3 = 63018038201$. Calculations show that $(\frac{2}{p_i})_4 = -1$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Hence, by Wei's Proposition, there are no solutions to Equation (168) for $m = 7\mu_4$.

In fact, calculations show that for $7 \leq i \leq 155$, M_i has a prime divisor congruent to 7 modulo 8, so these cases also cannot be solutions to Equation (168). In establishing this, the only difficulty is in factorizing M_i . Once a factor congruent to 7 modulo 8 has been found, it is easy to verify that it is indeed a factor. To substantiate our claim, for each i with $7 \leq i \leq 155$ we exhibit an explicit prime divisor of M_i congruent to 7 modulo 8. Consider the following set of 62 primes congruent to 7 modulo 8:

$$P = \{23, 47, 71, 79, 103, 167, 191, 223, 239, 263, 311, 359, 431, 479, 607, 719, 887, 983, 1031, 1103, 1279, 1399, 1487, 1511, 1823, 1879, 2671, 2767, 3271, 3559, 4903, 4943, 6823, 7583, 8231, 23447, 39551, 53527, 72559, 153511, 167911, 255511, 625111, 869951, 1471271, 2593399, 10808983, 13980671, 39556927, 108732031, 125448527, 160812623, 209110079, 627025159, 9707524087, 181155438071, 291814585319, 3072313317767, 15238519898992991, 39834495682679591, 15327739968951498750119, 110095018941508669324502008759\}.$$

Now, consider the set

$$R = \{40, 9, 1, 4, 21, 1, 6, 5, 4, 15, 19, 55, 2, 1, 10, 9, 1, 48, 11, 2, 50, 4, 9, 8, 1, 41, 9, 1, 13, 4, 34, 22, 14, 9, 4, 1, 9, 59, 1, 61, 9, 5, 2, 9, 56, 26, 1, 4, 43, 1, 9, 32, 16, 46, 9, 4, 33, 1, 2, 58, 1, 9, 6, 5, 9, 2, 17, 27, 1, 28, 54, 1, 7, 4, 18, 5, 49, 15, 9, 1, 5, 2, 1, 29, 20, 9, 4, 37, 2, 6, 1, 30, 5, 1, 4, 36, 9, 5, 44, 4, 60, 1, 10, 3, 1, 62, 9, 4, 39, 5, 8, 2, 1, 9, 5, 1, 23, 9, 24, 51, 4, 57, 11, 1, 9, 4, 1, 2, 38, 31, 35, 5, 42, 4, 1, 52, 53, 1, 3, 45, 47, 9, 12, 5, 25, 1, 4, 8, 1\},$$

and let r_i denote the i -th member of R . The enthusiastic reader will easily verify that for each $1 \leq i \leq 149$, the r_i -th member of P is a divisor of M_{i+6} .

It follows from the above that the smallest possible value of m for which there could potentially be a solution to Equations (167) and (168) would have $m \geq 7\mu_{156}$. We do not know if there is a solution for $m = 7\mu_{156}$. In particular, we have been unable to find any factors of M_{156} , which is unsurprising as $M_{156} \cong 1.8 \cdot 10^{718}$.

Remark 34. Note that if a solution to Equations (167) and (168) exists, and there is an extangential LEQ corresponding to case (c) of Theorem 3, with sides a, b, c, d , then by Remark 31, its perimeter would be

$$2(a + b) = 4mnY > 4mn > 2\sqrt{2}m^2.$$

In particular, if there is an extangential LEQ corresponding to $m = 7\mu_{156}$, then the perimeter would be at least $5.0 \cdot 10^{718}$.

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